

STUDY OF THE TEMPORARY EVOLUTION OF THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF A POLLUTED SOIL IN OIL EXTRACTION FIELD FROM SUPLACU DE BARCĂU, BIHOR COUNTY, ROMANIA

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Abstract

Soil pollution from crude oil and other oil residues is one of the most common forms of pollution in oil extraction field.

The study on the evolution time of polluted soil with oil and oil residues was carried out over a period of 15 years (1997 - 2013) in oil extraction field from Suplacu de Barcău, Bihor county, Romania. The taxonomic unit of the soil on which the study was conducted was the type of luvisol, the albic subtype (albeluvisoil).

The area was outside the underground combustion fronts, it was homogeneous from the point of view of the relief, vegetation and groundwater, which is not under the influence of the groundwater layer and does not benefit from additional supply of rainwater from the surrounding areas.

After establishing the set of physico-chemical analyzes, in 1997 two soil profiles were opened in polluted soil (PS) and in unpolluted soil, the latter constituting a control variant (CS) in interpreting the results. The evolutionary changes of the physical indicators: structure and bulk density and chemical properties respectively: soil reaction, organic carbon, humus, total nitrogen and C / N ratio were followed.

During the study, there was a steady decrease in organic carbon from 8.78 % in 1997 to 2.8 % in 2013, the most significant being in the period 1997-2002.

Continuous decreases in organic carbon content were due to soil microbiological activity, which has become increasingly active, the toxic effect of the pollutant has decreased intensity. New organic compounds have been formed with different properties, which, through total mineralization, formed simple mineral compounds accessible to plant development, allowing the vegetation to be installed.

Thus, it has been shown that during the period 1997-2013 the natural attenuation of oil residues and crude oil from the soil occurred.

Key words: albeluvisoil, oil pollution, mineralization, toxicity, natural attenuation, physical and chemical properties of soil

INTRODUCTION

The presence of toxic organic components of oil residues in the soil has negative effects on agricultural ecosystems and ultimately on the health of the population (Aisien et al., 2015; Johnston et al., 2019).

The main cause of pollution of the soil with oil and oil residues is the accidents that occur in the oil extraction fields (Berchez, Stanciu, 2019).

Since hydrocarbons contain large amounts of organic carbon, the main component of soil organic matter, it influences all other chemical, physical and biological properties of soil (Colibaş et al., 1995).

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The most important physical properties of the soil that influence the process of hydrocarbon transformation in the soil are: the texture, by the percentage of colloidal clay and the structure that determines the density and porosity of the soil, with direct influences on the soil air regime.

Most of the total carbon and nitrogen content of soils is found in organic compounds. During the transformation and mineralization of organic matter, nutrients will be made available to the plants (Káta et al., 2019). Organic matter contributes to nutrient retention and rolling, soil structure, moisture retention and availability, pollutant degradation and carbon sequestration.

Biodegradation of pollutants from different environments, air, water or soil, consists in the attenuation, transformation or elimination of toxic substances through biological processes specific to the living world, plants, animals, microorganisms (Wang et al., 2012; Sabău, Șandor, 2018).

Bioremediation of oil-contaminated soils is produced under natural conditions, biodegradation of organic pollutants under the action of cultivated plants (phytoremediation) and microorganisms (bacteria, fungi, etc.) in the soil (Neag, 1997; Glick, 2010; Kovacs et al., 2012; Mohammadi-Sichani et al., 2017).

The bioremediation technology of soil contaminants, applied under natural conditions, without human intervention for intensifying biodegradation is known as natural attenuation (Wiedemeier et al., 1999; Sabău et al., 2013; Marić et al., 2018).

In recent years, the concept of improving natural attenuation (Enhanced Natural Mitigation) has been defined, which refers to the measures taken to initiate or intensify the natural attenuation process in order to reduce contaminants concentration from the environment faster (Onifade et al., 2007; Sabău et al., 2012; Odukoya, Lambert, 2015; Chikere et al., 2017).

To reduce the period of biodegradation, the natural attenuation process is stimulated, through various agro pedo improvement measures, which aim: improving soil aeration through deep loosening work; correcting soil acidity by applying amendments; application of organic and mineral fertilizers to stimulate vegetative growth of plants and the equilibration of the carbon/nitrogen (C/N) ratio (Zhao et al., 2015).

The location of the polluted soil is homogeneous from the point of view of the vegetation type, with groundwater at depths that do not influence the evolution of the profile, do not benefit from additional rainfall contribution from the neighboring lands and is not under the influence of the human factor.

The period of monitoring of the natural attenuation process of the pollutant is 15 years (1997-2013), being excluded the influence of all the anthropic factors that could influence the accuracy of the observations.

The objective of this work is to monitor the evolution of an albeluvisoil, polluted with oil residues, located on a land surface without crude oil extraction facilities, outside the underground combustion fronts, in the southeast part of Suplacu de Barcău, Bihor county, Romania.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The monitoring consisted of direct field observations on the appearance and development of vegetation and physico-chemical analysis at five-year intervals.

At the beginning of the observation period in 1997, two soil profiles were excavated, one in the polluted oil residue area (PS) and one in the immediate vicinity in an unpolluted area, considered as a control (CS). For the horizons of the two profiles of albeluvisol (Berchez, 2014), physical (texture, structure, bulk density, specific density, total porosity, wilting coefficient, field water capacity, maximum water holding capacity and available moisture holding capacity) and chemical analyzes (pH, organic carbon, humus, total nitrogen and carbon/nitrogen ratio) complete were performed.

Since the presence of the pollutant was identified, on the PS profile to a depth of 24 cm, in order to follow PS evolution over time, samples were taken from depths of 0-20 cm and 20-40 cm at intervals of 5 years (2002, 2007 and 2013). For each interval the structure, bulk density, reaction, organic carbon, humus, total nitrogen and carbon / nitrogen ratio were determined.

Field placement of soil profiles, field data collection and soil sampling were performed in accordance with the "Methodology of pedological studies" (Florea et al., 1987) and the methods used for physico-chemical analysis and interpretation of the results are those agreed by the standards in force.

1. Sample collection

In the first year of the research 1997, when were analyzed the two soil profiles (PS and CS), soil samples were collected from each horizon delimited on profile. For the determination of hydro physical properties, soil samples were collected in metal cylinders of known volume (100 cm³), in four repetitions. The samples for determining the chemical properties were collected in plastic bags.

For monitoring the quality evolution on PS, samples were collected for hydro physical and chemical analyzes from the horizon polluted with hydrocarbons and oil residues. There have been used two depths: 0-20 cm

(the surface horizon Ao) and 20-40 cm, which overlaps on the transition horizon AE to eluvial albic horizon Ea and partly the eluvial albic horizon. The samples for hydro physical analysis were collected in metal cylinders of known volume, in four repetitions and those for chemical determinations in plastic bags.

2. Sample analysis

For the two soil profiles (PS and CS) the texture was appreciated at the opening of the profiles, by the dry and wet examination of the soil from each horizon. The separation of the granulometric fractions (sand, dust and clay) in the laboratory followed the method of dry and wet sifting and the pipetting method, based on the principle of sedimentation speed of colloidal clay. The type of structure and the size of the structural aggregates was appreciated on the field when opening the profiles for each horizon.

Physical (specific density, bulk density and total porosity) and hydrophysical (wilting coefficient, field water capacity, maximum water holding capacity and available moisture holding capacity) properties were determined in the laboratory by analyzing soil samples collected in metal cylinders (Sabău, 2012).

The methods used to determine the chemical properties are soil reaction by potentiometric method in aqueous solution, organic carbon by the method of calcination and total nitrogen by the Kjeldahl method. The C / N ratio was calculated using the results of the above determinations.

The analyzes of the samples collected from the horizons of the two soil profiles (PS and CS) were carried out by the Office for Pedological and Agrochemical Studies Oradea, Bihor county.

Physico-chemical properties of soil samples collected from the polluted horizons of the PS, in the years 2002, 2007 and 2013 were determined in the Pedology Laboratory of the Faculty of Environmental Protection Oradea, using the same methods.

In order to highlight the evolution of polluted soil PS during the 15 years of monitoring and the natural attenuation of the pollutant due to biodegradation, the physico-chemical characteristics of PS from 2013 were compared with those of the initial profile (PS 1997) and the unpolluted control profile (CS 1997).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The general appearance of the soil surface in the researched area is flat, free from external drainage and the ground water is located at depths greater than 2 m. If in the unpolluted area of the control profile, the natural vegetation is grassy, medium developed (Fig. 1.a) on the polluted surface grassy vegetation is rare or lacking (Fig. 1.b).

a) b)
 Fig. 1. The appearance of the soil surface (1997):
 a) unpolluted soil (control); b) polluted soil

Physical properties. The differences between physicochemical properties of control soil profile (CS) and the polluted soil (PS), for 1997 are presented in table 1.

For both profiles, CS and PS the physical properties appreciated in the field are: high cohesiveness in wet and dry conditions; plastic in wet, solid and rough condition in a dry state; high wet adhesion; high compaction and unclear transition between Ao and AE horizons. On the surface with polluted soil the appearance is muddy and accentuated wetting, with high degree of compactness under natural humidity conditions and strong smell of hydrocarbons. On the PS profile it can see the thickness of pollutant infiltration of 24 cm.

The texture is sandy on a depth of 0 - 34 cm, sandy coarse clay on a depth of 34 - 60 cm and clay on a depth of 60 - 145 cm for the both profiles, CS and PS.

The soil structure of CS is poorly developed on a depth of 0-20 cm (Ao), poorly formed on a depth of 21-34 cm (AE), without a structure on a depth of 34-60 cm (Ea), prismatic on a depth of 60-120 cm (Bt) and nonspecific below. The PS does not have a structure on a depth of 0 - 60 cm, prismatic structure on a depth of 60-120 cm (Fig. 2) and unspecified below 120 cm.

If the bulk density and hydrophysical indices of CS have normal values for an albeluvisol (WRB-SR-1998) on the PS profile, the bulk density has high values in Ao (+0.22 g/cm³) and AE (+0,04 g/cm³) due to the high compaction degree as a result of the presence of the pollutant.

Hydrophysical indicators (Wilting coefficient, Field water capacity, Available moisture holding capacity and Maximum water holding capacity) present values different from those of the CS at the level of Ao and AE horizons due to the differences between Total porosity, that are – 8.14 % on Ao and – 1.40 on AE.

Chemical properties. The soil's reaction of CS and PS is moderately acidic on Ao, AE and Bt horizons and strongly acidic on the El horizon and the parental material C is slightly acidic.

Table 1.

The differences of physico-chemical properties between the control soil and the polluted soil at the level of 1997

Horizons	Control soil (CS)						Polluted soil (PS)					
	Ao	AE	Ea	Bt	C		Ao	AE ₁	AE ₂	Ea	Bt	C
Depths (cm)	0-20	21-34	35-60	61-120	121-145		0-20	21-24	25-34	35-62	62-122	123-145
Coarse sand (2.0-0.2 mm) %	6.2	9.5	13.2	3.8	1.2		6.2	9.5	9.5	13.2	3.8	1.2
Fine sand (0.2-0.02 mm) %	48.3	46.8	43.4	36.9	32.1		48.3	47.8	47.8	43.4	36.9	32.1
Dust (0.02-0.002 mm) %	14.6	14.3	24.9	25.6	23.8		14.6	13.3	13.3	24.9	25.6	23.8
Colloidal clay (> 0.002 mm) %	30.9	29.4	18.5	33.7	42.9		30.9	29.4	29.4	18.5	33.7	42.9
Texture	LN	LN	SG	TT	TT		LN	LN	LN	SG	TT	TT
Bulk density g/cm ³	1.42	1.46	1.52	-	-		1.64	1.59	1.46	1.52	-	-
Specific density g/cm ³	2.7	2.7	2.72	-	-		2.7	2.7	2.7	2.72	-	-
Wilting coefficient %	10.48	11.04	-	-	-		10.48	11.14	11.04	-	-	-
Field water capacity %	24.0	23.7	-	-	-		23.0	23.0	23.7	-	-	-
Available moisture holding capacity %	13.52	12.66	-	-	-		12.42	11.96	12.60	-	-	-
Maximum water holding capacity %	33.45	31.3	-	-	-		23.93	25.86	31.3	-	-	-
Total porosity %	47.4	46.0	-	-	-		39.26	41.12	46.0	-	-	-
pH (H ₂ O)	5.42	5.28	4.9	5.7	6.4		5.10	5.20	5.28	4.9	5.7	6.4
Organic carbon %	1.27	0.66	0.23	-	-		8.78	7.63	0.66	0.89	-	-
Humus %	2.20	1.34	0.40	-	-		15.14	13.15	1.14	1.53	-	-
Total nitrogen (%)	0.26	0.12	0.08	-	-		0.26	0.24	0.12	0.08	-	-
C / N ratio	4.9	5.5	2.9	-	-		33.76	31.79	5.5	2.9	-	-

Fig. 2. The appearance of polluted soil at the mobilization attempt (1997)

Compared to CS where the organic carbon content is low, PS organic carbon has high values in the Ao and AE horizons, on a depth of 0-24 cm, indicating pollution with organic substances. The CS content of humus is normal, whereas on PS it is very high but poor quality, corresponding to the high organic carbon content. The total nitrogen content are very low.

The C / N ratio on the polluted soil (PS) profile of 33.76 in the Ao horizon and 13.0 in the AE horizon, higher than the control soil (CS) profiles with 28.86 and 7.7, indicates the presence of organic pollutants in the soil.

Evolution of some physico-chemical indicators of polluted soil (PS) in the period 1997-2013.

In the 2002, the phenotypic characteristics of an oil polluted soil are still visible at the surface of the soil; the shallow presence of poorly developed grass vegetation, consisting of gramineae and muscels (Fig. 3.a).

After 10 years of observations (2007) on the surface of PS it is remarked: the presence of a grassland vegetation with medium density, consisting of gramineae species (Fig. 3.b) and the lack of oil pollution signals.

At the end of the observation period (2013) PS is occupied with agricultural crops (maize Fig. 3.d) due to the change in the category of use from pasture to arable. There is a more pronounced vegetative growth of the crops located on the former soils polluted in 1997, relative to the rest of the culture.

Fig. 3. The appearance of the PS surface in: a) 2002; b) 2007; c) 2010; d) 2013.

Table 2 presents the result of physico-chemical analyzes performed 15 years after the start of the study, in the period 1997-2013.

During the analysis of the polluted soil material, it was found that the soil structure recovered in time, evolving from the soil without structure (1997) to the medium developed granular structure (2013).

Also, the bulk density, the main physical property of the soil, indicates an improvement from a moderately compacted soil in the Ao horizon (1.64 g / cm^3) and respectively poorly compacted in AE₁ (1.52 g / cm^3) in the first year, to poor loosening, on both horizons (1.40 g / cm^3) in the last year.

The evolution of active acidity indicates an improvement in the chemical properties of PS. On the surface horizon the increase with 0.9 pH units causes the transition from the moderate acid range (pH = 5.1) to the weak acid range (pH = 6.0). In the AE₁ horizon, the increase of 0.34 pH units does not lead to another reaction class, the characterization remaining moderately acidic (pH = 5.36-5.7).

The decreasing the organic carbon content in the soil in the absence of human factor intervention is attributed to the triggering of self-regulatory mechanisms in the soil. The values of organic carbon indicators dropped in the Ao horizon from 8.78 % and in AE₁ from 7.63 % to 2.8 % in 2013. In the period 1997-2002, the most significant decreasing of organic carbon is registered. The considerable decrease in organic carbon values is mainly due to the intensification of the microbiological activity of the soil and the vegetation installation.

Total humus content for PS shows the same reduction trend as organic carbon content, but an increase in its quality can be suspected.

Table 2

Evolution of some physico-chemical indicators of polluted soil (PS) in the period
1997-2013

Years	PS (1997)	2002	2007	2013	CS (1997)
Horizons	Ao	Ao	Ao	Ao	Ao
Depths (cm)	0-20	0 – 20	0 - 20	0 - 20	0-20
Structure	Without structure	Incipient stages of formation of the granular structure	Low - Medium developed structure	Medium granular structure developed	Poorly developed structure
Bulk density g/cm ³	1.64	1.52	1.44	1.40	1.42
pH (H ₂ O)	5.1	5.4	5,9	6.0	5.42
Organic carbon %	8.78	6.62	3.46	2.8	1.27
Humus %	15,14	11,41	5,97	4.87	2.20
Total nitrogen %	0.26	0.37	0.37	0.4	0.26
C/N ratio	33.76	17.89	10.17	7.0	4.9
Horizons	AE1	AE₁	AE₁	AE₁	AE₁
Depths (cm)	20-40	20 – 40	20 - 40	20 - 40	20-40
Structure	Without structure	Incipient stages of formation of the grain structure	Low - Medium developed structure	Medium grain structure developed	Poorly developed structure
Bulk density g/cm ³	1.52	1.52	1.50	1.40	1.46
pH (H ₂ O)	5.36	5.2	5.4	5.7	5.28
Organic carbon %	7.63	6.84	3.92	2.8	0.66
Humus %	13.15	11,80	6,76	4.87	1.34
Total nitrogen %	0.24	0.31	0.31	0.4	0.12
C/N ratio	31.79	22.06	12.64	7.0	5.5

The percentage of total nitrogen increased in the Ao horizon by 0.14 percenters (from 0.26 to 0.40) and in AE₁ by 0.16 percenters (from 0.24 to 0.40). The percentage of total nitrogen remained constant between 2002 and 2007. The depth migration process of the N-soluble compounds formed can explain the constant value of the percentage of N in the period 2002-2007.

C / N ratio values dropped considerably from 33.76 to 7.0 in Ao and from 31.79 to 7.0 in AE₁, suggesting the shift from organic matter with early humification to a high quality humus.

The differences between the polluted soil (PS) after 15 years of evolution (2013) and the control soil (CS) unpolluted from 1997, on 0-24 cm depth are presented in figure 4.

Fig. 4. The differences of Organic carbon (%), Total nitrogen (%) and C/N ratio, between CS (1997) and PS (2013)

At the end of the observation period (2013), the organic carbon content is the equivalent of a soil with medium fertility. The percentage of total N is low, but higher than that of neighboring areas. The low value is attributed to the deep migration of N-formates, under a weak acid pH and the absence of bases in the soil.

The indicators considered for comparison with the control profile, (CS) on the 0-24 cm depth show higher values with 41.8 % for organic carbon, 60 % for total nitrogen content and 71.4 % for the C / N ratio.

After comparing at the end of the study the values of the indicators studied with the control values, it can be observed that the trophic properties of the polluted soil are slightly higher, being comparable to those of a fertile soil environment.

Discussion. Higher vegetal growths recorded on plants are due to organic carbon converted into humus during 15 years of soil evolution and to a higher percentage of total nitrogen than neighboring areas.

The distinction between the Ao horizon and the AE transition horizon is no longer clear due to the soil preparation work (28-30 cm deep) and crop maintenance.

During the study, there was a continuous decrease in the value of organic carbon from 8.78 % to 2.8 %, the most significant being in the

period 1997-2002. Decreasing the organic carbon content in the soil in the absence of human factor intervention was due to soil self-regulation mechanisms, the soil having its own mechanisms under the given climatic conditions to return to the original state.

The continuous decrease is due to the microbiological activity of the soil, which becomes more and more active, the toxic effect of the pollutant decreases, new organic compounds are formed with different properties, which, by total mineralization, form simple basic compounds accessible to the plant development.

With the decrease in organic carbon, the percentage of total nitrogen increased from 0.26 in 1997 to 0.4 in 2013 as a result of total mineralization of simple organic compounds resulting from oil decomposition. Increasing the percentage of total nitrogen and decreasing the percentage of organic carbon led to a decrease in the C / N ratio from 33.76 in the Ao horizon to 7.

In the analysis of the pollutant material of the soil was found the improvement of the soil structure, the continuous decrease of the percentage of organic carbon, the increase of the pH value, the increase of the total nitrogen content and the decrease of the carbon / nitrogen ratio. It is thus demonstrated that during the study period the natural attenuation of the organic pollutants in the soil occurred.

In the absence of a permanent source of pollution in a first phase, oil degradation mechanisms were carried out by: aerobic, optionally anaerobic, anaerobic bacteria, sulfidating bacteria, sulfoxidants, ferrobatics and hydrocarbon oxidation bacteria, which led to a decrease in organic carbon content.

Developing vegetation and reducing organic carbon content also has the secondary effect of lowering bulk density and decreasing soil compaction. On the ground, the observations revealed the installation of vegetation in the first stage of the monitoring.

At the end of the monitoring period, in 2013, the physicochemical analyzes of the polluted soil are comparable to those of an average fertile soil, being superior to the unpolluted soil (CS) to which they were reported.

CONCLUSIONS

Monitoring the evolution of the hydrophysical and chemical properties, over a period of 15 years (1997-2013) of a land contaminated with crude oil and oil residues, occupied by an albeluvsoil, from Suplacu de Barcău, Bihor county, highlighted the improvement of the initial conditions following the installation of spontaneous vegetation and of the process of pollutants biodegradation.

For long periods of time (10-15 years) the physical properties of the soil, highlighted by reducing the apparent density values, take place. It is

also noted the improvement of the chemical characteristics of the polluted soil, due to the balance of the C / N ratio due to the reduction of the organic carbon values and the increase of the total nitrogen content. This evolution of the physico-chemical properties shows that during long periods of time (10-15 years) in the soil, the natural attenuation of the pollutants represented by hydrocarbons and petroleum residues occurs.

The large period in which the biodegradation of organic pollutants from the soil occurs, without any anthropic intervention, shows that for to reduce the period of natural attenuation it is necessary to stimulate the process of ecological reconstruction of hydrocarbon-polluted soils by applying agro-pedo ameliorative measures, that intensify the activity of microorganisms involved in the biodegradation process.

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APPLICATION OF LIDAR TECHNOLOGY IN CATTLE GRAZING AREAS

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Abstract

Precision farming technologies increasingly appear in the livestock sector. The most precision animal husbandry innovations are in the precision breeding and nutrition, but nowadays, different robots (e.g. robotic milking systems, robotic barn cleaners, etc.) can help for effective animal production, mainly in barn. The number of such innovative solutions in field is less. In order to collect spatial information about the ethology of animals, grazing dairy cattle are surveyed by LiDAR sensor. The focus area is a pasture near Nyírbátor (BÁTORTRADE Trade and Services Ltd., North Trans Tisza Region, Hungary). Application of LiDAR terrain characteristic, topography, vegetation status (e.g. the qualitative and quantitative characteristic of vegetation) and grazing cattle in the pasture can be detected. The main goal of our study was to detect grazing cattle on field by ALS system. LiDAR data was useful for animal detection, and based on the spatial data lying and standing animals were identified distinguishing from each other. In order to examine the static position of cattle, digital elevation model was created based on the high precision spatial data. Based on the distribution and behaviour of the animals, different problems (e.g. environmental stress) in animal husbandry could be concluded. Multispectral image pattern and monitoring the spatial distribution of cattle's movement, wet locations can be identified on the pasture. Using LiDAR data seems a promising opportunity to optimize land use and livestock size.

Key words: LiDAR, ethology, vegetation status, terrain characteristic

INTRODUCTION

Today, more and more areas require accurate, reliable and up-to-date characterization of Earth's surface and terrain. The currently rarely applied, but emerging airborne laser scanner (ALS, Airborne Laser Scanning, also known as LiDAR, Light Detection and Ranging) satisfies these needs with the speed of data extraction, the amount and accuracy of the information to be extracted. The LiDAR is an active remote sensing system with its own signal destination (Mutlu et al., 2008; Székely et al., 2007). It is similar to a sonar which uses sound waves or a radar which uses radio waves to map things. But a LiDAR system based on light-emitting and detection, which uses light sent out from a laser to measure the elevations of things, for example ground, forests or buildings. This remote sensing method measures the distance between the emitting device and the reflecting surface with a laser light (Drosos and Farmakis, 2006; Liu, 2008; Lloyd and Atkinson, 2005).

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There are three different ways to collect LiDAR data: from the ground, from the airplane and even from the space. From these the most commonly applied data is the airborne LiDAR data, when a laser scanner – which attached to an airplane or helicopter, or drone (Neonic, 2014) – creates 3D point cloud model of the surface.

The emitted laser light reflects from the objects on the surface and the system records the time between transmitted and backscattered pulses. Since the speed of light is known the distance can be calculated (Csiha et al., 2017; Doneus et al., 2015; Drosos and Farmakis, 2006; Liu, 2008; Lloyd and Atkinson, 2005; Riczu et al., 2016). To image objects it uses ultraviolet, visible or near infrared light (Cracknell and Hayes, 2007).

The airborne laser scanning can be used in, such as forestry, including forest fire management (Fernandes et al., 2004; Lohr, 1998; Mutlu et al., 2008; Saye et al., 2005; Tamás et al., 2011; Tamás et al., 2013; Utkin et al., 2002), coastal surveys (Lohr, 1998; Saye et al., 2005), geomorphological research (Eeckhaut et al., 2007; Kasai et al., 2009), archaeological surveys (Bewley et al., 2005; Challis, 2006; Devereux et al., 2008) and infrastructural and environmental projects (Challis et al., 2008; Wehr and Lohr, 1999).

The reasons of this wide application area of this technology are the speed of surveying, relatively large surveyed area and acquiring of high resolution data.

In agriculture, for example in grazing, the application of remote sensing instruments provides an opportunity to examine the heterogeneity of the vegetation in the pasture (Tamás et al., 2014) and study the animal behaviour. In this study besides the terrain characteristic, vegetation status and topography, we also detected the grazing cattle on the pasture. The advantage of LiDAR as a remote sensing technology is that it doesn't have to be in direct contact with the tested object, so it doesn't disturb the natural behaviour of animals.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The sample area was located near to Nyírbátor, easter part of Hungary (Fig. 1), which is owned by the Bátortrade Corporation and the grazing area was part of the LiDAR survey.

The laser surveys were carried out by Eurosense Ltd. in Feburary, 2017. The laser measurement was performed using the IGI LiteMapper system. The LM 6800 can perform up to 400.000 points per second (laser PRR: 400 kHz). The scanner and related processing software (RiAnALYZE 6.0.2, RiWORLD 4.3.7, TerraScan v16, TerraMatch) can also use waveform analysis.

The high-resolution survey covered 107.8 ha, which contains the arable and the grassland also. The area was built from 129.072.937 points. The resolution of the LiDAR data points is 14.58 points/m², which is appropriate for high resolution models.

Fig. 1. The surveyed area in Nyírbátor

In this research, our evaluation was carried out in a small part of the grassland, which was 4.7 ha (and it contains more than 2.5 million points, 33.08 points/m²). The airborne laser data allows the unique identification and monitoring of the cattle, so not only the status of the pasture were measured, but we also get information about the grazing cattle's ethology, the behaviour of animals. The processing of the data was made in ENVI LiDAR software environment.

As the figure 2 shows the Digital Surface Model (DSM) displays the land surface with all the objects (both natural and artificial also) on the area. The DSM shows where and how much vegetation is growing, so it is useful for the vegetation management. In other application areas the DSM is also useful for view obstruction and runway approach zone encroachment.

If we void the artificial (power lines, buildings and towers) and natural (trees, other types of vegetation) objects, we generate a Digital Elevation Model (DEM). The DEM is useful in soil mapping, hydrologic modelling, terrain stability and land use planning (GIS Geography, 2017). In contrast, in the DSM, all object covered by a mesh.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the surveying method are called point cloud, which is a set of data in a 3D coordinate system and these data represent the external surface of an object (Axelsson, 1999; Drosos and Farmakis, 2006). Laser data provides an opportunity to segment different surfaces, such a grazing animals or canopy coverage. In this case, the lying and standing animals were distinguished, since this method is suitable for segment the grazing and/or digesting cattle.

Fig. 2. The DSM and DEM of the grazing area

Objects above ground can be visualized by subtract DEM from DSM. That way watering facilities and other noise effects were separated from the animals.

Figure 3 shows the alignment of animals at the moment of the survey, where the animals group around the feeding place. Based on the pixels of cows, a height histogram was created as it shown in the figure 3. By this elevation histogram the standing and lying cows can be separated from each other. The separation threshold was on 1 m, so above 1 m, animals are standing, below 1 m, animals are lying.

By frequency of pixels, the average area of a cow can be calculated (2.54 m^2). According to our calculations the total area of standing cows is 406.25 m^2 and 278.25 m^2 the area of lying cows, which means that about 160 cows stands and 110 lies.

This surveying just was a one-time occasion, but with multiple LiDAR surveys the movement of livestock and the alignment of the animals

could be monitored. A surveying method would be important before and during the grazing.

Previous to precision cattle grazing it is required to know the area, because the pasture should fulfil the feeding requirements of the animal. By analysis of multispectral images qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the vegetation (biodiversity, invasive plants etc.) can be concluded. The surveying also would be important during the grazing, because the grazing cattle modifies its environment. In other researches, this method could be extended to monitoring other animal species, for example it would also be possible to observe the wild population on different regions.

Fig. 3. Frequency of standing and lying animals

CONCLUSIONS

Summary the application of remote sensing technology in animal husbandry provides an opportunity to observe animal behavior and its changes, and also suitable to examine the welfare of cattle. By remote sensing the information about the temporal and spatial changes of the pasture (e.g. soil, vegetation, grazing ability etc.) also provided.

Acknowledgment

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VEGETATION DYNAMICS IN COMMUNITY RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AREAS: A MEASURE OF PROGRESS

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Abstract

*Ghana's Community Resource Management Areas (CREMAs) are established to reduce biodiversity degradation through the promotion of communal responsibility to conserve resources for sustainable benefits. This study was conducted to assess vegetation dynamics in three CREMAs in the northern savanna zone of Ghana through the application of remote sensing techniques and field observation. The findings showed the vegetation cover of all the three study areas improved over the period between 1990 and 2010. There were indications of successions from lower tier vegetation classes to higher ones. The riparian vegetation of the study sites changed from open savanna woodland to closed savanna woodland mainly through the grazing activities of the hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibious*) and management practices that restrict farming, livestock grazing, charcoal production and suppress wildfires. The suppression of wildfires has resulted in considerable amount of fuel load which must be managed to prevent severe-intensive-fires in the future. Notwithstanding the general improvement in vegetation cover, there were also considerable increased coverage of bare surface/built up areas indicating economic activities also moved up over the period.*

Key words: biodiversity, community, ecotourism, savanna, vegetation, wildfire

INTRODUCTION

Ghana's Ministry of Environment Science and Technology (MEST) in 2012 identified northern Ghana to have had prolonged history of land degradation which has resulted in desertification at certain parts of the northern zone of the country. Again, a report on Ghana from the country's Ministry of Lands and Natural Resources (MLNR) in 2012 stated 135,000 ha of forest cover is lost annually through: (1) expansive agriculture, (2) increasing urbanization, (3) mining and mineral extraction and (4) harvesting of wood for lumber and fuel. The alarming degradation of the country's land resources has resulted in the formulation of new strategies aim to halt biodiversity losses and promote sustainable development (Wood, 2008).

The Government of Ghana and development partners engage communities to work towards stopping the degradation through different sets of interventions. One of the strategies being implemented to halt the continuous land degradation is through promoting the establishment of Community Resources Management Areas (CREMAs). As at the year 2009 the total area covered by CREMAs in Ghana was 200,000 ha (Roe et al., 2009). Again, by the year 2010, there were 26 active CREMAs that had

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been established in Ghana (Asare et al., 2013). The Wildlife Division of Ghana devolve authority to managing biodiversity to local institutions that set up CREMAs.

The CREMA strategy intervention aim is not only to stop biodiversity degradation, but also to help regeneration of the ecosystem to its optimum productive levels that will support rural livelihoods (Ekpe et al., 2014; Owusu-Ansah, 2019). The establishment of CREMAs is to promote sustainable utilization of biodiversity resources through good governance structures that are locally developed. The CREMA structures consist of regulations and alternative livelihood support programmes that are implemented through collaboration with other institutions at the local level to manage biodiversity resources (Owusu-Ansah, 2019). Community leaders who lead the process are expected to enforce conservation laws which include antipoaching patrols, prevent wildfires and other forms of encroachment that degrade biodiversity resources.

This study assessed the vegetation dynamics of three Community Resources Management Areas (CREMAs) that have been established in the fragile ecosystem of northern Ghana. The sites are Wechiau Community Hippopotamus Sanctuary (WCHS), Zukpri Integrated Wildlife Sanctuary (ZIWS) and Sayinga-Kasena-Gavara-Kara (SKGK). These sites are prone to annual wildfires and other human induced degradation such as illegal felling of trees for lumber and charcoal production. Overgrazing by livestock (especially from nomadic herdsman cattle) is also more pronounced in the northern savanna zone. Biodiversity and other forms of land degradation are exacerbated by an annual short duration rainfall and high temperatures which make this zone of Ghana vulnerable to wildfires (MLNR, 2012).

The study purpose was to track changes in the vegetation cover of the three sites between 1990 and 2010. Huge amounts of biodiversity resources are devolved to community leaders to manage when CREMAs are established (Roe et al., 2009). Failure to properly manage these resources by the community leaders will lead to further degradation. The resources then will be regarded as open access leading to abuse in the manner of the 'tragedy of the commons' (Moxnes, 1998). If that was to happen, it would be improper and a disincentive to the Government to continue to implement the CREMA strategies. Changes in the vegetation cover of the study sites were used to gauge progress in biodiversity management effectiveness in the CREMAs to prevent degradation (Leeuwen et al., 2010).

Theoretical Background

The ineffectiveness of centralized government biodiversity conservation programmes has been debated in the literature. Biodiversity resources degradation causes have sometimes been blamed on centralized management concepts (Agrawal and Gibson, 1999; Lockwood et al., 2010).

Indeed, one major reason to the disregard for conservation laws in communities are placed on the enmity that results from centralization policies such as the creation of protected areas to the exclusion of rural people (Agyare, 2013; Bixler et al., 2015; Grodzinska-Jurczak et al., 2012). CREMAs in Ghana are set up to reduce some of the negative impacts of centralized conservation strategies through collaboration between government and communal structures established to manage biodiversity.

The CREMA strategy guidelines have been targeted at putting more lands under conservation. The problem with this strategy however, is that the Ghana Government does not own large tracts of lands for conservation because most land tenure arrangements in the country are under traditional rulers and families (Agyare, 2013; Roe et al., 2009). The approach to circumvent this difficulty is to promote the implementation of collaborative biodiversity resources conservation policies in the country (The Wildlife Division, 2000).

The argument for the implementation of collaborative conservation strategies is to get some communal lands to be put under conservation without the enmity that characterizes centralized protected area regimes (Jones and Erdmann, 2013; Kluvánková-Oravská et al., 2009; Shafer, 2015). The strategy does not only promote participatory conservation services in rural areas, it is also a means of promoting alternative livelihoods programmes to improve standard of living (Ekpe et al., 2014). The CREMA strategy implementation focus has been on areas with rich biodiversity which has greater risk to degradation. Monitoring progress to see the established CREMAs do not suffer degradation is not only to perpetuate the resources, but also to replicate the programme and its benefits in other areas.

Liu et al., 2016 emphasized the need to monitor vegetation dynamics especially in ecosystems like the savanna where negative human activities combine with harsh abiotic conditions to degrade biodiversity resources. Remote sensing techniques have been useful in monitoring changes in vegetations at a large scale. Different vegetation types and characteristics respond variably to remote sensing application. It has been stated that moisture content, chlorophyll and other pigment levels in plants have varied sensitive levels and respond differently to remote sensing techniques. The technology is used to differentiate among vegetation types (Leeuwen et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2016; Norman et al., 2014).

The main objective of this research was to understand how the CREMA leaders have been able to prevent the degradation of the biodiversity resources that has been entrusted unto them. Vegetation trend analysis has been used in determining management activities effectiveness (Norman et al., 2014). The assumption to this study was that effective management of the CREMAs prevent vegetation degradation which leads to

lower level vegetation classes succeeding to higher ones. The trend analysis of this study considered the changes in the percentage coverage of the different vegetation classes at three temporal points.

Two research questions were asked for the study.

(1). What are the trends in vegetation cover since the conservation sensitization/ education and enforcement activities began in the CREMAs?

(2). How would the changes in the different vegetation classes impact on: (I) wildfire management, (II) herbivory and (III) ecotourism development in the CREMAs?

This study was used to triangulate with interview and field observation data collected for the author's doctoral dissertation. It was to attest to the responses of the CREMA leaders that suggest they had been able to reduce the incidences of wildfires, poaching, overgrazing and farming close to riparian areas in the CREMAs.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study Sites

Three CREMAs were purposively selected for this study (Devers and Frankel, 2000) because they occur in the same ecological zone. Sayinga-Kasena-Gavara-Kara (SKGK), Wechiau Community Hippopotamus Sanctuary (WCHS) and Zukpri Integrated Wildlife Sanctuary (ZIWS) are located in the Guinea savanna ecological zone. The SKGK is located between latitudes 10°45' 45''N and 11°00' 12'' N and longitudes 1°18' 00'' W and 1° 39' 00'' W with a total area of 587.26 km² (The Wildlife Division, 2017). The total land area of ZIWS is 420 km². ZIWS is located within latitude 10° 00' 00'' N and 10° 20'00'' N and longitude 2° 30'00'' W and 2° 50' 00'' W in the Upper West Region of Ghana. WCHS can be found in the Wa West District of the Upper West Region lying between latitudes 9° 40' 05'' N and 10° 10' 47''N and also between longitudes 2° 20' 00''W and 2° 50' 30''W (Ghana Statistical Service, 2010). Both WCHS and ZIWS lie in the same continuum of land mass drained by the Black Volta and its tributaries.

The three CREMAs are populated by different types of wildlife species that enrich the biodiversity of the ecosystem. For example, WCHS and ZIWS have sizeable populations of hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibious*) which inhabit the Black Volta (Olayide et al., 2013). Primates species like the Patas Monkey (*Erythrocebus patas*), and the Baboon (*Papio anubis*) are also common in the study sites. The SKGK also has a sizeable population of roan antelope (*Hippotragus equines*) and the place is particularly known to be part of the annual migration route of Elephants (*Loxodonta africana*) from Burkina Faso to Ghana (Lungren, 2008). Large number of cattle herds (particularly from nomads) traverse the study sites.

Methods

A time series vegetation map was developed for each of the selected sites over three temporal points (the years 1990, 2000 and 2010) to relate vegetation cover changes. Field visits were undertaken to each of the study sites and locations with closed canopy tall trees were selected. Estimated centers of such closed savanna woodlands in each of the study sites were marked with Global Positioning System (GPS) coordinates. A time series vegetation maps were developed from the coordinate points through remote sensing techniques (Maurin et al., 2015) to study the changes in the vegetation cover over a twenty - year period (1990 to 2010). In all nine images were developed for analysis.

The images developed were for dry season (late March) at each time point to eliminate possible influences of annual crop fields on the vegetation percentage coverage. The timing for the images was to get the optimum natural vegetation coverage for analysis devoid of crop fields. Also, the effects of wildfires would have been felt by late March when the images were developed (Norman, 2014). The time series imagery maps of the CREMAs were developed for 1990 which predates their establishments. Images were developed for 2000 which marked the CREMAs formative stages and 2010 which gave ample time to assess the effectiveness in halting degradation of the vegetation (Leeuwen et al., 2010).

Data Analyses

Savanna vegetation has many succession classes (Maurin et al., 2015). In this study, the savanna vegetation has been classified to include in a descending order closed savanna woodland, followed by open savanna woodland, which is also followed by dense herbaceous /grass vegetation. The rest of the classes are grass herbaceous vegetation and bare surface/built up areas. The Black Volta River coverage area was also determined for WCHS and ZIWS.

The percentage coverage of each vegetation class at each temporal point were related in the analyses to observe the trends in the changes. Findings have been presented in descriptive tables showing areas covered in square kilometers and percentage coverage of each vegetation class.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The series for this section begins with WCHS, followed by ZIWS and then SKGK. The discussions section brings into perspectives the observed changes in vegetation cover, focusing on its implication on: (1) wildfire management, (2) herbivory and (3) promoting ecotourism.

Vegetation Cover Changes in WCHS

The analyses were based on a sampled area of 33.99 Km² of WCHS as seen in Fig. 1. The general observation was that there had been

improvement in the vegetation cover. There was a general trend of the lower-class vegetation types succeeding into higher levels. Details in the changes in the vegetation types in WCHS is shown below (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Time Series Image Map of WCHS for 1990, 2000 and 2010

Table 1

Matrix of land cover by class for the years 1990, 2000 and 2010 in WCHS

Vegetation Class	Year of Assessment					
	1990		2000		2010	
	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover
Closed savanna woodland	0.5587	1.64	2.8287	8.32	2.8301	8.32
Open savanna woodland	9.840	28.95	8.9712	26.39	9.6062	28.26
Dense herbaceous/grass cover	17.1903	50.57	14.9032	43.84	16.5132	48.58
Grass/herbaceous cover	6.0354	17.75	5.36402	15.78	2.3256	6.84
Bare surface/built up areas	0.270	0.79	0.8226	2.42	2.1348	6.28
Water body	0.0972	0.28	1.1034	3.25	0.5832	1.72
Total	33.9931	100	33.9931	100	33.9931	100

WCHS in the year 1990 had the largest portion of its vegetation as dense herbaceous/grass made up of 50.57 % which reduced considerably to 43.84 % by the year 2000. However, there was a major increase of this vegetation class from the 43.84 % in 2000 to 48.57 % in 2010. The inching up of the percentage coverage of the dense herbaceous/grass vegetation could only be attributed to a higher succession from the lower grass herbaceous, class which percentage coverage reduced over the same period (2000 to 2010) from 15.77 % to 6.84 %.

The closed savanna woodland forms the highest class of the vegetation succession ladder in the West African savanna ecosystem. This vegetation class in 1990 covered only 1.64 %. The closed savanna woodland vegetation moved up to 8.31 % by the year 2000. As it is expected, its lower tier-the open savanna vegetation class had its coverage reduced a little from 28.94 % to 26.39 %. This suggests a succession to the upper class of the closed savanna woodland occurred from the second tier. The closed savanna vegetation maintained its coverage with the same percentage of 8.32 % in 2010 as it was in 2000.

The Black Volta is an important international water body for Ghana and Burkina Faso. The River covered 0.28 % of the sampled area as at 1990. The Black Volta coverage increased to 1.10 % in 2000. However, the River in 2010 reduced to almost half of its 2000 figure. In 2000, the River occupied 1.10 Km² as against the 0.58 Km² in 2010. Seasonal changes in climatic conditions would have been the major cause of the variations.

Bare surface/built areas in WCHS were relatively small covering 0.79 % in 1990. It increased to 2.42 % over the ten-year period between 1990 and 2000. The bare surface/built up areas continued to increase and within the period between 2000 and 2010, it jumped from 2.41 % to 6.84 %. The movement upwards of this vegetation class suggest an increase in human settlements and activities that degrade the vegetation occurred.

Vegetation Cover Changes in ZIWS

The analyses were based on a sampled area of 43.22 Km² of the ZIWS. ZIWS lies at the north of WCHS on the course of the Black Volta River. The general observation was that there was an improvement in the vegetation cover, notwithstanding a considerable increase in the bare surface/built up areas over the twenty-year period. There were general trends of lower tier vegetation classes succeeding into higher levels (Fig. 2). The percentage changes in the vegetation cover that occurred over the period is shown below (Table 2).

In 1990, more than half of the ZIWS' sampled area was made up of a dense herbaceous/grass of 55.73 % which was followed by open savanna woodland covering 29.68 %. The dense herbaceous/grass vegetation reduced by a little over eight percentage points to 47.95 % in 2000.

However, there was no major change in the dense herbaceous/grass vegetation percentage coverage by 2010. It only dropped by 0.89 % of what was recorded in 2000. This change is in contrast to the major increase that was observed in the same class of vegetation in WCHS from 43.84 % to 48.57 % between 2000 and 2010.

Fig. 2. Time Series Map of ZIWS for 1990, 2000 and 2010

Table 2

Matrix of land cover by class for the years 1990, 2000 and 2010 in ZIWS

Vegetation Class	Year of Assessment					
	1990		2000		2010	
	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover
Closed savanna woodland	0.8343	1.93	1.0998	2.55	1.152	2.67
Open savanna woodland	12.8287	29.68	14.0122	32.42	10.854	25.11
Dense herbaceous/grass cover	24.0868	55.73	20.7253	47.95	20.3393	47.06
Grass/herbaceous cover	3.7539	8.69	3.501	8.1	6.642	15.37
Bare surface/built up areas	1.1196	2.59	2.9601	6.85	3.9204	9.07
Water body	0.594	1.38	0.9189	2.13	0.3096	0.72
Total	43.217	100	43.2173	100	43.2173	100

The closed savanna woodland (the highest vegetation class) stood at 1.93 % which was slightly higher than the 1.64 % recorded for WCHS in 1990. The closed savanna woodland vegetation did not increase substantially compared to what was observed in WCHS where it moved from 1.64 % to 8.31 % between 1990 and 2000. In ZIWS, it increased marginally from 1.93 % to 2.55 %. Again, it increased marginally from 2.55 % to 2.67 % between 2000 and 2010.

The Black Volta River covered 1.38 % compared to the 0.28 % of WCHS in 1990. The River's percentage coverage increased from 1.38 % in 1990 to 2.13 % in 2000. Again, the seasonal variation in climatic conditions would be the major cause of the differences in the Black Volta coverage as was also observed for WCHS over the same period. The River in 2010 saw a reduction in its coverage to 0.72 % in 2010. Again, the drop in the volume of the water suggest harsher climatic conditions variation over the period might have occurred.

The bare surface /built areas for ZIWS in 1990 was 2.59 % which was higher than the 0.79 % recorded for WCHS. The bare surface/built up areas increased to 6.85 % in 2000. This was a marked difference from the changes that occurred in WCHS, which increased from 0.79 % to 2.42 %. By 2010, the bare surface/built up areas in ZIWS had increased from 6.85 % to 9.07 %. The 9.07 % was the highest conversion of vegetation cover into a bare surface/built up area of the three study sites. Expansion in human activities including settlements and economic activities were the major causes for the conversion into bare surface/built areas.

Vegetation Cover Changes in SKGK

The analyses were based on a sampled area of 71.5 Km² of the SKGK. River Sissili and its tributaries are the main drainage of the CREMA. This River completely dries up in the dry season and therefore its percentage coverage was not shown in the images for analysis. There are substantial sections along this River that have riparian forests. The riparian forest serves as an important wildlife corridor between protected areas in Burkina Faso and Ghana. Fig. 3 shows the changes in vegetation coverage that occurred in the SKGK. Details of the changes that occurred over the period is shown below (Table 3).

The SKGK in the year 1990 had the largest vegetation class as dense herbaceous/grass covering 46.86%. This class was followed by open savanna woodland making 33.08% of the sampled area. The dense herbaceous/grass vegetation reduced from 46.82% to 41.03% by the year 2000 and it reduced further to 37.57% in 2010. The reductions suggest a succession to the upper open savanna vegetation woodland occurred. This

was confirmed by the open savanna vegetation steadily increment in coverage between 2000 and 2010.

Fig. 3. Time Series Image Map of SKGK for 1990, 2000 and 2010

Table 3

Matrix of land cover by class for the years 1990, 2000 and 2010 in SKGK

Vegetation Class	Year of Assessment					
	1990		2000		2010	
	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover	Area/ Km ²	% Cover
Closed savanna woodland	3.0663	4.29	3.8691	5.41	5.5444	7.75
Open savanna woodland	23.6503	33.08	23.5392	32.92	28.1672	39.39
Dense herbaceous/grass cover	33.4792	46.82	29.3428	41.03	26.8668	37.57
Grass/herbaceous cover	10.4148	14.57	14.1098	19.73	8.5292	11.93
Bare surface/built up areas	0.8901	1.24	0.6489	0.91	2.3996	3.36
Total	71.5010	100	71.5098	100	71.5072	100

The open savanna woodland moved from 32.92 % to 39.39 % over the period. The changes in the open savanna woodland would not have been contributed by the dense herbaceous alone looking at the margin of increase. The grass herbaceous class also reduced from 19.73 % to 11.93 % between

2000 and 2010. This suggests a succession from this class to two tier classes above occurred.

The closed savanna woodland which form the highest class of the vegetation succession ladder covered 4.29 % in 1990. This percentage coverage happened to be the highest within this class of vegetation among the three study sites in 1990. By the year 2000 the closed savanna woodland vegetation moved up to 5.41 % and further moved to 7.75 % in 2010. The open savanna woodland vegetation reduced marginally from 33.08 % to 32.92 % between 1990 and 2000. This suggests a succession to the upper closed savanna woodland occurred. This is confirmed by the marginal increase of the closed savanna woodland from 4.29 % to 5.41 % over the period.

The bare surface/built areas coverage was 1.24 % in 1990 which surprisingly reduced to 0.91 % by 2000. That was the only situation where a reduction occurred in this class of vegetation within a ten-year period in any of the study sites. However, between 2000 and 2010 there was an increase from 0.91 % to 3.36 %. The increment was largely contributed by the level of human settlement developments that moved up over the period. A cursory look at the satellite image showed communities which were essentially dots expanded considerably over the period (Fig. 3).

Improved Vegetation Cover: Implications for Wildfire Management

The threat of wildfires and its intensity increase with drier conditions coupled with higher fuel load that result from previous unburnt vegetation (Sebata, 2017). Findings from Gordijn et al., 2012, cited in Sebata, 2017 indicated that when areas are suppressed from the effect of wildfires for long, it results in woody plant vegetation. On the contrary incidences of wildfires reduce the number of adult trees in the savanna by killing seedlings and saplings (Campbell, 2013). At seedling and sapling stages of tree development, it is unable to resist and recover from some of the intense fires of the savanna. Wildfires however, has the advantage to reduce competition thereby increasing growth rate of few trees that survive.

Savanna vegetation has been predicted to undergo major changes in ecological functions and processes (Baudena et al., 2015; IPCC, 2007). The prediction was based on the effects of global warming which affect moisture content of plants and grasses in the savanna. The consequence of that prediction was a heightened incidences of annual wildfire regimes in the savanna. The ultimate outcome will be losses in biodiversity in the savanna ecosystem due to fragmentation (Liu et al., 2016). However, the general trend in the vegetation dynamics in the three CREMAs suggested the vegetation has been managed well with lower tier classes succeeding to higher ones. The findings from the satellite imagery and field observations

pointed the leaders have been able to reduce some of the threats such as wildfires and indiscriminate felling of trees within as well as regulating farming activities in sensitive ecological zones.

Notwithstanding the findings of an improved vegetation cover in the CREMAs, the predictions of Baudena et al. (2015) and the IPCC (2007) still looms particularly in the drier areas of the CREMAs. The sampled areas for this study were mostly the riparian forests where closed canopy vegetation existed and incidentally these areas were designated in the CREMAs as core zones where little human activities were allowed. The moisture content of the riparian vegetation is relatively higher compared to vegetation types further from the waterbodies. The riparian vegetation does not suffer much losses to wildfires and other threats that negatively impact on the vegetation (Norman et al., 2014). These factors would have accounted for the observed improved vegetation cover of the CREMAs.

However, there are considerable fuel loads that have built up at the unburnt areas of the CREMAs and any spark of wildfires could be devastating (Sebata, 2017). Efforts like conservation education, creating fire belts and enforcing regulations should be constant in the CREMAs, so as to prevent fires that could severely impact on biodiversity. Controlled burning regimes have to be promoted, to reduce fuel loads to prevent devastating wildfire episodes from occurring (Goodenough et al., 2016).

Improved Vegetation Cover: Implications for Herbivory

Herbivory, either by grazers or browsers together with wildfires is considered to be one of the major factors that disturbs savanna ecosystems (Liu et al., 2016; Sebata, 2017). Herbivory alone has considerable impacts on the vegetation cover classes of the savanna. Chritz et al., 2016 stated megaherbivores like the hippopotamus and elephants have the capacity to change the savanna ecosystem by their herbivory. Hippopotamus feeding intensity on grass vegetation reduces them into swards that are found on the banks of their aquatic habitat (Kanga et al., 2011). Habitat dominated by hippopotamus promote woody vegetation stands along waterbodies through their feeding habits (Chritz et al., 2016; Kanga et al., 2011).

This study findings showed an increasing closed savanna woodland vegetation along the Black Volta River in WCHS and ZIWS. For example, WCHS closed Savanna woodland vegetation percentage coverage increased from 1.64 % to 8.31 % between 1990 and 2010. This finding suggests the effort to conserve the hippopotamus yielded, the benefit of increasing woodland coverage. A combination of management practices and the feeding habits of the hippopotamus resulted in a succession of lower tier vegetation classes to higher ones.

The leaders of the CREMAs have to continue controlling livestock grazing in the core zones to limit competition between cattle and

hippopotamus (Kanga et al., 2011). An increasing number of hippopotamus will benefit the CREMA as it has the potential to increase the number of tourist visits to the CREMAs.

Improved Vegetation Cover and Ecotourism Development

Ecotourism development is one of the main objectives that drive the establishment of CREMAs. The purpose is to create alternative livelihoods that will ease the pressure on the extraction of biodiversity for subsistence (Ekpe et al., 2014). The dynamics between grassland and woody vegetation in the savanna oscillate in an equilibrium among variations in the levels of wildfires, moisture, soil stability and herbivory (Sebata, 2017).

According to Arbieu et al., 2017, open savanna vegetation is essential to the development of wildlife base ecotourism. The essence is that the open savanna increases visibility for tourists to appreciate wildlife. Dynamics in savanna vegetation also alter habitat, home ranges and feeding regimes of wildlife. Arbieu et al., 2017 again, reported dense vegetation cover reduced tourists viewing satisfaction perception of wildlife species.

The findings of this study showed there had been shifts in succession from lower tier vegetation classes to the highest-closed savanna woodland vegetation. However, this class of vegetation still covers relatively a smaller area in all the three CREMAs which would not pose challenge for tourists viewing. The two largest vegetation classes in all the CREMAs were the open savanna woodland and the dense herbaceous/grass vegetation.

Generally, there were successions from the lower dense herbaceous/grass vegetation to the higher open savanna woodland in all the three CREMAs for the period. These two sets of vegetation classes are essential to promote wildlife tourism. They increase visibility compared to the closed savanna woodland (Arbieu et al., 2017) and also, promote herbivory by ungulates (Chritz et al., 2016; Kanga et al., 2011; Sebata, 2017).

The CREMA management should take note about these two sets of vegetation in developing their tourism products to generate revenue to run their activities, and also, to provide alternative livelihoods for the communities.

Management should not only be obsessed in preventing wildfires to promote successions to closed savanna woodlands, but have an integrated approach that will promote grazing and controlled burning regimes to keep an open savanna woodland and dense herbaceous/grass vegetation (Sebata, 2017). Such management activities will be beneficial in generating fresh growth for herbivory (Kanga et al., 2011) for a productive savanna ecosystem (Chritz et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2016).

CONCLUSIONS

Community Resource Management Areas (CREMAs) are established to reduce biodiversity degradation through the promotion of communal responsibility to conserve the resources for sustainable benefits. This study assessed vegetation dynamics in three CREMAs in Ghana. The purpose was to determine management effectiveness outcomes in reducing biodiversity degradation by assessing changes in the vegetation cover. Satellite images and field observations were used to track changes in the vegetation cover of the CREMAs.

The findings showed the vegetation cover of all the three study areas improved over the period between 1990 and 2010. There were successions from lower tier vegetation classes to higher ones. The leaders of the CREMAs have controlled threats like wildfires, overgrazing and tree felling for lumber and charcoal production. The CREMAs conservation activities have been conservation education, law enforcement, creation of wildfire belts and promotion of alternative livelihood programmes to improve biodiversity sustainability.

The benefits of implementing these activities were seen in an increasing coverage of closed savanna woodland vegetation in the CREMAs. The established closed savanna woodland vegetation along the banks of the Black Volta were the results of the hippopotamus grazing activities coupled with conservation activities in WCHS and ZIWS.

The management of the CREMAs have been able to suppress incidences of wildfires in the core zones, which has resulted in fuel load accumulation. Constant measures have to be put in place to prevent any spark of fires because it could be devastating due to the high intensity of such fires. The conservation activities have benefited the ungulates and other wildlife populations in the CREMAs.

The CREMAs objective of promoting wildlife tourism could be enhanced with increasing biodiversity and abundance. Tourists satisfaction dips with closed woody vegetation. The CREMA management should promote and maintain open savanna and dense herbaceous/grass vegetation for viewing satisfaction and grazing opportunities for tourists and wildlife respectively.

The major challenge to the vegetation cover of the CREMAs was the increasing percentage coverage of the bare surface/built up areas which increased from 0.79 % to 6.84 % in WCHS over the period. Similar trends were observed for ZIWS and SKGK for the period between 1990 and 2010. For ZIWS the bare surface/built up areas increased from 2.59 % to 9.07 % and for SKGK it moved up from 1.24 % to 3.36 %.

The change in ZIWS bare surface/built areas was the highest percentage change among the three CREMAs. The increasing human settlements and its economic activities particularly those related to agriculture, charcoal burning and logging of trees pose major threats to the vegetation cover of the CREMAs.

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CHARACTERISTICS OF CHERNOZEM SOIL IN A LONG TERM FIELD EXPERIMENT IN HUNGARY

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Abstract

The polyfactorial long-term field experiment was conducted in 1983 on a calcareous chernozem soil in Hungary (Debrecen-Látókép experimental farm) to determine the long-term effect of different doses of chemical fertilizers and irrigation on the yield, nutrient uptake of maize (in monoculture production) and on soil parameters. Our aim was to analyse and compare the changes of soil chemical and microbiological characteristics for 33 years NPK fertilizer application either in irrigated and or in non irrigated version. Soil pH, humus, nutrient content and some soil microbiological parameters were analyzed. The microbiological parameters slightly, the chemical parameters of soil significantly influenced by long term application of NPK fertilizers.

In fertilized plots: the pH decreased, humus content increased. The availability of supplied nutrients, NPK improved, while non-supplied macronutrients, calcium and magnesium significantly decreased in fertilized plots compared to control. The significantly decrease in calcium content call attention, that the same effect in acidic sandy soil might be particularly harmful. In fertilized plots the number of bacteria tended to decrease, while the number of microscopic fungi and saccharase enzyme activity significantly enhanced. The irrigation did not cause significant changes of measured microbiological parameters.

Key words: long-term field experiment, chemical, microbiological soil parameters

INTRODUCTION

The long-term experiments (LTEs) are commonly used to compare the long term effects of different agrotechnical factors which are greatly influence the yield and physical, chemical and microbiological properties of soil (Bhattarai et al., 2015; Marschner et al., 2002). The LTEs are suitable for studying the long-term effects of plant production technologies like nutrient management, irrigation to test the sustainability of a farming system and to provide long-term datasets (Johnston, Poulton, 2018).

In the framework of the university's agricultural research projects in University of Debrecen (Hungary) the long-term fertilization and irrigation field experiment was conducted in 1983 at Debrecen-Látókép farm, in Eastern part of Hungary. The soil type of the area is calcareous chernozem with loamy texture (Chernozems in WRB). In this experiment, in the maize monoculture production technology, the influence of crop production factors on the maize yield (Domuța, 2015), nutrient uptake and on chemical,

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physical and microbiological properties of soil (Onęć et al., 2015) have been followed for 33 years (Nagy, 2010; Kátai, 2006).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The polyfactorial long-term field experiment design is split-split plot, the main plots represent the irrigation variants (non-irrigated and irrigated), the split plots cover the different fertilizer doses.

Our present study is focused on to evaluate and compare how long-term fertilization and irrigation processes alter some chemical and microbiological properties of chernozem soil in the field of maize monoculture cultivation in the 33th year of the experiment. The soil parameters measured before setting of the experiment in 1983 and measured in summer of 2016 were compared.

The examined plots of experiment is arranged with different doses of NPK fertilizers with and without irrigation varieties. The treatments are control, N₁PK (180 kg/ha N, 184 kg/ha P₂O₅, 210 kg/ha K₂O) and N₂PK (300 kg/ha N, 184 kg/ha P₂O₅, 210 kg/ha K₂O). Each treatments is set up in four replication. The types of applied chemical fertilizers in 1983-2010 period were ammonium-nitrate, superphosphate and potassium-chloride, while from 2010 the superphosphate has been changed to monoammonium-phosphate. From this period the calcium, as the component of superphosphate was not supplied any more.

The soil sampling was in a depth of 0-20 cm in June of 2016. Soil chemical parameters, pH, AL-P₂O₅, AL-K₂O, AL-Ca, AL-Mg and 0,01M CaCl₂-Mn were measured. Soil microbiological parameters, the total numbers of bacteria (bouillon agar) and fungi (PGA) were measured by plate dilution method (Szegi, 1979). The measurement of saccharase activity was carried out according to the method of Frankenberger et al. (1983). The urease enzyme activity was measured by (Kempers cit. Filep, 1995). The CO₂ production of soil was determined for 10 days of soil incubation at constant soil temperature and moisture content.

The statistical evaluation was made by using SPSS 13.0 program. The significant differences were calculated at 5 % level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The soil sampling and measuring of soil parameters were in June of 2016 in the 30th year of the experiment. In this summer there was no need to irrigate the “irrigated” experimental plots because of the heavy rain in June (146.3 mm; annual average: 818 mm). As a result of rainfall the differences of moisture content of soil samples of irrigated and non-irrigated plots were balanced and ranged between 19.01-20.08 %.

Some original chemical soil characteristics of the experimental area measured before setting the experiment in 1983 is shown in Tables 1, 2. The values of pH, humus content, AL-P₂O₅, AL-K₂O, AL-Ca, AL-Mg and CaCl₂-Mn of soil samples in irrigated and non-irrigated area in different treatments measured in 2016 are shown in Tables 1, 2.

Table 1

Effect of NPK fertilization and irrigation on the pH, humus and nitrate content of soil

Treatments		pH (H ₂ O)	pH (KCl)	Humus %	NO ₃ -N mg kg ⁻¹
		n.i.**	1983		6.2
	contr.	7.04b*	5.81b	3.56a	13.08a
	N ₁ PK	6.88b	5.63ab	3.70b	50.33b
	N ₂ PK	6.44a	5.28a	4.33b	105.6c
	contr.	6.77ab	5.71ab	4.37b	14.56a
i.**	N ₁ PK	6.52ab	5.47ab	4.44b	52.86b
	N₂PK	6.10a	5.19a	4.81b	106.2c

*Values with the same letter are not significantly different from each other (P>0.05)

**n.i.: non irrigated plots; i.: irrigated plots.

Table 2

Effect of NPK fertilization and irrigation on the nutrient content of soil

Treatments		AL-P ₂ O ₅	AL-K ₂ O	AL-Ca	AL-Mg	CaCl ₂ -Mn
		mg kg ⁻¹				
n.i.**	1983	138	272	-	-	-
	contr.	51.1a*	168a	3933b	423b	7.57a
	N ₁ PK*	158.2c	250bc	3827b	380a	11.42a
	N ₂ PK*	172.3c	254bc	3380a	369a	24.59bc
	contr.	50.4a	159a	3760b	460b	10.61a
i.**	N ₁ PK*	139.3b	232b	3513b	404a	16.44a
	N₂PK*	143.2b	241b	3013a	353a	28.96c

*Values with the same letter are not significantly different from each other (P>0.05)

**n.i.: non irrigated plots; i.: irrigated plots.

Comparing the original pH_{KCl}= 6.2 value of the area measured in 1983 (before setting the experiment) and the pH_{KCl}=5.8-5.2 in 2016, it can be said, that the long term soil tillage, and NPK fertilization caused significant decrease in pH values, increase in acidity. The value of control decreased almost 0.4 unit, while the highest fertilizer dose caused about 0.6 unit drop in pH value compared to control one. The pH of irrigated plots tended to become more lower than that of non irrigated ones.

The humus content increased in time in control parcel (from 2.76 % to 3.56 %, 4.37 %) and values also became higher in fertilized plots compared to control. The humus values tended to be higher in the irrigated area. The better nutrient availability in fertilized plots and the irrigation caused higher

biomass production and the higher byproducts of maize which had been incorporated for 33 years might cause increased humus content of soil.

The NO_3^- also significantly enhanced in all fertilized plots compared to control, but there were no differences between values of irrigated and non irrigated area.

The AL- P_2O_5 and AL- K_2O in control plots significantly decreased in time, compared to data measured in 1983, due to the lack of long-term nutrients supply of this area. The availability of phosphorus and potassium in fertilized and non-irrigated plots were significantly higher.

The non-fertilized macronutrients, Ca and Mg significantly decreased in all NPK fertilized plots compared to control. These macronutrients have not supplied for ages but maize took up calcium and magnesium year by year. The better NPK supply - the higher yield - the greater decrease in calcium and magnesium content of soil.

Because of the acidity effect of long-term NPK fertilization, the solubility and availability of manganese significantly increased in all fertilized plots and reached its maximum in N_2PK treatment. In the irrigated area where the pH value became even more reduced, the availability of manganese tended to increase more.

The changes of some microbiological parameters: the number of bacteria, microscopic fungi, the saccharase, urease activity of soil and the CO_2 production during 10 days incubation of soil are summarized in Table 3.

The total number of bacteria tended to decrease in the fertilized soil, while the number of microscopic fungi enhanced. Our results showed that there were not any differences in the number of bacteria and fungi between treatments of N_1PK and N_2PK and between values of irrigated and non-irrigated plots.

Regarding the measured enzyme activities, either long term fertilization or irrigation did not alter the urease activity significantly, but a decreasing trend appeared due to higher fertilizer dose (N_2PK). In the long-term fertilized soil the saccharase activity was found significantly higher compared to control value.

The increase in humus content due to fertilization, might cause increased catabolic processes of organic matters and indicated increased values of saccharase enzyme activity. Increase in enzyme activity was also observed Kandeler et al., 1999 after addition of either NPK fertiliser in a long-term study.

The intensity of microbiological decomposing processes can be followed by measuring the CO_2 production. Based on our results it can be concluded that either long term fertilization or irrigation did not alter the

CO₂ production of soil significantly, but decreasing trend can be realised in fertilized plots.

Table 3

Effect of NPK fertilization and irrigation on some microbiological parameters of soil

Treatments		Number of bacteria	Number of microscopic fungi	Saccharase activity	Urease activity	CO ₂
		(x10 ⁶ g ⁻¹ soil)	(x10 ³ g ⁻¹ soil)	glucose mg/100g	NH ₄ ⁺ mg/100g	mg CO ₂ * 100g ⁻¹ * 10 days ⁻¹
n.i. **	contr.	19.62a*	23.3b	5.11a	56.4a	19.62a
	N ₁ PK *	12.67a	34.0ab	15.82c	53.4a	12.67a
	N ₂ PK *	17.29a	34.7a	17.23c	48.6a	17.29a
i.**	contr.	19.08a	26.3ab	5.04a	46.6a	19.08a
	N ₁ PK *	11.35a	28.8ab	13.93b	47.5a	11.35a
	N ₂ PK *	15.95a	29.8a	16.02c	43.3a	15.95a

*Values with the same letter are not significantly different from each other (P>0.05)

**n.i.: non irrigated plots; i.: irrigated plots.

CONCLUSIONS

The long-term fertilization caused significant changes, while irrigation caused smaller changes in the chemical and microbiological properties of chernozem soil.

In fertilized plots: the pH decreased, humus content, nitrate, phosphorus, potassium supply of soil enhanced, the solubility of manganese increased. The long term non-supplied macronutrients (Ca, Mg) significantly decreased, which unfavorable change call attention, that the same effect in acidic sandy soil might be particularly harmful. In fertilized plots the number of bacteria tended to decrease, while the number of microscopic fungi and saccharase enzyme activity significantly enhanced. The irrigation did not cause significant changes of measured microbiological parameters.

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INFLUENCE OF FERTILIZER AND CULTIVAR ON THE GLUTEN QUALITY OF WINTER WHEAT

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Abstract

During our experiments in 2017/2018 crop year at Látókép Experimental Farm of University of Debrecen, we examined the effect of different cultivars and increased dosages of artificial fertilizer (control, N₉₀PK, N₁₅₀PK) on quality of wheat gluten. The gluten quality parameters of winter wheat were significantly influenced by fertilizing and cultivar. N₉₀PK dosage improved significantly the measured parameters, further fertilizer application had no statistically provable effect. Application of artificial fertilizers increased significantly the gluten spread of the samples, compared to the control ones. KG Kunhalom had significantly higher crude protein (CP), wet gluten (WGC), dry gluten, gluten ratio and Zeleny index (ZI) parameters, this means that KG Kunhalom had the best protein and gluten quality potential. Also only KG Kunhalom with N₁₅₀PK fertilizing treatment complied with the Hungarian premium class. According to Hungarian standard, samples with control treatment and Hybiza with any fertilizing treatment were unfit to bakery use. Using Pearson's correlation analysis results, CP and ZI were in tight positive; WGC was in medium positive, while gluten index was in loose negative correlation with fertilizing. In the case of growing wheat for baking use, there is a need to put great emphasis on selecting the right cultivar and agrotechnology practices.

Key words: winter wheat, cultivar, fertilizing, gluten quality, crude protein

INTRODUCTION

Wheat flour plays a very important role in our daily diet, which is the basic material of many industries (Ragasits, 1998). The quality parameters of wheat can be affected by many agrotechnical factors (Erdei, Szániel, 1975). Considering these factors, one of the most important is proper nutritional supply, which can be achieved by artificial fertilizing (Győri, Győriné, 1998). The usage of artificial fertilizers is influenced by nutrient reactionary properties of the cultivated wheat genotype (Pepó, 2011), as a result the basic condition of economical wheat production is the selection of the proper genotype (Ágoston, Pepó, 2005). According to Borghi et al., 1995, nitrogen fertilizer has a decisive influence on the baking quality of wheat. Above a certain threshold, increasing fertilizer dosage does not improve statistically yield and quality of winter wheat. This threshold was 180 kg ha⁻¹ N in Walsh et al., 2018 and 168 kg ha⁻¹ N in Shi et al., 2007 researches. The recommended optimal N fertilizer dosage is between 120-150 kg ha⁻¹ (Asthir et al., 2017; Horváth et al., 2014, Montemurro et al.,

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2007) to realize yield and quality potential of the genotype, to avoid nitrogen leaching out and plant lodging.

Nitrogen fertilizing can affect significantly the ratio and the amount of gluten proteins (Wieser, Seilmeier, 1998), therefore the baking test volume and the gluten spreading (GS) as well (Pollhamer, 1973). The cultivar properties had medium significant effect on wet gluten content (WGC), Zeleny index (ZI), crude protein (CP) and gluten index (GI) (Lukow, McVetty, 1991; Masauskiene, Ceseviciene, 2005). In the 4-year experiment of Pepó, 2002, when 120 kg ha⁻¹ N was given the WGC of GK Öthalom increased with average 5% comparing to the control ones. Fertilizer dosage was in medium correlation with gluten spread, tight positive correlation with crude protein and wet gluten content (Masauskiene, Ceseviciene, 2005; Eser et al., 2017), while Tanács, Gerő, 2003 did not find any relation between fertilizing and gluten spread.

Good quality wheat has above 40 ml Zeleny index, while ZI under 20 ml can result in unsatisfactory product quality (Baltás, 1998). Zeleny index is determined mainly by the effect of genotype (Branlard et al., 2001). Considering the Hungarian wheat standard, premium wheat flour has 14% CP, 34% WGC and 45 ml ZI.

The Glutomatic system is capable of giving information about not only gluten quantity, but quality as well. During this method, the washed gluten is put into a special sieve, then centrifuged. The percentage of wet gluten, that remains on the sieve is giving the gluten index. Gluten index (GI) above 90 refers to strong gluten, while GI under 30 refers to weak quality (Preston, Williams, 2003). According to Hlisnikovsky et al., 2014, elite class wheat has 25-27% WGC and 80-90 GI (Table 1).

Table 1

Some quality parameters of Czech national standard for wheat (Hlisnikovsky et al., 2014) and Hungarian national standard for wheat (MSZ 6368:2017)

Parameters	Czech wheat standard			Hungarian wheat standard		
	Elite class	Quality class	Bread class	Premium	I. class	II. class
Crude protein	12.6	11.8	11	14	12.5	11.5
Zeleny index	49	35	21	45	35	30
Wet gluten	25-27	23-25	20-23	34	30	26
Gluten index	80-90	66-80	41-65	-	-	-

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experiment was set up at Látókép Experimental Farm of University of Debrecen in the 2017/2018 growing season, which has a

chernozem soil type. The area has medium humus content, medium phosphorus and potassium supply and neutral pH. The forecrop of the experiment was sweet maize. Effect of three fertilizer levels (control, N₉₀P_{67,5}K_{79,5}; N₁₅₀P_{112,5}K_{132,5}) was tested in 10 m² plots in 4 repetitions. The 50 % of nitrogen and the whole amount of the phosphorus and potassium were applied in autumn, the remaining 50 % of the nitrogen fertilizer was applied in spring as top dressing. Following winter wheat genotypes were tested: GK Öthalom, Mv Ispán, GK Csillag, KG Kunhalom and Hybiza (hybrid genotype).

First the samples were treated by SLN Pfeuffer sample cleaner, then we conditioned them to 15.5 % moisture content, lastly ground into flour with Brabender Quadrumat Senior laboratory mill. Crude protein (Kjeldahl method), wet gluten content (ISO 21415-2:2015), Zeleny index (MSZ EN ISO 5529), dry gluten content (ISO 21415-4:2006), gluten index (ISO 21415-2:2015) parameters were defined at the Institute of Food engineering, University of Szeged, Faculty of Engineering.

For processing the results of the measurements IBM SPSS Statistics 22 program's one- and two-way ANOVA (with Tukey and Bonferroni post-hoc tests, on 0.05 significance level) and Pearson's correlation analysis were performed. According to Tóthné, 2011, there are tight, medium and loose correlations if the correlation coefficient is between 0.75-1, 0.5-0.75 and 0.25-0.5, respectively.

For graphical representation Python 3.7 version's Seaborn 0.9.0 library was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Months of the autumn were mild, and gradually cooling down with an abundant amount of rainfall. The mild weather of December and January was also favorable for wheat plants. Due to the cold weather of February and March, the plants were underdeveloped in the beginning of April. It was very hot in April and May, which was unfavorable for the vegetative development of wheat and shortened the phenological stages. In May, the rainfall and the fall in temperature could not compensate the negative effects of the previous period. The summerlike weather of June shortened the grain filling and maturity periods. To summarize, the weather of the 2017/2018 growing season was unfavorable for the vegetative and generative development of wheat plants.

According to our results, fertilizing and cultivar had significant effect on gluten quality parameters (Table 2). The main parameters varied between 7.9-14.4 (crude protein); 16.7-34.8 (wet gluten) and 20.4-45.2 (Zeleny index).

Gluten index was affected significantly by both cultivar and fertilizing. Considering N₉₀PK treatment, GI was decreased significantly compared to control samples. GK Öthalom (98.7-81.2) and Hybiza (96.1-93.2) had the highest gluten index. According to Preston, Williams, 2003, these two genotypes had strong gluten, and belonged to the ‘Elite class (80-90), 1st class in Czech standard’. Meanwhile Mv Ispán (83.5-66.3) belonged to the “Quality class (66-80), 2nd class in Czech standard”. KG Kunhalom (56.9-43.2) and GK Csillag (65.7-36.1) belonged to the ‘Bread class (41-65), 3rd class in Czech standard’ (Hlisnikovsky et al., 2014). Genotypes in different quality classes differed significantly. The results of Hybiza were pretty interesting, because this hybrid genotype was unfit to bakery use with any fertilizing treatment (Hungarian wheat standard), but its GI was one of the best, which means it had a very strong gluten.

Wet and dry gluten contents were significantly affected by N₉₀PK fertilizing treatment. Cultivar had also significant effect. KG Kunhalom had significantly higher, while Hybiza had significantly lower WGC and DGC results compared to the other genotypes.

Table 2

Effect of different cultivars and fertilizing treatments on the gluten quality parameters,
(Debrecen, Hungary, 2018)

Cultivar	Treatment	GI	WGC	DGC	GR	GS	ZI	CP
GK Öthalom	Control	98.7	16.7	5.9	2.8	0.4	20.4	8.8
	N ₉₀ PK	87.0	25.2	8.9	2.8	1.0	32.4	12.0
	N ₁₅₀ PK	81.2	28.3	9.6	3.0	0.8	36.7	13.1
Mv Ispán	Control	83.5	20.7	7.1	2.9	1.4	25.9	9.6
	N ₉₀ PK	69.4	27.1	9.3	2.9	1.5	35.1	12.0
	N ₁₅₀ PK	66.3	28.8	9.9	2.9	1.1	38.2	12.8
GK Csillag	Control	65.7	20.7	7.1	2.9	2.4	23.7	9.7
	N ₉₀ PK	35.8	29.7	10.1	2.9	5.3	34.9	12.8
	N ₁₅₀ PK	36.1	31.8	10.8	3.0	5.8	35.8	13.5
KG Kunhalom	Control	56.9	24.3	8.3	2.9	3.6	32.6	10.7
	N ₉₀ PK	44.3	34.0	11.5	3.0	4.2	42.5	13.8
	N ₁₅₀ PK	43.1	34.8	11.7	3.0	4.9	45.2	14.4
Hybiza	Control	96.1	16.8	5.7	2.9	0.4	23.8	7.9
	N ₉₀ PK	95.4	22.0	7.6	2.9	0.8	33.0	10.1
	N ₁₅₀ PK	93.2	23.2	7.9	2.9	0.8	35.1	10.5

Abbreviations: GI= gluten index, WGC= wet gluten content, DGC= dry gluten content, GR= gluten ratio, GS= gluten spreading, ZI= Zeleny index, CP= crude protein

Gluten ratio was not affected by fertilizer dosages. The GR results of KG Kunhalom were significantly higher than GK Öthalom.

Fertilizing, cultivar and the interaction of them had significant effect on gluten spread. Application of artificial fertilizers increased significantly the gluten spread of the samples, which result correlates well with Pollhamer, 1973. Studying the GS results two groups can be made: 1) GK Öthalom, Hybiza and Mv Ispán (0.4-1.5); 2) KG Kunhalom and GK Csillag (2.4-5.8). The GS results differed significantly between the two groups.

Zeleny index and crude protein were increased significantly by N₉₀PK fertilizing dosage, further fertilizer application did not have statistical effect. The ZI and CP results of KG Kunhalom were significantly higher than the other genotypes. Mv Ispán had higher ZI compared to Hybiza and GK Öthalom. Hybiza had significantly lower CP than the other 4 cultivars. The following statements proved that the Zeleny index is determined mainly by the effect of genotype, the findings of Branlard et al., 2001.

There was only one sample (KG Kunhalom, N₁₅₀PK), that met the parameters of premium class (Hungarian standard), moreover GK Csillag (N₁₅₀PK) and KG Kunhalom (N₉₀PK) complied with the 1st class, till then Mv Ispán (N₉₀PK, N₁₅₀PK) and GK Öthalom (N₁₅₀PK) complied with 2nd class (Hungarian standard) (Fig. 1). According to Hungarian wheat standard, samples with control treatment and Hybiza with any fertilizing treatment were unfit to bakery use.

Fig. 1. Crude protein in the case of 3 treatments (0=control, 3=N₉₀PK, 5=N₁₅₀PK) (Debrecen, Hungary, 2018)

These results suggest that, the optimal fertilizing dosage is N₉₀PK, application of more fertilizer also improves the parameters, but it is not statistically provable. If we take all information into account by Asthir et al., 2017; Horváth et al., 2014; Montemurro et al., 2007, we can see that in our research the recommended fertilizer dosage is lower. Presumably this was influenced by the year, cultivar and forecrop improving effect. In our research sweet maize was the forecrop, which does not exploit the nutrient and water supplies of the soil, and creates favorable condition for winter wheat.

Using Pearson's correlation analysis results (Table 3), we can state that CP (0.753**) and ZI (0.783**) were in tight positive; WGC (0.714**) and DGC (0.716**) were in medium positive, while GI (- 0.298*) was in loose negative correlation with fertilizing. This finding proved the statement of Masauskiene, Ceseviciene, 2005. WGC (0.971**), DGC (0.977**) and ZI (0.902**) were in tight positive; GS (0.553**) was in medium positive; GI (-0.680**) was in medium negative correlation with crude protein content. GS (- 0.917**) and WGC (- 0.759**) were in tight negative correlation with gluten index. Gluten spread did not correlate with fertilizing, so we confirmed the results of Tanács, Gerő, 2003.

Table 3

Correlation analysis between gluten quality parameters (Debrecen, Hungary, 2018)

	Fertilizing	GI	WGC	DGC	GR	GS	ZI	CP
Fertilizing	1							
GI	-.298*	1						
WGC	.714**	-.759**	1					
DGC	.716**	-.740**	.995**	1				
GR	.207	-.382**	.329*	.230	1			
GS	.220	-.917**	.645**	.621**	.383**	1		
ZI	.783**	-.549**	.922**	.916**	.325*	.444**	1	
CP	.753**	-.680**	.971**	.977**	.223	.553**	.902**	1

Abbreviations: GI= gluten index, WGC= wet gluten content, DGC= dry gluten content, GR= gluten ratio, GS= gluten spreading, ZI= Zeleny index, CP= crude protein

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

**.. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

CONCLUSIONS

Summarizing our results, the gluten quality parameters of winter wheat were significantly influenced by fertilizing and cultivars. On the basis of our measurements, N₉₀PK dosage improved significantly the measured

parameters, further fertilizer application had also improved effect, but this was not statistically provable. If we take all information into account by Asthir et al., 2017, Horváth et al., 2014, Montemurro et al., 2007, in our research the recommended fertilizer dosage was less than the amount they recommended (120-150 N kg ha⁻¹). Presumably this was because of the year, cultivar and forecrop improving effect. Application of artificial fertilizers increased significantly the gluten spread. GK Öthalom and Hybiza had the highest gluten index (belonged to the Elite class in Czech standard). The results of Hybiza were pretty interesting, because this hybrid genotype was unfit to bakery use with any fertilizing treatment (Hungarian wheat standard), but its gluten index was one of the best, which means it had a very strong gluten.

Using Pearson's correlation analysis results, gluten spread did not correlate with fertilizing, so we confirmed the results of Tanács, Gerő, 2003. CP and ZI were in tight positive; WGC was in medium positive, while GI was in loose negative correlation with fertilizing. Gluten index was in medium negative correlation with crude protein content.

In the year of 2018 with sweet maize as forecrop, KG Kunhalom had significantly higher CP, WGC, DGC, GR and ZI parameters, this means that KG Kunhalom had the best protein and gluten quality potential. Also only KG Kunhalom with N₁₅₀PK fertilizing treatment complied with the Hungarian premium class. According to Hungarian wheat standard, samples with control treatment and Hybiza with any fertilizing treatment were unfit to bakery use.

In the case of growing wheat for baking use, there is a need to put great emphasis on selecting the right cultivar and agrotechnology practices. In the future we will do the measurements in the next season as well, to extend our research with the year effect.

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THE ECOLOGICAL RECONSTRUCTION OF FOREST ECOSYSTEMS AFFECTED BY LANDSLIDES

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Abstract

Landslides mainly affect agricultural lands in Romania's hill areas or in proximity of water sources. They are caused by a complex number of factors (of geological, geomorphologic and climatic origin) as well as by the land's use. A significant part of Romanian's land fund is in an improper state ecologically-wise and productivity-wise, as a result of landslide processes. This imposes a series of actions, for both the agricultural and forestry sectors, in order to mitigate landslides.

The present paper emphasises the results of the investigations performed before 2000 and during 2015-2017, regarding the characteristics of landslides, their management/consolidation works, the forest culture species and types used on landslides, as well as their behaviour and efficiency. Experimental forest cultures established on landslides are 35 and 65 years old, so they can offer valuable scientific information regarding the types of cultures and silvotechnical works necessary for underlying ecological reconstruction solutions. The characteristics of landslides require the installation of forest vegetation only after the proper management of lands. The most important works are capturing and steering waters from outside the affected area, draining micro depressions with water excess, modelling the land as well as consolidation works for detachment ravines and versant basis. The forest vegetation installed on landslides ensures the land's stabilization as a result of regulation of the hydric regime and mechanical consolidation by roots.

Key words: landslide, ecological reconstruction, forest vegetation, management/consolidation works

INTRODUCTION

Landslides are included in land degradation processes that imply, as any degradation form, a deterioration process of the land's natural potential, significantly affecting the ecosystem's integrity, either by reducing the sustainability of the ecologic productivity or by reducing biological diversity.

Such phenomenon represents a major threat to human life, having devastating effects on the environment, economy (especially on communication) or socially (affecting human settlements).

In Romania, landslides strongly affect agricultural lands (especially meadows), as well as forest lands from hill, plateau or sub Carpathian hills over the entire country. Landslides occupy a surface of 702.000 hectares of agricultural lands, namely 2.9 % of the country's total surface (Dumitru et

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al., 2002) and approximately 95.000 hectares of afforested lands, namely 1,5% of the forest's surface. On 7.9 % of this surface, the phenomenon manifests with a high and very high intensity (Adorjani et al., 2008), especially near water courses.

The improper ecological and productive state of a considerable surface of the country's land fund as a results of land degradation and aridization (by accentuating climatic extremes, namely temperatures and precipitations) imposes a series of actions with an economical-social impact (Sabău and Iovan, 2018; Man et al., 2018). These actions involve both the agricultural and forest sector, being connected with improving and capitalizing or efficiently using degraded lands.

The problem of ecological reconstruction of lands affected by the harshest degradation processes (depth erosion, landslides) assumes a special importance under the severe vegetation conditions offered by these lands. As a result, this has become an important national strategy issue that involves both specialists as well as local authorities for finding the best solutions for stopping degradation processes and capitalizing these lands.

The present paper takes into account the results of investigations concerning the ecological reconstruction of landslides, emphasizing the effect of forest vegetation in stabilisation and mitigation of landslide lands, as well as the behaviour of the species used in afforestation.

The cost of works that must be realized for stabilising landslides cumulated with the losses suffered and the expenses for counteract unwanted effects lead to considerable sums of money.

All these inconveniences can be avoided by carefully monitoring areas that are predisposed to these phenomenon (Constandache et al., 2012) and by applying preventive measures (Popov et al., 2017; Dincă, 2004).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research have emphasized the following aspects:

- in the mountain area, composed mainly of hard and semi-hard rocks, landslides rarely occur, being represented by crumbling and rolling (approximately 60.000 ha of forests affected by this phenomenon were identified only in the Southern Carpathians) (Dincă and Achim, 2019);

- in watershed basins and sub-Carpathian hills, composed mainly of soft rocks (clay or marl) alternating with semi-hard or hard substrate (sandstone, gyps), landslides show a large development, being represented by consistent mass landslides, caving, plastic and slime drifts. Landslides are generated by a multitude of causes, among the most frequent being the erosive disruption of slopes by torrential flows, the oscillation of reclined layers with a different permeability.

- a decisive influence in preparing, activating and the dynamic of landslide processes is caused by the land's lithologic and structural characteristics (Untaru, 1979). As such, landslides are favoured by the oscillation of reclined layers that have different permeability. In their dry state, clays are strongly fissured, allowing an easy water penetration inside the layer, acting like an ointment and changing the initial rigid structure in a malleable system.

- relief conditions are decisive in the dynamic of landslide processes, influencing both the spreading and intensity and especially the manifestation forms. Among the relief elements, the slope and fragmentation degree show the highest influence on the land's stability. As such, slopes are predisposed to landslides, while the relief's fragmentation determines a dense network of valleys that undermine the slope's basis.

- climatic conditions play an important role with regard to landslide predisposition. A decisive role is manifested by lingering rains that occur on long periods of time, associated sometimes with a slow snow melting (Constandache et al., 2018). Temperature variations have negative effects on the land's stability, while dilatation-contraction processes have as a result the partial break of the soil's cementation links. water erosion has a significant importance in generating landslides, particularly depth erosion that determines a loss of land stability (Kachova and Dincă, 2015).

As a consequence, land's degradation through landslide is generated or favoured by a complex number of factors, agents and mechanisms (Constandache, 2001; Constandache et al., 2016b). The morphogenetic agents, correlated with specific geomorphologic factors, have generated a high variety of land degradation processes and forms. A multitude of slope processes through which the soil is removed and/or covered with non-fertile materials or that deform slopes and affect land stability are characteristic to hilly areas (Constandache and Nistor, 2008).

The study was carried out in 6 experimental blocs (30 permanent research areas) located in different forest cultures (pine ± broadleaved, poplars, willow, alder, black locust, oak, ash, etc.) from lands affected by different forms of landslides. The areas were located in different areas (phyto-climatic levels) from South-East Romania, an area highly predisposed to landslides.

The method consisted in direct observations, measurements and laboratory analyses, realized both in the field as well as in special research surfaces stationary.

Investigations regarding site conditions, management technologies, afforestation methods (compositions, schemes, techniques, etc.) and the effects of silvotechnical works were performed in research plots installed in stands affected by landslides (experimental forest cultures). The mapping of

landslides used the unitary site mapping method of degraded lands (Ciortuz and Păcurar, 2004). Direct observations and determinations were realized on the degraded land with regard to relief, soil, lithological substratum, the degradation's intensity and nature, the origin of water excess and vegetation. Determinations and observation that allow the establishment of the degradation's shape, nature and intensity as well as the effects of improvement works on the land and forest vegetation were realized in all research plots.

Experimental forest cultures established on landslides are 35 and 65 years old, so they can offer valuable scientific information regarding the types of cultures and necessary silvotechnical works for the selection of ecological reconstruction solutions.

The stands' state was permanently monitored through periodic measurements (5 years) over the main biometric (diameters, heights, etc.) and qualitative parameters (breaks, dieback) in the 30 long-term research plots.

The investigations were performed in perimeters from Moldavia Plateau (Valea Caselor –Vaslui County) and the Curvature Sub Carpathians (Caciu-Bârsești, Pârâul Sărat – Valea Sării, Ruget - Colacu, Roșoiu - Andreiașu–Vrancea County; Livada and Murgești – Rm.Sărat, Buzău County).

Observations regarding the characteristics of recent landslides affecting the forest fund as well as the application of ecological reconstruction measures were realized in Brodina – Suceava, Moinești – Bacău, Milcovel – Vrancea, etc. (Table 1).

Table 1

The GPS coordinates of the perimeters

Perimeters/County	GPS Coordinates	
	N (X)	E (Y)
Caselor Valley/Vaslui	570285.43	570285.76
Caciu-Bârsești/Vrancea	474842.99	612858.48
Sărat river- Sării Valley/Vrancea	489145.05	640417.99
Ruget-Colacu/Vrancea	491214.08	643778.98
Roșoiu-Andreiașu/Vrancea	473398.30	641243.76
Livada-Rm.Sărat/Buzău	435276.35	650414.95
Murgești-Rm.Sărat/Buzău	434781.99	649493.60
Brodina/Suceava	709530.36	530669.85
Moinești/Bacău	UPI	564841.28
	UP V	548140.82
Milcovel/Vrancea	477625.03	648893.02

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main components of a landslide are:

-detachment ravine situated in the superior part;

- landslide body;
- landslide basis (forehead).

Landslides, affected by mass dislocation gravitational processes, represent an important category of degraded lands that have posed significant and complex problems in the improvement and capitalization actions. The difficulties are generated by: the diversity of landslide types and manifestation forms in regard with the landslide's mass depth, degree and consistency; the large variety of vegetation conditions offered by these lands to different cultures etc.

Investigations realized in different areas (Buzău, Vrancea, Bacău, Vaslui, Suceava) have emphasized the fact that landslides affect almost all use categories; the largest part of landslide affected lands become unproductive (Zaruba and Mencl, 1974). In the case of lands from the forest fund, trees are bent and unrooted, with their state strongly affected. As such, the integral removal of the affected forest vegetation from the landslide's surface is necessary. Mixtures of soil with rocks are found in most cases on the land's surface, especially on meadows or on lands with water excess (Fig. 1-4).

Fig. 1. Landslide in forest area, OS Brodina, Suceava County (photo: Constandache, 2010)

Fig. 2. Hydro technical transversal works with the purpose of consolidating the slope's basis, pr. Milcovel, OS Focșani, Vrancea County (photo: Constandache, 2012)

The mapping of lands affected by slides has shown that land movement processes have led to the emergence of complex degradation forms, usually associated with:

- lands with strongly fragmented soil mass, with rock and soil complexes;

- lands with moderately drained zonal soils, when the landslide was deep (over 5-6) and the soil mass weakly fragmented;
- micro depressions with stagnant water or with fluid soil mass (slime streaming);
- detachment ravines with surface rocks.

The studied landslides are characterized by a multitude of shapes, according to their evolution stage, the trigger factor's intensity action and the circumstances in which they occur. With regard to the evolution stage, the entire possible range was recorded, from incipient landslides, emphasised through slight deformities in slope areas or small rifts, up to the most brutal manifestations, characterised by high displacements, with consistent sliding mass, plastic or slimy. In regard with the triggering factor's action intensity, slow up to very fast displacements were identified. The lithological, structural, stratigraphic and pedologic conditions in which landslides occur are reflected in: the general aspect of movements, their shape, the micro relief of sliding masses, the land's fragmentation degree, the soil's characteristics vegetation conditions etc. (Untaru, 1979).

Landslides are frequent in Sub Carpathian areas, especially in the inferior part of slopes, alongside rivers or cloughs and in areas characterised by lateral erosions or riverbed sinking (Fig. 3-4). Through erosion at the slope's basis, landslides are triggered. Landslide areas are extended regressively around the initial outbreak, both lateral as well as in the slope's superior part. They can affect the entire length of hydrographic network, with extensions send up to the slope's superior trinity. The systematic clearing, through torrential erosion, of land masses situated at the basis of slopes affected by older landslides cause their periodical reactivation (Untaru, 1979; Constandache and Nistor, 2008).

Fig. 3. Landslide along Rosoiu-Andreiasu river, OS Focșani, Vrancea County (photo: Constandache, 2017)

Fig. 4. Landslide with strongly fragmented soil mass, with the basis in Tazlăul Sărat river OS Moinești, Bacău County (photo: Constandache, 2019)

Silvotechnical works for the ecological reconstruction of landslides

The investigations showed that landslides can be stabilized through afforestation (Untaru, 1979; Silvestru-Grigore et al., 2018; Constandache et al., 2016a), but only after performing special land management works (Constandache and Nistor, 2008).

Taking into consideration the limitative factors for installing forest vegetation (landslides with an active movement process due to the slope's erosive disruption, the presence of micro depression with excess water or uphill water that infiltrates up to the clay layer), the afforestation works are recommended only after the stabilization of landslide masses through land consolidation/management works. Special consolidation works (namely consolidating the slope's basis) might be necessary in certain situations. Tree extraction and an ecological reconstruction with local non-profitable economic species that have a strong fixing power (oleaster – *Eleagnus angustifolia* L., sea buckthorn – *Hippophaë rhamnoides* L.) is recommended for the lands from forest area affected by landslides.

Management/consolidation works for landslides.

The consolidation works for landslides were integrated within the management works and measurements realized for torrential hydrographic basins. They have contributed in preventing landslide reactivation and stabilizing the unstable slopes.

An important role in stopping landslides was represented by special depth erosion works that have allowed a rapid instalment of forest vegetation on slopes and on the depth erosion formations (approximately 4 years). In addition, they have effectively contributed in consolidating landslides from neighbouring surfaces (Untaru et al., 1982).

Amongst the special consolidation works for torrential formations with a purpose in stabilizing landslides, we mention (Constandache and Nistor, 2008; Bogdan et al., 2015):

- consolidating gully beds and cloughs with local materials (dry masonry thresholds, polyethylene bags filled with soil on sucker beds and sea buckthorn branches, wattle work);

- transversal hydro technical works formed of thresholds and dams, on cloughs and torrents;

- re-establishing footing at the base on unstable slopes, with supporting walls or sand bags at the slope's base where a water course is present.

Very good results were obtained by masonry thresholds from stone without plaster, followed by vegetal thresholds realized from sea buckthorn fascine rolls, soil and stone. The consequence of these works was represented by a talweg raising, through the accumulation of the material transported from the slopes behind them, ensuring a lateral footing. The

main consequence was the changing of forces that act on the soil masses affected by the landslide, in a positive way, contributing to the landslide's stabilization.

The ensuring of slope stability as a consequence of creating a hydrographic network through hydro technical works has had an essential role in stabilizing slopes and ensuring afforestation conditions, as well as in protecting the roads from the slope's base.

Some works, such as those for supporting unstable slopes with supporting walls, had a limited application in stopping forest fund landslides.

The main landslide management/consolidation works achieved in different studied improvement perimeters are rendered below:

- ensuring the leakage/deviation of water originating from slope drains or from shore springs.

- eliminating water excess from micro depressions; ditches with a trapezoidal section were disposed ramified or "in spike" on the slope's highest line at a depth that reaches the stable rock layer in order to evacuate excess water and to drain micro depressions with stagnant water;

- the land's micro modelling, namely equalizing micro depressions and areas with mountainous relief, covering rifts in the case of strong soil fragmentation in order to prevent water infiltration in the soil's mass up to the sliding bed;

- consolidation works for landslide detachment surfaces through continuous fences, "armed with vegetation" terraces or narrow terraces on which green belts of white alder and sea buckthorn were established (Bârsești, Andreiașu perimeters) (Constandache et al., 2010); the fences have ensured conditions for installing forest vegetation on the small terraces sustained by them by protecting seedlings at excavation through a superficial erosion. In the cases in which twigs without a slipping capacity were used for wreathing fences, the works have shown their functional role in 5-6 years. A higher technical efficiency was registered for fences with green willow twigs, whose duration was prolonged up to eight years. Even in the case of reactivations which have moved and sometimes buried the fences, they managed to regenerate, leading to the land's coverage and consolidation (Bogdan et al., 2015).

The land consolidation works were used and adapted to specific local conditions. Some works, such as the ones for reinforcing unstable slopes and drainages, had a limited use in stopping forest fund landslides, especially in the situations in which important economic objectives had to be protected (roads, constructions etc.).

In the case of landslides situated outside objectives that require a special protection, the execution of the above-mentioned works was not

possible because of economic reasons. In these cases, landslides stabilization and mitigation were obtained over a longer period of time by applying a complex of measures and works subordinated to the integral management action of torrential hydrographic basins.

These works had an important role in creating conditions for installing forest vegetation and for ensuring a fast water drainage from areas affected by landslides.

Species, formulas and techniques for the afforestation of landslides

The high diversity of spatial conditions on narrow spaces has led to best results through cluster plantations composed of species adequate to real site conditions (Traci and Untaru, 1986). The clusters were composed of black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia* L.), ashes (*Acer spp.*), oleaster (*Eleagnus angustifolia* L.), birdcherry tree (*Prunus avium*), poplar (*Populus spp.*), ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) and sea buckthorn (*Hippophaë rhamnoides* L.).

In the case of mixture pine – broad-leaved cultures from lands with block landslides, the following species were used: pure pine clusters on 40 – 100 m², mixed with broad-leaved clusters on 20 – 50 m²; row and intimate mixtures with broad-leaved species.

According to Traci and Untaru, 1986, the density of plantations was of: 3000 – 5000 seedlings per hectare for black locust (6700 seedlings per hectare for dislocation surfaces); 4000 – 6700 seedlings per hectare for mixed pine broad-leaved cultures; 5000 – 6700 seedlings per hectare for oleaster cultures; 6700 – 15000 seedlings per hectare for sea buckthorn cultures (13.000 – 15.000 for belt plantations).

The same plantations procedures used for the afforestation of eroded lands (Constandache et al., 2010) was also generally used for landslides (Traci and Untaru, 1986). Those included bare-root planting in 30/30/30 cm planting holes, notch planting planting seedlings grown in containers etc.

The planting performed in holes on the rifts was used for fragmented lands, followed by their equalization and covering (Untaru et al., 1982). Due to the good soil's aeration from these places, the roots have developed very fast in depth. The growing of all species was superior, prevailing closed canopies and consolidating the land with 2-5 years earlier.

Forest cultures (white alder – *Alnus incana*, black alder – *Alnus glutinosa*, European ash – *Fraxinus excelsior* etc.) installed on landslide affected lands associated with the hydrographic network fulfil a more important role in land consolidation and in preventing the reactivation of mass sliding processes. This fact is caused by their biological drainage effect and through the surface horizon's consolidation. The observations

obtained for the evolution of land degradation processes have shown that both degradation and torrential processes have diminished considerably after the execution of hydrotechnical works for the correction of depth erosion networks (including the usage reorganization for reception basins). Landslides associated with the hydrographical network were stabilized in a proportion of 50 – 60 % through the consolidation effect of the realized works. However, it continues to be active in areas unaltered by works, in which the installation of forest vegetation was not possible (Traci and Untaru, 1986).

The investigations (Constandache et al., 2002) have shown that active erosion and mass dislocation processes occurred only on 7.7% of the basin's surface after 30-40 years from Roşoiu hydrographic basin's management with clay and sandstone (B.H. Milcov). This percentage can be compared with the initial 32.6% recorded before the management plan, in the conditions of an increased forest percentage from 8% to 64%. The active management works have occupied approximately 7% from the perimeter's surface before the management plans, with 2.6% for the semi active ones and 2% for the stabilized ones (Untaru et al., 1982). The surfaces affected by erosion and active dislocations were also identified on lands that were still used as pastures.

All these aspects confirm the fact that reinstalling forests on degraded lands represents an advantageous and efficient mean of reconstructing and improving the productive potential of these lands.

Investigations realized in forest cultures from landslides with different site conditions have emphasized the following aspects:

In oak plots (Murgeşti – Râmnicu Sărat, Valea Caselor – Vaslui), the species that have presented a good evolution of landslides with block sliding or weakly fragmented were sessile oak (*Quercus petraea* L.), black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia* L.) - on lighter soils with a sandy-clay up to clay texture; Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) and black pine (*Pinus nigra*) associated with mixture and helping broad-leaved species: Norway maple (*Acer platanoides*), birdcherry tree (*Prunus avium*), European ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*), Turkish maple (*Acer tataricum*), manna ash (*Fraxinus ornus*) and shrubs (wild privet – *Lygustrum vulgare*, common dogwood – *Cornus sanguinea* etc.), for heavy-textured soils. At the age of 40-45, sessile oak stands had a 0.7 consistency and an active vegetation state; pine stands also had a good behaviour at the same age on landslides with a reduced mobility. The Scots pine had higher growths as its biometric conditions are correlated with micro-site conditions (Fig. 5, Table 2). Black locust cultures had a good evolution with regard to their height and diameter growths up to the age of 25-30 when over 50% of the samples were affected by drought. As such, their maintenance is not advisable after the age of 25-30 as the

consistency decrease under 0.7 leads to their regeneration decrease. However, black locust stands have presented a good evolution of moderately up to strongly fragmented landslides (on light soils), followed by ash (on heavier soils with an ensured soil humidity). White/black poplar (*Populus alba/Populus nigra*) stands (monocultures or mixed cultures with different species: sea buckthorn (*Hippophaë rhamnoides*), alder (*Alnus spp.*), willow (*Salix spp.*) on lands with temporary water excess and crack willow (*Salix fragilis*) on lands with water excess have presented a good evolution up to the age of 25 years. The present state of white poplar and willow stands (that have reached age 40), emphasizes the effect of not performing regeneration cuts on time, leading to the weakening of tree vitality and the regeneration capacity. Black locust cultures have reached pretty good results on landslide dislocation surfaces, with rocks on the surface, clay-sandy up to clay texture and a reduced content of calcium carbonates. On the other hand, on predominantly clay layers (with a high CaCO₃ content), only sea buckthorn (*Hippophaë rhamnoides*) and oleaster (*Elaeagnus angustifolia.*) cultures have presented a satisfactory evolution.

Fig. 5. Distribution of trees by diameter classes a) Pi=Scots pine (*Pinussylvestris* L.) - P8; b) Pi.n, Fr. = Black pine (*Pinusnigra*) mixed with ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) - P9, on landslides with the mass of earth moved in blocks, weakly fragmented, in the perimeter of Valea Caselor (Vaslui county)

Table 2

The characteristics of 40 years old pines, in pure stands or mixed stands with ash on landslides with the mass of earth moved in blocks, weakly fragmented in the perimeter of Valea Caselor (Vaslui county)

Plot (P)	Average diameter (Dm)			Average high (Hm)			Number of trees / hectare		
	Pi	Pin	Fr	Pi	Pin	Fr	Pi	Pin	Fr
8	21.66			18.67			1094		
9		19.86	12.5		14.06	9.00		819	152
10	22.30		9.91	18.81		7.13	727		418

Caption: Pi= Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.); Pi.n = black pine (*Pinus nigra*); Fr = European ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*).

In sessile oak and common beech plots, on weakly fragmented landslides with block dislocation, black pine and/or Scots pine stands mixed with sycamore (*Acer pseudoplatanus*), European ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*), birdcherry tree (*Prunus avium*), and other shrubs have presented a good evolution, followed by sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) ones mixed with sycamore, Turkish cherry (*Prunus mahaleb*) etc. Their vegetation state is active at the age of 60, with a proper consistency (0.7-0.8).

Observations performed in permanent research plots have emphasized the fact that mass dislocation processes (predominantly through landslides) were stopped or considerably reduced (semi stabilised) on more than 80% of the surface after a period of 15-25 years from the execution of riverbed consolidation works. These were associated with tree and forest shrub plantations in the situations in which the afforestation was appropriately sustained by land management works consisting in eliminating water excess from depressions, micro-modelling the land and ensuring a rapid drainage of water afflux that overflows the landslides, associated with consolidation works for unstable slope basis. The obtained analyses have emphasized the following representative situations regarding the time period after which the dislocation processes stability was obtained or they were considerably reduced (Untaru et al., 2008): muddy or plastic superficial leaking, after 15 years; superficial landslides after 10-25 years; profound landslides after 15-25 years.

However, it must be mentioned that the stability of landslides with a depth higher than 3 m only through afforestation works proved to be hard to perform or unfeasible without the execution of water excess drainage works as well as works for sustaining and consolidating slope basis.

The investigation's research have emphasized the following types of forest cultures installed on landslides with different site conditions that have presented a good evolution and a high efficiency in stopping landslides (Traci and Untaru, 1986; Constandache, 2015):

- black pine (*Pinus nigra*) and/or Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) cultures mixed with broad-leaved species (sycamore, ash, forest birdcherry tree, manna ash, Turkish oak, dogwood, privet etc.) from landslides with block sliding, weak up to moderately fragmented, with a reduced mobility in the oak subarea up to the beech and coniferous belt;

- oak (*Quercus spp.*) cultures and/or ash in mixture with other broad-leaved and shrubs from landslides with block sliding, weak up to moderately fragmented from oak subarea up to the beech belt;

- black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) cultures, on landslides with light and medium soils from the silvosteppe up to the sessile oak subarea;

-black alder (*Alnus nigra*), white alder (*Alnus alba*), and willow (*Salix spp.*) from lands with water excess (in regard with the excess duration), from the *Quercus petraea* and *Fagus sylvatica* belt;

-sea buckthorn, oleaster (and indigo bush cultures from strongly fragmented cultures with surface rocks and landslide sliding surfaces, rich in calcium carbonates.

Amongst the preventive measures, we mention: avoiding the execution and location of insufficiently consolidated forest roads as well as different types of constructions in areas with a high landslide predisposition; using animals for towing wood material in sensible areas instead of forest machines. Also, eliminating grazing mentioned by Hinkov et al., 2019 is observed in our research.

CONCLUSIONS

The highest predisposition towards landslides is represented by lands from hilly areas and depression areas with clay or alternate marl and clay substratum.

Landslides are determined by the combined action of two or more causes, with the land's moistening as a general cause; the highest percentage is recorded by erosive disruption associated with land moistening.

Forest vegetation is remarkable through its positive effect in preventing landslides, by diminishing surface leaking and reducing erosion from the slope's basis in comparison with lands lacking forest vegetation; forest vegetation installed on landslides ensures slopes stability as a consequence of adjusting the hydric regime and mechanical consolidation through roots.

Water intake and steering works from outside the area affected by landslides represents the main prevention method for landslides. Micro modelling and levelling affected lands and eliminating water excess are management works necessary for creating conditions for installing forest vegetation.

Hydrotechnical works realized on water streams from areas affected by landslides represent the best solution for stopping erosive disruption, in consolidating unstable slopes from torrential hydrographic basins and in protecting forest roads; some consolidation works with supporting walls have a limited use in the forest fund.

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other studies (2008, 2010, 2019) for afforestation of landslides in forest lands on Vrancea, Bacău and Suceava County Forest Administration.

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EVALUATION OF SOIL WATER MANAGEMENT PROPERTIES BASED ON LiDAR DATA AND SOIL ANALYSES, AT FARM LEVEL

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Abstract

Rapid weather fluctuations with an increasing demand for resource use impacts crop production sustainability leading to severe use of land and water resources. Laboratory analysis and technological improvements, such as remote sensing, generate new information and knowledge, to ease the visibility of effects by agricultural practices, bringing new opportunities to better use resources and improve farming sustainability and water management practices. Irrigation use and assessment are important to assure the sustainability; planning and modelling based on soil-plant economy relationship by the use of technological innovation, as Lidar imagery, enhancing the precision to large scale knowledge gained a plot-farm level.

Agronomics, agriculture engineers, management technologies aim to reduce non-productive water use in agriculture. Finding the correlation between soil water retention and physical parameters contributes to irrigation management plant, therefore, reducing water use, cutting costs for agri-food production and reducing environmental impact.

Soil sampling is performed in two depth and analysis of soil physical and water retention parameters with the correlation of LiDAR survey proving in-depth on-field information. Silt-loamy texture makes a good texture, water retention capacity. A decrease of silt content in the upper layer (6.4 %), an increase of sand and clay (7 % and 28 %) respectively. Conventional soil cultivation made an impact on the soil upper layer. Soil water retention did not show the major fluctuation of two layers regarding pF values. LiDAR results shown the area is not susceptible to erosion, 68 % is in the 1st slope category and 28 % in the 2nd. LiDAR, clear understanding and visualisation of site laboratory data for different.

The field is well drained, vegetation period and cultivation could require scheduled, separated irrigation on land based on DEM and runoff lines helping to improve irrigation planning and water use efficiency. Demonstration the benefits of using high accuracy remote sensing LiDAR data, preventing water logging, misuse, and improve irrigation management and shows good examples to use in large scale to ease comprehensive understating of data.

Key words: remote sensing, LiDAR, soil properties, Water retention, farm/in, irrigation

INTRODUCTION

Continuous warmer climate, rapid weather fluctuation and unpredicted change of rainfall and increasing demand for agro-food production due to population growth, along with the need for efficient use of natural resources, is becoming more challenging with imminence to act precisely. Determining which land and crops have the capabilities give the best production in the given conditions for the available resources, starting

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at plot farm level to up-scale, using up to date innovations, such as remote sensing technology, is highly important for the advancement of efficient planning and management practices.

Water scarcity will become a fundamental problem that will trigger changes in agricultural cultivation and management practices especially in arid and semi-arid conditions. Establishing changes in soil and water management and cultivation requires detailed information and planning about soil parameters, water resources, and cultivation plan. Lack of appropriate agricultural management strategies towards proper irrigation management, increase plant stress during drought periods, and non-sufficient use of ameliorative and drainage facilities can result in soil degradation. Waterlogging caused from intensified rainfall has an outcome on arable land in soil cultivation and crop production. Precipitation impacts the integrity of the soil aggregates as they begin to diminish and infiltration rate decreases.

Laboratory analysis with technology improvements, such as remote sensing, help to determine different issues occurring and ease solutions. Increase of temperature, change of rainfall patterns, intensified drought frequency and severity will lead to higher water demand (Nagy et al., 2018) and decrease of supply. Supplementary irrigation is likely to become more important in agriculture to support agriculture and maintain crop yields and its quality in multiple climate types. Irrigation performance assessment is critical and vital to ensure the sustainability of irrigated agriculture and this can be supported by different field measurements and prediction of factors like soil texture and structure (Rabot et al., 2018) and water retention capacity. Planning and modelling the irrigation based on soil-plant economy relationship, experienced at plot-farm level, by use of technological innovations, such as LiDAR (Light detection and ranging) imagery, enhances the quality of understanding of laboratory data and potentially to up-scale such technological innovations (Demelezi, 2019).

Water availability, climate change, and soil composition create many areas that have intrinsically saline nature and cause the salinization of soil. Strategies on soil salinity management can be considered. Considering applying irrigation in the field we should have detailed information about soil physical properties and water sources (Gálya et al., 2015).

Cultivation requires detailed planning and information about soil parameters such as physical, chemical and microbiological soil parameters. Soil productivity should be maintained and improved over time, but this causes water resources depletion and misallocation of water resources based on the crop needs and weather conditions. Therefore, scheduling irrigation according to the average soil moisture content of the entire profile may be beneficial for plants and farmers. Soil analysis recovers enough information

about soil characteristics and linking them with LiDAR data of the arable land results in better management of the water and soil sustainability and sustainable production

The effects of climate change will create instability of crop production especially on the crops that are depended on irrigation or have high water demand. Identification and improvement of water management on arable field focusing on the soil water capacity and soil physical properties in relation to remote sensing technology, such as LiDAR is highly important. Soil conditions and soil water potential availability are crucial to be analysed and visualised, via remote sensing technology, to ease interpretation of practical use in large scale, since they support, makes room for the maximum supplement for plant needs considering the fact the moisture in the soil is an important crucial factor in nutrient cycling in the soil matrix. Good soil texture and structure of soil and water retention of the soil is important to have a good crop production to the farm. Therefore, the use of LiDAR may contribute to enhance the precision to a large scale by knowledge gained at plot-farm level.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The researched arable land is located in Nyírbátor, in this research are analysed the water management properties of the arable land (85.5 ha). Nyírbátor is located in Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg county in the eastern region of Hungary. Bátortrade Ltd. is located in Southeast of Nyírség, the location of the sampling is $47^{\circ}48'51.5''\text{N}$ $22^{\circ}09'21.7''\text{E}$, 147 metre above the sea level and with an area of 553 km^2 . Figure 1 shows the location of the sampling area indicated on purple, and sampling points on the field.

Fig. 1. Sampling area

Nyírbátor is situated on the edge of a moderately warm and moderately cool climate belt. The average annual temperature is $9.5 - 9.7^{\circ}\text{C}$, which increases during the growing season and reaches a value of around 16.6°C . On the hottest summer days, the maximum temperatures are

around 34 °C, the average temperature of the coldest winter days are between -17.0 ° C and -18.0 ° C. The annual rainfall is 570-600 mm, in the summer it is about 350-360 mm. The most common wind direction is north-east and south-east, with an average speed of 2.5 m / s.

In terms of terrain, the broad area is at altitudes between 117.5 and 183.4 meters above sea level. Approximately 50 % of the surface is corrugated plain and 40 % is of medium elevation. In the northern part of the region; high percentage of the soil is sandy and lamellic-arenosol brown forest soil. Considering the percentage distribution, the largest type is sandy soil around 37 %. The second one is the brown forest soils with 26 % (Soil Survey, 2014). The remaining 21 % is made up of marshy soils (4 %) and meadow soils (17 %). The area is mainly characterized by forest area (50 %) and arable land (35 %).

It is a dry area, however typical of the area to develop inland water, occurring as a result of the periodic rainy years. There is no stagnant water, constant water in the area. The depth of the groundwater is about 4 to 8 m (Gálya et al., 2018).

Soil sampling was performed in two depths, 30 and 60 cm. Since the upper layer of the soil is under cultivation and deeper depth can be considered as not influenced or actively under cultivation but affected by agricultural techniques. On the analysed arable land, we modelled at 102 points, representing more than 1 sample per hectare (1.19 samples/ha), from a total of 510 samples. Strategy chosen for analysis was proposed by Christakos and Olea, 1992.

The physical parameters of each sample were measured (> 2 mm, 200 µm - 2 mm, 50 - 200 µm, < 50 µm) to determine soil texture and soil water retention parameters as: maximum water capacity, minimum water capacity, moisture capacity, wilting point, available water, gravitational water and capillarity gravitational water content, in addition the GPS coordinates data were taken per sample.

Data processing

Based on the measured data, we created a GIS database (X and Y coordinates, and Z variables) according to UTM system (zone N34), and then prepared the maps using an appropriate interpolation method. We used kriging method to generate the maps, which is one of the most effective and often used methods for most spatial analysis in scientific articles, known as an interpolating technique (Virdee and Kottegoda, 1984), the spatial resolution of the map was set automatically to 0.5 m.

Processing numerous data's, we used Surfer and ArcGIS environment. In the first step of processing, we created grid files in the Surfer software environment by creating a grid file, with the Kriging gridding method.

Arable land was surveyed between harvesting the former crop and sowing the next one. The combination of the resulted appropriate factors provided a good opportunity to understand the topography of the area and evaluate differences in micro-relief and ignoring the vegetation. The aerial LiDAR survey was done by the Institute of Water and Environmental Management and Eurosense Ltd. On the arable land of 85.55 hectares with its immediate vicinity. Using IGI LiteMapper laser system, the resolution of LiDAR data points is 14.58 point/square kilometres thus it can be used to build high-resolution models.

The laser point cloud processed by photogrammetry was pre-processed with Global Mapper software. I also carried out a preliminary elevation profile analysis in the software for the arable site.

On the basis of the LiDAR image, I have made the digital elevation model and map of slope categories based on high-resolution LiDAR data. During processing I have made different optimisation methods for pixel aggregation. Then, I have sorted the roads, canals, and reservoirs. During the next phase, I have investigated the run-off and accumulation relations on the basis of slope conditions.

For the statistical analysis have used IBM SPSS Statistics 24 software used the descriptive analysis tool from the analysis tool, and the generated the statistical analysis for required parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of all parameters measured and estimated in the study described and discussed are presented such as soil physical analysis, soil moisture content analysis and comparison and correlation of results with the LiDAR digital elevation model.

Soil composition for the soil particles larger than 200 micrometres classified as sand and gravel in the upper layer of the soil is around 37 % while for the distribution in the deeper layer is 34.46 %. There is an increase of sand particles in the upper layer compared to the bottom to 7.37 % of sand.

Silt content for 30 cm depth had 57.3 % of silt and 61.27 % in 60 cm depth. Based on their spatial distribution there is decreased percentage of its content in the soil for the upper layer for about 6.4 % (Table 1). The underground level of 4 to 8 m provides an advantage for capillarity rise (Kirkham, 2007) to cache upper layers during the summer.

Silt is the determinant factor for our soil with high spatial distribution differences between two layers (Fig. 2). In two depths we can see a difference between their content in the soil. In the upper layer the mean is lower as well as the minimum concentration of silt particles is lower

whereas in the 60 cm depth where we have done analysis the mean and minimum concentration is higher.

Table 1

Statistical distribution for soil physical parameters analysis (in percentage)

Descriptive Statistics of soil particles								
	Min		Max		Mean			
	30 cm	60 cm	30 cm	60 cm	30 cm	Std. Error	60 cm	Std. Error
> 2 mm	0.1	0.01	29.0	31.40	3.64	0.58	2.73	0.475
200 μm - 2mm	15.8	15.6	46.6	49.60	33.31	0.72	31.73	0.6605
50 μm - 2 mm	26.0	39.2	76.8	77.80	57.3	0.97	61.27	0.832
< 50 μm	0.4	0.2	12.6	10.60	5.5	0.24	4.278	0.239

Fig. 2. Spatial Distribution of silt particles at 30 cm (left) 60 cm (right), with a site picture

The clay content of the soil particles smaller than 50 micrometres, for 30 cm (Table 1) depth their content is 5.5 % of clay for 30 cm depth and 4.27 % for 60 cm.

Soil texture calculation for 30 cm depth

$$37 \% (\text{sand}) + 57.3 \% (\text{silt}) + 5.5 \% (\text{clay}) = 100 \%$$

Soil texture calculation for 60 cm depth

$$34.46 \% (\text{sand}) + 61.27 \% (\text{silt}) + 4.27 \% (\text{clay}) = 100 \% \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Soil texture based on the data we determined that the soil parameters tell that on this soil we have the soil type Silty-Loamy texture. Characterised by a small percentage of clay and sand dominated by silt particles. Having a (Soil Survey, 2014) perfect combination for growth of most plants, fertile, fairly well drained and hold more moisture than sandy soil but are easily compacted. Loamy are comprised of a mixture of clay,

sand, and silt that avoid the extremes of clay or sandy soils and are fertile, well-drained and easily cultivated. They can be clay-loam or sandy-loam depending on their predominant composition and cultivation characteristics. If it is sandy soil its water holding capacity will be much lower than at clay (Soil Taxonomy, 2006).

Water in nature arrives in soil surface as precipitation, in form of rainfall, hail or snow. Soils contain pore, and that the size of these pores is determined by the particle size distribution of soil where here we have done its determination of the soil texture (Eq. 1).

The in-situ measurement of field water parameter provides the spatial distribution of water quality (Priju et al., 2014) which affect groundwater quality. Soils can hold different water holding capacity, the higher the percentage of silt and clay sized particles, the higher the water holding capacity affected as well by organic matter. Smaller particles, less than 50 μm (clay and silt) have a much larger surface area than the larger sand particles.

The total water content of the soil for 30 cm depth (Table 2) the minimum measured was 30.92 % while the maximum 48.34 % and the mean value was 38.42 % with a standard deviation of 3.21 %. Arable land soil is cultivated and under conventional tillage (Busari et al., 2015).

Table 2

Statistical distribution for soil physical parameter in 60 cm depth

Descriptive Statistics for soil samples at 60 cm depth								
	Min		Max		Mean			
	30 cm	60 cm	30 cm	60 cm	30 cm	Std. error	60 cm	Std. Error
Total water content	30.92	29.42	48.34	45.0	38.42	0.344	38.17	0.31
Minimum water capacity	11.09	9.19	40.96	40.62	27.03	0.7	26.17	0.78
Field capacity	4.61	1.75	36.58	37.73	19.05	0.86	18.95	0.88
Wilting point	1.43	2.16	25.21	23.5	10.90	0.46	10.83	0.41
Available water content	4.01	1.95	25.85	25.94	11.14	0.44	10.78	0.48
Gravitational water	0.11	0.8	20.42	20.77	8.94	0.45	9.606	0.47

Figure 3 the spatial distribution of total water content differs in two depths. Important to mention that in the middle-south part of the plot is the area where is both depths are the minimum of water content. Deep ploughing (FAO Soils Bulletin 54) which is mostly applied in the farm has the ability to reach the depth of 35 cm on average and since the parental

material and the soil horizons are the same from the depth of 10 to 120 cm on average, the soil contents can be the same for the same horizon based on Rasmussen, 1999. Continuous cultivation of the soil causing severe compaction in the 30 cm depth because of conventional farming and decreasing of organic matter and soil moisture conditions.

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of water content: a) Total water capacity; b) Minimum water capacity

The minimum water capacity is the amount of water hold in soil after few days of free drainage for the depth of 30 cm a mean of 27.03 % with a standard deviation of 6.08 %. In the 60 cm a mean value of 26.17 with a standard deviation of 7.35 %. Spatial distribution of soil analysis for minimum water holding capacity shows that we have three main areas with heterogenous distribution of water holding capacity, both layers have similar minimum water holding capacity.

Field capacity (Denmead and Shaw, 1962) names the amount of water which can be held in soil after free drainage of excess water. On 30 cm depth the mean values are 19.05 % with a standard deviation of 8.09 %. In the 60 cm depth the mean value of 18.95 % with a standard deviation of 8.25 % (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of water content: c) Field capacity; d) Wilting point

The wilting point of the soil is considered where the plants' wilt as a lack of moisture in the soil (Kirkham, 2007) for the upper layer of the mean value is 10.9 % with a standard deviation of 4.41 %. Lower values for a 60 cm depth layer are observed with a mean value of 10.83 % and a standard deviation of 3.89 %. Evaporation from the soil surface, transpiration by plants and deep percolation combined reduce soil moisture status between water applications. Soil water content reaching wilting, plants become stressed and wilt.

Available water of the upper layer has mean values of 11.14 % with a standard deviation of 4.12 %, in the deeper layer, we also noticed lower values of available water content the mean values are 10.78 % with a standard deviation of 4.55 %. The surface water generated from rainfall or irrigation moves horizontally or in surface based on the slope of the land, groundwater moves laterally and slowly towards the sea to complete the hydrological cycle, but part of it will seep into springs, streams, rivers, and lakes on the way.

Gravitational water (Kirkham, 2007) is the free water moving through soil porosity by the force of gravity for 30 cm depth mean values of 8.94 % with a standard deviation of 4.22 % in the deeper layer of the soil a mean of 9.6 % with a standard deviation of 4.42 % and spatial distribution seen in figure 5. The greater difference between the gravitational water mean values. A slower rate of movement of gravitational water on the soil causing flooding in case of higher amounts of water found in the upper surface as in case of heavy rainfall or excessive irrigation.

Fig. 5. Spatial distribution of water content: e) Available water content; f) Gravitational water

The capillary rise is the available water transported upwards by a capillary rise from the water table and surface tension properties (cohesion and adhesion forces) to the root zone depends on the soil type, the depth of the water table and the wetness of the root zone. Capillarity water can

normally be assumed to be zero when the water table is more than about 1 m below the bottom of the root zone.

Remotely sensed data such as LiDAR brings a high advantage on data gathering and visualisation of site information. Analysing (Johannsen and Carter, 2004) adding GIS maps and digital terrain and field operation information is valuable in plot-farm level, aiming with LIDAR data to potentially experience use of it on large scale, in much detailed analysis. Assist and ease decision making much faster in the agricultural sector particularly in productivity and environment management.

Digital elevation model (Fig. 6, below) of arable land based on processed LiDAR data. Showing elevation difference of 10 meters, in the northern part of the area is higher (151-156 m), while the southern part of it is lower (149-146 m) indicated in brown colour. The slope map of the area with a spatial resolution of 0.5 m, higher the resolution the much better the accuracy of the slope delineation.

Fig. 6. a) Digital elevation model with run-off lines; b) Slope categories; c) Histogram of slope categories

Field slope map were created 5 categories (0-5 %; 5-12 %; 12-17 %; 17-25 %; > 25 %). Having 68.30 % of area in 1st category (0-5 %) distribution as flat land and 28.23 % of the arable land belongs to the second category of the slope. Slope categories 12-17 %, 17-25 %, and more than 25 % represent a smaller percentage of the area in total 3.49 % of the total arable land (Fig. 6c).

Water can easily come to a stop on these areas and create waterlogged areas, the infiltration of air and water is decreased because of soil tillage (Rasmussen, 1999). Areas where are paths on the field for machinery movement and transport or channels for excess water. Soil heterogeneity (Chen et al., 2017) affects the distribution of soil moisture through variation in texture, organic matter content, porosity, structure, and macro-porosity, all of which affect the fluid transmission and retention properties (Mohanty

and Skaggs, 2001). Research of Gilding, 1983 shows that during summer or drought periods the moisture content or the available water is decreased more in the upper portion of the soil.

With DEM we can create the runoff map of the arable land (Bales et al., 2007) (Fig. 6a) from the elevation data differences in connection with soil water retention under the climatic information of the region there might be areas of waterlogged areas. Runoff lines created by DEM can help drain the field. Although the south area is more prone to waterlogging, drain channels should be considered.

GIS and remote sensing techniques are vital means, providing better alternatives compared to conventional techniques in monitoring and assessment of drainage (Singh, 2018) as well they could be used for irrigation planning, irrigation performance, water management practices, monitoring of irrigation at different scales and water resource utilization (Bastiaanssen et al., 1999). Prone to excess water based on tables 1 and 2 and figure 3 the south part of the field shows lower values of the field distribution in each parameter. Evaluation of irrigation programs for the field to separate the area for better water management and soil cultivation and LiDAR possibilities of area delineation factors contributing to soil water management.

CONCLUSIONS

Variation of soil analysis in two depth 30 and 60 cm could be seen more easily when they were displayed used ArcMap for their spatial distribution these variations were observed as well by Mohanty and Skaggs, 2001. The arable land texture is classified as silt-loamy, a comparison of two depths of soil texture showed that clay and sand content has been increased in the upper layer (28 % and 7.37%) while silt content dropped (6.4 %) compared to the deeper soil layer.

Smoothed spatial distribution in the upper layer and scattered in a 60 cm layer, changes which have come from soil cultivation, conventional soil tillage practice, and weather condition. Cultivation practices made an impact up to 30 cm of the soil depth. On the 60 cm layer had more variances, divergent and higher standard error results compared to 30 cm layer with less variation regarding soil texture classification.

Excluding the total water content seen an increase of maximum values reached and the available water content of the soil is lower in the deeper layer. Other soil water retention parameters of the soil did not show major fluctuation of two layers related to pF values of the soil.

LiDAR data shows us the whole field and understand the DEM, DSM. It resulted that the area is not susceptible to erosion since 68 % is in the first category of the slope and 28 in the second category of the slope. Elevation

models and surface model which were created to a raster display permits to optimise cultivation, irrigation practices, water flow and logging in the field.

The field can be well drained, applying irrigation should be scheduled/separated for different areas of the same field. DEM and runoff line would improve irrigation planning and water use efficiency. Increased water use, intensified droughts, and weather fluctuation will require improved agricultural practices toward appropriate crop production and sustainable development.

The use of remotely sensed data such as LiDAR brought a high advantage on data gathering and visualisation of site information. Hence, mapping and digitalisation of terrain information are valuable, comprehensive and easily understandable in plot-farm level.

As such, LiDAR experience benefits at plot-farm scale and it brings advantages to up-scale its larger agricultural zones.

Results demonstrate the spatial visualization of data the benefits and advantages of using high accuracy remote sensing LiDAR data to prevent possible field waterlogging, finding of soil hydrological characteristics and the correlation with results soil parameters analysis for a better water and irrigation management planning.

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DOLOMITE AND CALCITE TREATMENTS APPLYING IN MELIORATION OF AN ACIDIC SANDY SOIL

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Abstract

*In the Institute of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science of Debrecen University in pot experiment, the effect of two carbonate containing amendments are examined on some properties of an acidic humous sandy soil ($pH_{H_2O}=5.2$) originating from Nagykáta. In the two treatments the amendments were granulated dolomite and calcite, the applied quantities were $3 t ha^{-1}$. In the amelioration pot experiment all treatments enriched NPK fertilizers taking into account the nutritional requirements of test plant (*Phaseolus vulgaris nanus L*); it was a „Yellow-podded - Maxidor” bean.*

On the bases of the first year results, the water management parameters were influenced positively by dolomite and calcite treatments. The water permeability of sandy soils decreased significantly in dolomite treatment. At the same time, the water holding capacity of the soil increased almost equally due to dolomite and lime doses. The pH of the soil increased, the hydrolytic acidity decreased, both under the influence of dolomite and lime, but the soil remained acidic. Among microbiological soil properties the number of total bacteria, the activity of saccharase, urease and dehydrogenase activity increased significantly, especially in the dolomite treatment. The CO_2 -production didn't change significantly in the treatments.

The intensive soil management, the application of high fertilizer doses affect negatively on soil reaction (pH), thereby some features of the soil would deteriorate; so the soil acidification affects an increasing proportion of agricultural land. With these results we would like to draw attention to the importance of soil amelioration of acidified soils with natural, carbonate-containing materials.

Key words: dolomite, calcite, acidic sandy soil, water management, chemical, microbiological characteristics of soil

INTRODUCTION

Sustainable agriculture (Velten et al., 2015) is an integral part of sustainable soil use (Oneţ et al., 2015), the preservation of our soil, and continuous amelioration of soils with bad qualities to increase soil fertility (Kocsisné et al., 2013).

Increased use of fertilizers and intensive soil use contribute to acidification of soils (Nduwumuremyi, 2013; Horváth, 2019). In Hungary the proportion of acid soil is about 25 % of the agricultural land. Studies prove the beneficial effects of lime and lime containing amendments on the chemical and microbiological soil properties (Zsuposné Oláh, 2002).

Gustavo Spadotti and Carlos Alexandre, 2015, studied the effects of surface lime and silicate treatments on chemical properties of soil, on soybean and corn test plants. Increased the concentration of N, Ca, and Mg

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in the leaves (Kátai et al., 2019), and also increased the seed yield of soybeans. In the experiment of Kovacevic et al., 2017, the dolomite also increased the yield of soybean, the protein content of the seed, and the oil content depending on the dose.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The pot experiment was set up in 2017 in the Debrecen University, Department of Agrochemistry and Soil Science on acidic sandy soil ($\text{pH}_{(\text{H}_2\text{O})} = 5.2$) with low humous content ($\text{Hu} = 0.67\%$) from Nyírkáta (Hungary). Every pot had 12 kg soil. Treatments were the same – 3 t ha^{-1} - with dosages of dolomite and CaCO_3 , separately.

The water content of treatments was in the same level, as the 70 % of the maximum water capacity. The pots were sprinkled in every day to the same mass. The test plant was the yellow pod – Maxidor type bush bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris nanus L.*).

As basic treatment NPK were added to every one kg soil, in form of ammonium nitrate solution (nitrogen), and P_2O_5 and K_2O solution of potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate and potassium sulphate.

Soil samples were taken in the tenth week after the seeds sprouted. The seeds were sowed 27. April in 2017. After the sampling the experiment was liquidated (7. July 2017).

Among the physical parameters of soil the moisture content (Klimes-Szmik, 1962), the water permeability and water holding capacity was measured according to Vér, 1979.

From among the chemical futures the pH of soil was measured in suspension of distilled water and M KCl [$\text{pH}_{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$; $\text{pH}_{(\text{KCl})}$] and the hydrolytic acidity (Filep, 1995), further nitrate nitrogen content and after 14 days incubation the level of nitrate mobilization (Felföldy, 1987) was determined.

Among the microbiological parameters the total numbers of bacteria (in meat soup agar), the number of microscopic fungi (in peptone glucose agar) was determined by plate dilution method according to Szegi, 1979. The further parameters were the soil respiration (Witkamp, 1966), the activities of saccharase enzyme (Frankenberger and Johanson, 1983), urease (Kempers cit. Filep, 1995) and dehydrogenase enzyme (Schinner et al., 1996).

This study aimed to evaluate the effect of improving materials on some physical, chemical and microbiological properties of an acidified sandy soil.

Statistical evaluation (Szűcs, 2002) was done by SPSS 13.0 program. The applied program was the One Way ANOVA, with the Duncan^a – test,

which showed the differences between the effects of treatments on significant level of 5 % advantageous offer in agricultural calculating, and correlation (*Pearson*) and regression analyses were taken between the measured soil parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Among the soil water management parameters the moisture content of soil was higher the both dolomite and lime treatments, than in the control. The water permeability of sandy soils decreased significantly in dolomite treatment, while the water holding capacity of the soil increased similarly by the dolomite and lime doses (Table 1).

Table 1

Effects of treatments on same water management parameters of soil

Treatments	Moisture content (%)	Water-permeability (ml 10 sec ⁻¹)	Water holding Capacity (n _m %)
Control	10.78a	113.3b	7.32a
Dolomite	15.14b	101.0a	13.65ab
Calcite	14.23b	110.2ab	15.00b
LSD ($p \leq 0.05$)	1.75	10.00	6.95

Regarding the chemical soil properties, soil pH increased slightly in the two amended treatments, but the pH of the soil remained acidic. At the same time, the hydrolytic acidity was reduced, but not significantly. The nitrate N content of the soil increased significantly as a result of the dolomite treatment, the net nitrification after 14 days of incubation increased, but the changes not statistically verified (Table 2).

Table 2

Effects of treatments on same chemical parameters of soil and the extent of the net nitrification

Treatments	pH _(H2O)	pH _(KCl)	Hydrolytic acidity (y ₁)	Nitrate-N (1) (mg 1000g ⁻¹)	Nitrate-N (2) (mg 1000g ⁻¹)	Net nitrification (mg 1000g ⁻¹)
Control	5.43a	4.20a	12.39a	8.86a	15.46a	6.60a
Dolomite	5.89b	4.46b	10.88a	11.42b	20.44b	9.02a
Calcite	6.01b	4.50b	10.55a	10.18ab	19.43b	9.25a
LSD ($p < 0.05$)	0.16	0.06	1.9	1.35	3.11	2.74

Among the biological properties of the soil, we have determined the total number of bacteria; it has increased by both treatments. In addition to dolomite, the number of bacteria was slightly higher (Table 3).

The number of microscopic fungi decreased in the treatments due to the increasing pH. The CO₂-production did not change by the treatments.

Table 3

Effects of treatments on some measured microbiological parameters of soil

Treatments	Total number of bacteria (*10 ⁶ g ⁻¹ soil)	Total number of fungi (*10 ³ g ⁻¹ soil)	CO ₂ -production of soil (CO ₂ mg 100g ⁻¹ 10 days ⁻¹)	Saccharase enzyme (glucose mg 100g ⁻¹ 24h ⁻¹)	Urease enzyme (NH ₄ -N mg 100g ⁻¹ 24h ⁻¹)	Dehydrogenase enzyme (INTF µg g ⁻¹ 2 h ⁻¹)
Control	5.14a	89.33b	14.35a	3.43a	19.53a	62.70a
Dolomite	6.23b	69.33a	15.12a	5.39b	42.07b	88.77b
Calcite	5.95ab	60.00a	14.89a	3.92ab	49.16c	88.60b
LSD (<i>p</i> < 0.05)	0.88	18.58	5.02	1.76	3.99	19.09

Among the activity of soil enzymes, the urease activity increased to the greatest extent, especially in the calcite treatment. Dehydrogenase activity was also significantly increased, almost the same level in the two treatments. More than doubled the saccharase activity increased, the greatest effect of the two amendments

Correlation analyses (*Pearson*) shows several close correlation among the soil parameters caused by soil improving material. Only a few of the correlations are highlighted, which have proved to be true in the case of lime and dolomite. The correlation coefficient (*r*) demonstrated a close positive correlation between the water holding capacity of the soil and the total number of bacteria (dolomite series *r* = 0.833; CaCO₃ series *r* = 0.709) (Fig. 1).

Further close or medium scale correlation was found between changes in hydrolytic acidity of soil and the number of microscopic fungi (dolomite series *r* = 0.715; CaCO₃ series *r* = 0.616) (Fig. 2).

The nitrate N content of the soil has close correlation some microbial parameters: with the urease activity (dolomite series *r* = 0.880; CaCO₃ series *r* = 0.876) (Fig. 3), also with total bacteria number (dolomite series *r* = 0.810; CaCO₃ series *r* = 0.767) (Fig. 4).

Fig. 1. Correlation between the water holding capacity and the total number of bacteria in the experiment

Fig. 2. Correlation between the hydrolytic acidity and number of microscopic fungi in the experiment

Fig. 3. Correlation between the nitrate -N and the urease activity in the experiment

Fig. 4. Correlation between the nitrate -N and the total number of bacteria in the experiment

CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to evaluate the effect of two improving materials - dolomite (3 t ha⁻¹) and calcite (3 t ha⁻¹) grist's - on some physical, chemical and microbiological properties of an acidified sandy soil. The results in the first year of the experiment have shown the following:

The parameters of water management, e.g. water permeability and water holding capacity were equally influenced positively by treatments;

Soil pH increased by the effect of dolomite and calcite, but due to its strong acidity, the soil stayed in acidic range; the lime increased the pH greater extent, but not significantly;

The hydrolytic acidity (y_1) decreased by the amendments, the soil acidity decreased. The lime application caused significantly higher decrease in this parameter.

The nitrate-N content increased in the amended treatments, improving materials had a positive effect on the nitrate mobilization, similarly the nitrate exploration rate also increased compared to control.

Regarding the microbial parameters, the number of total bacteria, the activity of saccharase enzyme increased significantly in the dolomite treatment. At the same time the number of microscopic fungi decreased significantly in both amended treatments. The activities of urease and dehydrogenase increased in both treatments, but the quantity of CO₂-production was not changed by amendments.

Between the measured soil parameters close correlation was proved in many cases. The pH was close correlation with urease and dehydrogenase activity; the hydrolytic acidity was close negative correlation with the total number of bacteria; the nitrate-N content was close correlation with number of bacteria, and the activity of urease enzyme.

In Hungary about 2.2 million hectares acidic sandy soil can be found. To improving these calcium and magnesium deficient acidic sandy soils, the application of soil amelioration is necessary. In a pot experiment the application of dolomite and calcite as amendments changed the physical, chemical and microbiological soil properties. Parameters of water management, the pH-conditions become more favourable. Due to the favourable environment, the biological activity of soil also positively has changed.

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VARIABILITY OF THE MAXIMUM AIR TEMPERATURE BETWEEN 1961 AND 2018 AT ARAD, ROMANIA

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Abstract

The paper presents the analysis of the temporal variability and the linear trend of the annual and monthly maximum air temperature, of the variability of the decennial maximum air temperature, of the annual and monthly number of summer days and tropical days, as well as the linear trend of the annual number of these days. For this purpose, the meteorological data on the daily, monthly and annual maximum air temperature were used, from the Arad weather station, on the period 1961-2018. The result was that the absolute maximum air temperature was 40.8°C in Arad and was recorded on 5th August, 2017. The linear trend of the annual maximum temperature was upward. We notice the increase of the values of annual maximum temperature starting with the year 1988, the increase being even more pronounced since 2000. The decennial maximum temperature increased from the 2nd decade to the 6th decade by 4°C. The linear trends of the monthly maximum air temperature, for all 12 months of the year, were upward. The most pronounced increase in the monthly maximum temperatures occurred, in the last years, in the summer months, in May and in the winter months. The annual number of summer and tropical days has increased greatly since 1992. During the period 1992-2018, the summer season extended by 15 days, on average. In the last 10 years, the summer season extended by 21 days, on average. The linear trends of the annual number of summer and tropical days are upward, the increase of the number of tropical days being more pronounced than that of the summer days.

Key words: maximum air temperature, variability, trend, summer days, tropical days

INTRODUCTION

The absolute extreme temperatures – absolute maximums and minimums – represent instantaneous values reached by the air temperature at a given time, being unique cases. They are usually random, registering at large intervals of time. However, they play an important role in assessing the climate of a region, showing the possible limits between which the air temperature may vary. Their values depend on the intensity of the solar radiation, the general circulation of the atmosphere, the local physical and geographical conditions (Climate of Romania, 2008).

Arad City is located in western Romania, in the northern sector of the Banatului Plain, which is part of the Western Plain of Romania. The city represents the residence of Arad County and stretches on both sides of the Mureș River. Arad weather station is located to the north of the river, in the sector that belongs to Aradului Plain, a subdivision of the Banatului Plain (Șerban, 2010).

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Banatului Plain is a territory where the advections of continental-tropical hot air masses are frequent and are felt during the year regardless of the season, generating heat in summer or episodes with very mild weather in winter. Therefore, it is important to know how much the maximum temperatures varied over the years and what is their trend in recent years, in the context of climate change. Heat waves that are becoming more frequent and intense in recent years are affecting human health, as well as the ecosystems. For humans, high temperatures cause thermal discomfort, sleep disturbances, decreased performance and productivity, cardiac and respiratory symptoms (Şerban et al., 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this paper, the meteorological data on the daily, monthly and annual maximum air temperature were used, from the Arad weather station. The studied period was 1961-2018 (58 years).

The Arad weather station is located in the Mureş River meadow, at a distance of 900 m from the river, being one of the oldest stations in the country, with measurements starting in 1880. It is located at an altitude of 116 m, having the geographical coordinates 46°08' latitude N and 21°21' longitude E. The station code is 15200 (<http://www.meteoromania.ro/>).

The paper presents the analysis of the temporal variability and the linear trend of the annual and monthly maximum air temperature, of the variability of the decennial maximum air temperature, of the annual and monthly number of summer days (days with the maximum air temperature $\geq 25^{\circ}\text{C}$) and of tropical days (days with the maximum air temperature $\geq 30^{\circ}\text{C}$), as well as the linear trend of the annual number of these days.

The data regarding the maximum air temperature come from the database of the National Meteorological Administration in Romania and from the website www.meteomanz.com.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the Arad weather station, *the multi-annual average air temperature* for the period 1961-2018 was **10.8°C**, being higher than that of the period 1961-2002, when it was 10.5°C (Şerban, 2010). During the analyzed period, the annual average air temperature varied between 9.4°C (in 1978 and 1980) and 12.9°C (in 2018). The high multi-annual thermal value is due to the altitudinal and latitudinal position of the station, which makes the values of the radiative-caloric balance to be higher, but also to the frequent advections of the tropical, hot air masses, specific to the southwest of the country.

Compared to the multi-annual average temperature, *the multi-annual maximum air temperature* over the same period of time was **40.8°C**. The

value coincides with *the absolute maximum air temperature* recorded in Arad. This value was recorded on **5th August, 2017**. Until then, the absolute maximum temperature in Arad was 40.4°C, recorded on 16th August, 1952 (Şerban, 2010).

The annual maximum temperature has varied over the years. The highest values rose to 38-40°C and produced especially after 2000. Thus, the years with the highest values were 2017, 2007 and 2000. There are 9 years with the annual maximum $\geq 38^\circ\text{C}$, 7 of them being between 2000 and 2017 (Table 1, Fig. 1). 10 years have the annual maximum temperature between 37.0-37.8°C, 8 of them being in the range 1992-2011.

Table 1

The years with the highest values of the annual maximum air temperature at the Arad weather station (1961-2018)

Crt. no.	Year	Value (°C)	The day when the annual maximum temperature was recorded
1	2017	40.8	5 th August, 2017
2	2007	40.2	24 th July, 2007
3	2000	39.1	21 st August, 2000
4	2008	38.5	15 th August, 2008
5	1961	38.3	12 th August, 1961
6	1988	38.3	6 th July, 1988
7	2012	38.3	24 th and 25 th August, 2012
8	2015	38.1	8 th and 22 nd July, 2015
9	2013	38.0	29 th July, 2013

Fig. 1. The variation of the annual maximum air temperature and its linear trend, at the Arad weather station (1961-2018)

The highest values of air temperature were reported in August and July (Table 1). They are hot summer months, when the anticyclonic baric

formations prevail and the land surface is strongly heated by the sun. The attainment of such high values of temperature is due to the advections of tropical, very hot and dry air masses, coming from the north of Africa and the persistence of this air over Romania.

From figure 1 we can see an increase in the values of annual maximum temperature starting with the year 1988, the increase being even more pronounced since 2000. Moreover, the linear trend of the annual maximum temperature is *upward* in Arad, for the period 1961-2018. The increase is in line with the trends of the increase of the air temperature of the last decades, reported in the specialized literature from global and national level (Wang et al., 2004; Fratianni, Acquaotta, 2010; Tang et al., 2010; Nastos et al., 2011; IPCC, 2014, <http://www.ipcc.ch>; Măhăra, 2006; Teodoreanu, 2007; Climate of Romania, 2008; Şerban, 2010; Şerban, Dragotă, 2013; Man et al., 2018; Şerban et al., 2018 etc.).

The lowest annual maximum temperatures had values of 31-33°C and occurred mainly in the range 1966-1980. The years with the lowest values were 1975 (31.2°C), 1980 (32.6°C), 1978 (32.7°C), 1969, 1966 etc.

Fig. 2. The decennial maximum air temperature and the average of the annual maximum temperatures on each decade, at the Arad weather station (1961-2018)

Figure 2 shows the decennial maximum temperature over the six decades of the period 1961-2018. It resulted from the highest annual maximum temperature in each decade. The last decade (2011-2018) is not complete. It is noted that the 1st decade (1961-1970) was warmer than the 2nd decade (1971-1980) and had the same value as the 3rd decade (1981-1990), respectively 38.3°C. A continuous increase of the decennial maximum temperature is observed starting with the 2nd decade. The highest

decennial maximum temperature had the last decade (2011-2018), of 40.8°C, and the lowest the 2nd decade (1971-1980), of 36.8°C. Thus, the decennial maximum temperature increased from the 2nd decade (D2) to the 6th decade (D6) by 4°C. The increase of the maximum temperature from one decade to another was of 1.5°C from D2 to D3, 0.8°C from D3 to D4, 1.1°C from D4 to D5 and 0.6°C from D5 to D6. So, the smallest growth has been noted between the last two decades.

Figure 2 also shows the average of the annual maximum temperatures calculated on each decade. The same distribution of the values is observed as in the case of the decennial maximum temperature, with the difference that the 1st decade has a lower value than the 3rd decade.

During the year, the air temperature gradually increases, once with the increase of the solar radiation values, from January to the summer months, when it registers a maximum, after which it decreases until December (Fig. 3). If in the case of the multi-annual monthly average temperature, the maximum occurs in July, in the case of the multi-annual monthly maximum temperature, it occurred in August. The cause is the persistence of the hot air over Romania, under anticyclonic weather conditions, as mentioned above. The thermal minimum occurred in January, both in the case of the monthly average temperature and the monthly maximum temperature. It is due to the frequent advections of arctic or continental-polar cold air, brought through the winter anticyclones.

Fig. 3. The multi-annual monthly average temperature and the multi-annual monthly maximum temperature of the air, at the Arad weather station (1961-2018)

From figure 3 we notice that the differences between the monthly maximum temperature and the monthly average temperature are about 20°C. The multi-annual monthly maximum temperature rose from 16.6°C in

January (January 1979) to 40.8°C in August (August 2017) and then dropped to 17.5°C in December (December 2008). The attainment of such high values of temperature in the winter months is generally due to the advections of maritime-tropical or maritime-polar air, brought through European cyclones (Măhăra, 1977).

Except for 3 months (January, March and May), in all other months of the year, the maximum thermal value occurred in the range 2000-2018. In 8 of the 12 months of the year, the maximum thermal value was registered in the range 2007-2018.

As a result of recording the monthly maximum thermal values towards the end of the analyzed period, but also of generally recording of some high thermal values in the last years of the analyzed period, the linear trends of the monthly maximum air temperature, for all 12 months of the year, are *upward* (Fig. 4-7). The months of July ($R^2=0.2036$), August ($R^2=0.1664$), June ($R^2=0.1107$), May, January, February and December have the most pronounced upward trends. The months of March, October, November, April and September have the lowest values of the trend. Therefore, *the most pronounced increase in the monthly maximum temperatures occurred, in the last years, in the summer months, in May and in the winter months. Lower increases were reported in March-April and in the autumn months.*

The variability of the maximum air temperature in Arad was also highlighted based on two characteristic extreme temperatures: *summer days* (the days when the maximum temperature was $\geq 25^\circ\text{C}$) and *tropical days* (the days when the maximum temperature was $\geq 30^\circ\text{C}$).

Fig. 4. The monthly maximum air temperature for the winter months and its linear trend, at Arad (1961-2018)

Fig. 5. The monthly maximum air temperature for the spring months and its linear trend, at Arad (1961-2018)

Fig. 6. The monthly maximum air temperature for the summer months and its linear trend, at Arad (1961-2018)

Fig. 7. The monthly maximum air temperature for the autumn months and its linear trend, at Arad (1961-2018)

The number of summer days. At the Arad weather station, 97 *summer days* are recorded on average, in a year. In the period 1961-2018, the annual number of summer days varied between 57 (in 1978) and 143 (in 2018). From figure 8 we notice that the annual number of summer days has increased greatly since 1992. If in the period 1961-1991 there were 7 years with more than 100 days of summer, in the period 1992-2018 there were 17 years with more than 100 days. In the period 1961-1991, the annual number of summer days ranged from 57 to 112 days, having an average of 88 days, and in the period 1992-2018 ranged from 74 to 143 days, having an average of 107 days. If the 3 summer months (the June-August interval) total 92 days, the average of 107 days shows that, during the period 1992-2018, the summer season extended by 15 days (half a month).

Fig. 8. The annual number of summer and tropical days and its linear trend, at Arad (1961-2018)

Starting with the year 2000, the annual number of summer days has exceeded 120 days. There are 6 years with over 120 days. In order of their value, they are: 2018 (143 days), 2009 (132 days), 2000 (129 days), 2012 (128 days), 2003 (127 days) and 2011 (121 days).

In the last 10 years (2009-2018), the average of the annual number of summer days was 113 days. That means the summer season extended by 21 days in Arad.

In this context, the linear trend of the annual number of summer days is *upward*, for the period 1961-2018.

The number of tropical days. At the Arad station, 33 *tropical days* are recorded on average, in a year. In the period 1961-2018, the annual number of tropical days varied between 3 (in 1978) and 71 (in 2003). We also notice

that the annual number of tropical days has increased greatly starting with the year 1992 (Fig. 8). Thus, in the period 1961-1991, the annual number of tropical days ranged from 3 to 44 days, having an average of 25 days, and in the period 1992-2018 ranged from 12 to 71 days, having an average of 43 days. In the period 1992-2018 there were 9 years with more than 50 tropical days and 4 years with more than 60 days. The 4 years are: 2003 (71 days), 2012 and 2015 (67 days), 1994 (62 days).

In the last 10 years (2009-2018), the average of the annual number of tropical days was 49 days.

The linear trend of the annual number of tropical days is *upward* for the period 1961-2018, the increase of the number of tropical days being more pronounced ($R^2=0.3064$) than that of the summer days ($R^2=0.2271$).

The increase in air temperature over 25°C is usually possible in the March-November interval, at Arad (Fig. 9). The highest frequency of summer days is in the June-August interval (18-25 days, on average), and between the months of the year, July has the highest average number (25 days). The monthly maximum number rises to 31 days in July-August. The summer days appear quite exceptional in November and March, in special synoptic situations.

Fig. 9. The maximum, average and minimum monthly number of summer days, at Arad (1961-2018)

Fig. 10. The maximum, average and minimum monthly number of tropical days, at Arad (1961-2018)

The increase in air temperature over 30°C is usually possible in the April-October interval (Fig. 10). Tropical days have the highest frequency in the July-August interval (11-12 days, on average), with July dominating. Most tropical days occurred in August 1992 (29 days) and August 2018 (27 days). The tropical days were recorded quite exceptional in April and

October, only between 2006 and 2013 (only 1 day, in April 2012, April 2013, October 2006 and October 2012).

CONCLUSIONS

At the Arad station, the absolute maximum air temperature was 40.8°C and was recorded on 5th August, 2017. During the period 1961-2018, the linear trend of the annual maximum temperature was upward. We notice the increase of the values of annual maximum temperature starting with the year 1988, the increase being even more pronounced since 2000.

A continuous increase of the decennial maximum temperature is observed starting with the 2nd decade. The highest decennial maximum temperature had the 6th decade (2011-2018), of 40.8°C, and the lowest the 2nd decade (1971-1980), of 36.8°C. Thus, the decennial maximum temperature increased from the 2nd decade to the 6th decade by 4°C.

Except for 3 months (January, March and May), in all other months of the year, the maximum thermal value occurred in the range 2000-2018. In 8 of the 12 months of the year, the maximum thermal value was registered in the range 2007-2018. The linear trends of the monthly maximum air temperature, for all 12 months of the year, are upward. The most pronounced increase in the monthly maximum temperatures occurred, in the last years, in the summer months, in May and in the winter months.

At the Arad station, 97 summer days and 33 tropical days are recorded on average, in a year. The annual number of summer and tropical days has increased greatly since 1992. During the period 1992-2018, the summer season extended by 15 days, on average. In the last 10 years, the summer season extended by 21 days, on average. The linear trends of the annual number of summer and tropical days are upward, the increase of the number of tropical days being more pronounced than that of the summer days.

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WHEAT YIELD PREDICTION BASED ON MODIS NDVI TIME SERIES DATA IN THE WIDER REGION OF A CEREAL PROCESSING PLANT

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Abstract

The environmental impacts of climate change have been identified as a central issue in of the agriculture because the emergence of drought risk is a growing barrier to crop production and resulting in a decline in the quality and yield of cereals in recent years. In recent years there was a great development made in cereal processing in Hungary. In general, food processing plants requires steady crop supply, therefore it is essential to monitor the possible yield or yield loss of the potential supply area of the new cereal processing plant in Gyöngyösvisonta.

The aerial and satellite images can be used to monitor the response time of areas to biotic and abiotic stress effects, in this study the application of water stress and drought monitoring. We analyzed on the basis of the remote-sensed time series data. In the context of recordings, a number of stress indexes can be calculated to determine the productivity of biomass during a drought period. The study site covers four counties around Gyöngyösvisonta. The source of remote sensed time series data was the 16-day images of MODIS NDVI. The 250 m ground resolution images were downloaded and processed in ArcGIS software using various GIS methods from 2003 to 2018 that area. The sample area was selected that used for the production of wheat from the CORINE database, NDVI, and crop phenology. We applied time series NDVI images using different masking techniques and created the models for wheat yield prediction. During modeling calibration of NDVI data sets was performed by correlation and regression calculations with yield and NDVI data sets. Based on the results moderate correlations ($r \sim 0.8$), areas with different drought risk levels can be delineated to estimate yield loss with MODIS data in May and June which is the most suitable period for yield loss monitoring before harvest. Calculating these data will allow farmers to determine the appropriate intervention time to avoid territorial degradation.

Key words: MODIS, NDVI, wheat, yield loss

INTRODUCTION

According to the Hungarian climate models, the temperature of the area shows a steady rise (Bartholy et al., 2011), which resulted in the gradual shift of agro-ecological zones (Harnos, Csete, 2008). Precipitation at the national level has decreased by an average of 50 mm per year over the last hundred years, and periods without precipitation have become longer, resulting in more frequent drought (Szász, 1988; Szász, 2005). The environmental impacts of climate change have begun to form a central issue in both humanity and agriculture, since the appearance of too much or too little rainfall can be a major factor in crop yields. Drought is one of the most complex natural hazards in crop production due to its slow onset and impact on yield (Sabău, Brejea, 2016), decreasing cereal quality and yield, and high

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variability over time. Due to drought, agricultural monitoring systems need to start on time. An important tool for climate adaptation is the development of monitoring sensory technologies through the development of precision agricultural technology (Tamás, 2001). Spectral material analysis has also been discovered as a tool for assessing agricultural drought, agricultural water transportation factors and the resulting yield and quality of crops, complementing the traditional research methodology (Atzberger, 2013; Tamás et al., 2015; Nagy et al., 2018). Aerial satellite or terrestrial multi- or hyperspectral recorders have made it possible to record plant quality parameters under field conditions (Neményi, Milics, 2007; Jung et al., 2017). Reflection properties can be observed in the spectrum, which can be supported by the integration of NDVI in wheat plants during the growing season. The MODIS Normalized Vegetation Index (NDVI) satellite image analysis (Gulácsi, Kovács, 2015) is a suitable tool for time series monitoring of the response of plants biotic and abiotic stress effects. From the processed information we can observe the changes of the plant density, the development of the plant diseases and the changes of the yield. With a wide viewing angle of 2.330 kilometers, MODIS captures images in 36 spectral bands around the world in 1-2 days. The sensor also measures the part of the planet's surface covered by clouds almost every day (II). In practice, MODIS data from Reeves et al., 2005 was used to estimate wheat yields in North Dakota and Montana. The source of the remote sensing data was 16-day MODIS NDVI images. The images show the results of 16 days of chlorophyll intensity and biomass on cloudless, clear images. In addition, MODIS NDVI images have a spatial resolution of 250 m, which is 6.25 ha / pixel, sufficient to monitor field and regional yields in the Central and Eastern Europe region. Spectral data collection provides a rapid surplus of information from the study area, providing the basis for reliable monitoring. During spectral data collection, data on soil-plant-water relationships in the studied area can be recorded up to a resolution of 1 m (Neményi et al., 2010). Plant-specific analysis results may be appropriate to predict NDVI / yield reduction (Rembold et al., 2013). The generated model can provide a good basis for predicting the yield of arable land besides monitoring drought (Nagy et al., 2018). The main is to use spectral technologies to monitor crop yield and yield loss, thereby improving and temporarily intervening in extreme weather conditions, especially drought-prone areas.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The Gyöngyösvisonta plant processes 250.000 tons of Hungarian GMO-free wheat per year using world-class, environmentally friendly, waste-free technology. With this quantity, in a good crop year, the factory can process one-tenth of the wheat to be exported. Hungary is the state-of-

the-art wheat starch factory in Central Europe. The wheat growing areas, closest to the farm cannot provide this quantity. Because of this, besides Heves County, the investigated counties include, the Tisza catchment area of Csongrád County, Borsod-Abaúj Zemplén County, Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok County, Békés County, Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County and Hajdú-Bihar County areas and areas with potential wheat production (Fig. 1) (Farágó, Koncz, 2012).

Fig. 1. Arable area of the examined counties

The most frequently influenced weather events are spring frost, drought, heat stress and stormy weather such as strong winds, hail and heavy rainfall (Antal, 2005). From these, the drought period is highlighted, because prolonged drought changes physiological processes, thereby limiting plant growth (Abid et al., 2018). For winter wheat to grow, the average daily temperature during the growing season must reach 2100 °C (Kismányoky, 2013). According to the National Meteorological Service, the minimum and maximum rainfall between the center of the Great Plain of Debrecen, between 1901 and 2010 was 321 mm and 953 mm. Increasing number of heat days during the ripening of cereals and the lack of precipitation can lead to a significant loss of yield hence to a deterioration in quality. However, too much precipitation can lead to prolonged ripening and lower quality. Due to the increase in crop volatility, the development of storage capacity may be justified in the future. MODIS NDVI images were downloaded from <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/> for the selected area and year. The downloaded years were 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018, for which we added data series already processed from 2000 to 2014. TerrSet and ArcGIS geospatial software were used to process the downloaded images. The

MODIS NDVI time series data available were downloaded for the sample site and was prepared for further processing and converted to GeoTiff in a TerrSet software environment. Remote sensing data from the internationally available CORINE 2012 land use database and topographic maps were processed and integrated with digital elevation model data. There are five main steps to calibrate NDVI in the ArcGIS software environment (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. NDVI calibration steps

MODIS NDVI data for April and July of each year were used to represent the wheat fields in the Tisza catchment areas. Based on the classification of the images, we made Boolean masks based on two images / year. After the images are sorted into a logical mask, they indicate the density of vegetation and the barren locations during the vegetation period. This eliminated the areas covered by alfalfa, maize and industrial crops in the case of wheat. The United States Geological Survey (USGS) used the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) models to select lowland areas and then used the CORINE Landcover dataset to select arable land. After sorting the arable land, the layers were merged and delimited by counties. The county - arable mask shows the arable areas of a county. We integrated the county arable mask and wheat-covered classified areas. Each year we received potential wheat growing areas for the county. After extraction, a data matrix of the average NDVI values was created, and the obtained values provides the basis for the calibration of the NDVI images (Tamás et al., 2015). The calibration was performed by linear regression of the average wheat yield (t / ha) available from the Central Statistical Office (CSO) until 2000-2016, and the results were validated with the data of 2017-2018. According to the literature, remote sensing time series of at least 6 years should be used for crop analysis (Dempewolf et al., 2014; Nagy et al., 2018). Using the regression equations, we estimated the estimate yields by county. The accuracy of the prediction was evaluated by the coefficient of accuracy index (R^2) (1) and for the validation of the model we calculated the

root mean square error (RMSE) (2) values for the analysis of the prediction and the regression. NRMSD facilitates the comparison between datasets or models (3).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y'_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad 1)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y'_i)^2}{n}} \quad 2)$$

$$NRMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - y'_i)^2}{n}} / (\max(y_i) - \min(y_i)) \quad 3)$$

where: y_i : measured data for the sample
 y'_i : estimated yields of the sample
 \bar{y} : average yield
 n : number of samples used for validation
 $\max(y_i)$: maximum measured data for the sample
 $\min(y_i)$: minimum measured data for the sample

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Processing of MODIS NDVI data series for Heves County in June

The predictions of the yields were made by linear regression of the estimated yield values of the examined years, which were compared with the yield data available according to the Central Statistics Office. The R^2 values were calculated on the basis of preliminary studies with NDVI and CSO yields for June 10 and June 26, which was $R^2 = 0.386$ on June 10 and $R^2 = 0.508$ on June 26 (Fig. 3). These values give a medium value for further evaluation. The regression equations were computed with the NDVI values to obtain the projected yield values for the year.

The direct potential supplier of the grain processing plant is Heves County, therefore the results for the county were evaluated separately. The June 10 and June 26 values obtained by calculating the regression equations were averaged and compared to the yields reported by the CSO (Fig. 4). Our prediction gave almost the same results, with the biggest differences observed in 2002 and 2010. 2010 was considered to be a very rainy year, which may have reduced yields.

Fig. 3. Relationship between NDVI values and yield

The RMSE error of the Heves County forecast was 0.43 on June 10 and June 26, as well. The projected value deviation from fair values was 8.45 % on June 10, with the largest deviation in 2007 and the lowest in 2015. In 2007, Hungary was characterized by a prolonged, highly drought-like climate, which explains and supports the high yield loss. As of June 26, the forecasted value deviation from fair value was 1.95 %, with the largest deviation in 2012 and the lowest in 2014. Taking into account the 3-year time horizon for Heves County, the deviation from the projected value to the fair value was 14.4%, and the deviation from the projected value to the fair value at the 6-year average was 10.75 % based on June 10 values. As of June 26, the 3-year forecasted value deviation from fair value was 10.97 %

and the 6-year forecasted value deviation from fair value was 8.42 % (Fig. 5). With the exception of the 14.4 % obtained on the basis of the 3-year average deviations at 10 June, the other values are close to or less than the accepted maximum of 10 %.

Fig. 4. Expected yield data for Heves County

Fig. 5. Mean deviation values for 3 and 6 years for Heves County

Processing of MODIS NDVI data series for June for the 7 counties in the Tisza catchment area

Using the average deviations from the projected value from the fair value, we examined the relationships between the estimated yield and the harvested yield values over a 3- and 6-year period for all years and counties examined. The 1-year average deviation from the projected value as at June

10 is 10.9 %, the 3-year average deviation from the forecast value is 11.67 %, and the 6-year forecast deviation from fair value is 11.97 %. As of June 26, the average deviation from fair value over the 1-year projected value is 9.9 %, the average deviation from the fair value over the 3-year projected value is 10.34 %, and the average deviation from the 6-year forecast value is 10.08 % (Fig. 6). Our values are slightly above the acceptable tolerance of 10 %, so these data can be used for future wheat crop prediction. With the forecasting method used, yields can be estimated 4 weeks before harvest. Accurate application of the model requires accurate application of the appropriate software and accurate data recording.

Fig. 6. Values of absolute mean deviations

Between 2000 and 2018, the RMSE error for the forecast for the seven counties examined was 0.38 on June 10 and 0.34 on June 26. RMSE / year values were further calculated from the forecast RMSE error values for the 7 surveyed counties of all years, from which RMSE /% yields were calculated using real yield data (Table 1).

Table 1

RMSE / % yield minimum, maximum and average values		
	June 10.	June 26.
Minimum RMSE / Yield %	7.96	4.41
Maximum RMSE / Yield %	25.55	27.58
Average RMSE / Yield %	14.65	13.78

CONCLUSIONS

Our investigations show that MODIS NDVI time series data images can be used to develop and calculate crop prediction. Crop prediction helps field workers and farmers to be prepared in time for the expected yield changes and their possible quantitative changes. Providing and developing a monitoring base can be an important step in improving the yield patterns of the Tisza River Basin, including both wheat and maize. The developed monitoring system for wheat can be based on the processing of the June values, within which we can apply the values of absolute average deviations in 6-year intervals, which can give approximate results up to 4 weeks before the wheat harvest. With this method we can support the yield of the potential supply areas of the grain processing plant built in Gyöngyösvisonta and their development, helping to get more and better-quality grain into the food chain in the future. Compared to climate data, it can help you to recognize early the effects of water stress caused by plant water scarcity or prolonged rainfall.

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CHANGES IN THE COMMON BEECH STAND MICRO-RELIEF DUE TO WINDFALLS IN THE MANAGEMENT UNIT VII VĂRATEC. SUDRIGIU FOREST DISTRICT, BIHOR COUNTY, ROMANIA

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Abstract

The volume of incidental wood products due to the catastrophic windfalls that occurred on the 17th of September 2017 was estimated, at national level at 460 thousand m³, of which over 200 thousand m³ were registered in the area administered by the Bihor County Forest Administration.

The main objective of this paper is the study of the changes that appear in the micro-relief and of the influence of some environmental characteristics, in the beech stands (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) from the Forest District Sudrigiu, Management Unit U.P. VII Văratec, Bihor County Forest Administration, Romania, as an effect of windfalls.

The field observations had the purpose of: determining the displaced volume (DV); breast height diameter ($D_{1.3}$); height of tree (HT); average root diameter (ARD); age (A); depth of micro-depression (DM) and depth of rock / parent material (DRP). Bifactorial linear regression of the DV according to the two characteristics of the tree ($D_{1.3}$) and the soil (DRP) allows an assessment of the volume of displaced soil with an accuracy of 95%.

The volume of soil dislocated in the beech stands (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) from the Forest District Sudrigiu, Management Unit U.P. VII Văratec, Bihor County Forest Administration, Romania, evaluated with the help of the two-factor linear regression based on the basic diameter of tree $D_{1.3}$ and the depth of the rock / parent material DRP and respectively the number of felled trees is between 2589.89 m³ for u.a. 100 A, partially affected and 13694.46 m³ for u.a. 104 A, affected by mass felling.

To acknowledge the total volume of dislocated land and of the specific volume (m³ / ha), for the different compartments, is important for the analysis and differentiation of the variants of works necessary for the forest reconstruction of the lands affected by windfalls.

Key words: windfalls, micro-relief, volume of dislocated soil, breast height diameter, depth of rock or parent material, forest reconstruction

INTRODUCTION

Forest ecosystems represent a considerable stock of resources that have significant economic effects on the development of modern society, mainly by supplying several types of raw materials, known as forest products.

Managing them on a sustainable basis requires a thorough and realistic knowledge of their structure and functioning in direct correlation with environmental factors. In this regard, it is of particular interest to be aware of the connections between forest ecosystems and disruptive environmental factors: wind, snow, fire, insects, fungi, etc. (Popa, 2005).

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Of all the disruptive environmental factors of forest ecosystems, wind is considered the most important abiotic factor, causing significant damage to forests, resulting in the uprooting or breaking down of trees, leading to considerable financial losses for forest owners (Ní Dhubhain, Farrelly, 2018).

The winds represent the main disruptive, natural factor of the mountain forest ecosystems, inherent and inevitable, concomitant or not, which have negative effects both ecologically, through the structural changes that it induces, as well as economically, through the losses of value of the wood volume and of the disturbances determined in the coherent application of the management plans (Măciuca et al., 2006).

Crainic, 2017 states that in the general classification of forest products: main products (forest regeneration logs); secondary products (cutting of young trees); hygiene products (other wood products: shrubs, ornamental shrubs, seedlings and various wood products) the wood resulting from natural disasters such as windfalls, is classified in the category of incidental wood products.

Specialty literature delimits, according to the intensity and the magnitude of the phenomenon, two major categories of windfalls: catastrophic windfalls - mass windfalls, due to particular weather conditions, very high intensity winds, which affect a wide area and isolated windfalls - which occur annually, as a result of medium intensity winds, with low economic effects, but which through accumulation become very important (Mitchell, 2013).

The windfalls, through the negative economic and ecological effects, impose the necessity of developing silvo-technical systems of sustainable forest management. The forestry interventions must be oriented towards strengthening the stability of the trees, in order to ensure and maintain the climax of the forest ecosystems (Popa, 2005).

Dorog and Crainic, 2003, shows that the stability of the trees can be expressed by a function in relation to several constant characteristics or which can be significantly modified. It is emphasized the fact that the stability of the stand is influenced by the component elements of the site, vegetation and last but not least, by the anthropic factor and other possible biological factors that may have a destabilizing character in some situations. Indices of structural characteristics of the stands are presented: composition, consistency, thickness indices and density indices and respectively synthesis indices of structural traits of the stands, such as the slimness coefficient and the Hart - Beking spacing index, which quantifies the stability of the stands and / or the opportunity to apply forestry interventions.

Factors that influence the evolution of windfalls can be divided into: triggering environmental factors, represented by climatic conditions (variety

of hydrometeors, temperature variations) and respectively environmental factors favoring windfalls (lithological substrate, soil, relief, slope, exposure) (Crainic, 2003).

The methods used to evaluate the risk of producing windfalls are classified in three broad categories:

- observational - consisting of analyzing specific risk indicators (Dorog, Crainic, 2003);

- mechanical experiments - consist of testing the resistance of the stands to the action of the wind either by mechanical modeling techniques of the behavior of the stands or by specific experiments (Peltola et al., 2000);

- mathematics, based on the principles of static and material resistance (Fetea et al., 2003);

- statistics - regression analysis in estimating the probability associated with windfalls depending on the environmental and stand factors (Popa, 2005).

In most cases, regardless of the assessment methods used, the importance of the species of trees, the type of soil and the subsoil, and of the wind loads acting on the trees and which can cause their overturning, is emphasized. Besides the soil and the subsoil, an important role is played by the relief, slope and altitude which act synergistically with the climatic elements when initializing and carrying out the windfalls (Coates et al., 2018).

Geambașu, 1984 mentions that a product of windfalls in the mountain area is the specific micro-relief known as the micro-relief of windfalls. In severe storms, the root system yields and is displaced from the ground along with a soil disk held between the roots. When the overturning of the trees takes place from upstream to downstream, in the area of detachment of the disks remains a characteristic micro-depression which eventually fades but does not disappear permanently (Fig. 1).

Taking into account that the windfall effects on the ground and relief are long lasting, the micro-relief of windfalls is transformed into an environmental element with a special indicator value on the forest's past. The existence of the micro-relief of the windfalls has a special importance for the environmental study, transforming it into a real instrument for assessing the risk of the resort when producing the windfalls (Crainic et al., 2003).

In Europe, wind is considered a major factor in disrupting forest ecosystems, where it is responsible for causing more than half the volume of all damage to forests (Gardiner, 2013). The growth in the frequency and severity of windstorms have been attributed to climate change, the number and intensity of these extreme phenomena increasing (Sabău, Iovan, 2018;

Constandache et al., 2018). This tendency of increasing frequency and intensity has been felt in Europe since the 1950s, also evidenced by the damage created to the forest stock. Between 1970 and 2010, the damage caused by the storm in the forests of the European continent doubled, rising from about 50 million m³ to about 100 million m³ (Chirici et al., 2017).

Fig. 1. The appearance of a stump located in the upstream-downstream direction, lateral view (Crainic, 2003, processing after Geambașu, 1984)

The negative effects of windfalls are also felt in Romania, especially in the mountain area. For example, the catastrophic windfalls of November 1995 affected an area of over 140 thousand ha, resulting in a total volume of about 7.9 million m³ incidental wood products. The disasters that occurred in Suceava county in March 2002 resulted in windfall products estimated at over 7 million m³ (Popa, 2005).

According to Agerpres, quoted by Capital, the storm that took place on September 17, 2017 which affected the west of the country, with a speed of over 100 km / h in the Apuseni Mountains, caused the damage of over 700 ha of forest. The volume of incidental wood products due to catastrophic windfalls being estimated at 460 thousand m³, out of which 246 thousand m³ was the result of mass windfalls. The biggest damages were registered by the Bihor County Forest Administration, the accidental wood products being valued at over 200 thousand m³ (Bălăceanu, 2017).

Only at the Sudrigiu Forest District, Bihor County Forest Administration, which manages a total area of 2177.7 ha of forest fund, out of which 1698.7 ha of public property of the state, the volume of losses assessed is over 60 thousand m³ of which 50525 m³ in the public state property stands. The Management Unit U.P. VII Văratec is detached by the volume of the damaged wood, where on the affected area of 611.7 ha (36 % of the total area) was evaluated a volume of accidental wood products of

36649 m³. The most affected are the beech stands (*Fagus sylvatica L*) the affected surface representing over 95% of the total, and the percentage of accidental wood products from the specified volume in the arrangement of almost 25 % (Crainic, 2017).

The main objective of this paper is the study of the changes of the micro-relief and the influence of some environmental characteristics, in the beech stands (*Fagus sylvatica L*) at the Forest District Sudrigiu, Management Unit U.P. VII Văratec, Bihor County Forest Administration, Romania as an effect of the windfalls from September 17, 2017.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The Management Unit U.P. VII Văratec, administered by the Forest District Sudrigiu, Bihor County Forest Administration, is located on the northeastern slopes of the Codru Moma Mountains, in the hydrographic basin of the Crișul Văratecului stream, with an area of over 58 km², of which approximately 66 % has a forest destination (Sabău, Iovan, 2018).

The following research methods were used to carry out this case study: bibliographic documentation, field observations on the surfaces affected by windfalls and tree breakage, environmental investigations, comparisons, point determinations, statistical analyzes, comparisons, correlations and regressions between the measured elements.

The field observations, made in 2019, on the itinerary and on the stationary, have as purpose the quantitative, qualitative and value evaluation of the catastrophic effects of the storm that took place on September 17, 2017 and implicitly the environmental conditions of the stands in which the windfalls and tree breakage occurred, using for this purpose the management of the U.P.VII Văratec Management Unit and the related planning maps (RNP-ICAS, 2014).

In order to choose the planning units in which to make characteristic determinations, it was considered that the most affected stands are those of European beech and the fact that over 75 % of the surface of U.P.VII Văratec is occupied by Cambisols, the rest of 25 % it is up to Chernozems and Luvisols (Dincă et al., 2017; Sabău, 2017).

The compartments (u.a.) were chosen to make determinations on the micro-relief resulting from the windfalls: plots u.a. 100 A; u.a. 103 A and u.a. 104 A (Fig. 2).

In plots occupied by European beech stands, observations were made on the itinerary, using the transects method, estimating the percentage of the affected surface, the slope exposure, the slope of the land and in the stationary, for determining the characteristic elements of the micro-relief obtained as a result of windfalls. The average density of the observation points was higher for the surfaces affected by mass windfalls.

They were measured with the roulette: the length L, the width and the height of the resulting soil disk, the breast height diameter of the overturned stand and in the resulting micro-depression, the type of soil, the nature of the rock or the parent material on which the soil was formed, their depth H (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Location of field observations (processed according to the U.P. VII Văratec Management Map, Sudrișiu Forest District)

Fig. 3. The geometrical elements of the windfall micro-relief: A - cross-section, B - longitudinal section, e - excavation, d - wind direction, h - the height of the earth disk, l - the width of the disk, L - the length of the disk (Crainic, 2003, relocation after Geambașu, 1984)

At each observation point, the breast height $D_{1.3}$ was measured with the clipper.

To estimate the height of the h stands, the slenderness coefficient $Z = h / D_{1.3}$, graphically represented for, based on the breast height diameter $D_{1.3}$, was used by Florescu, Nicolescu, 1996, respectively Florescu et al., 2002 (Fig. 4). the resulting value was then corrected taking into account the average height of the average diameter stand in the considered plot, resulting from the Valuation Act (APV). of the damaged wood mass (ROMSILVA, 2019).

Fig. 4. Evolution of the slenderness coefficient Z according to the basic diameter d , for beech - FA and fir - BR (source: Florescu, Nicolescu, 1996)

Using the geometric elements that were measured at each point, the root volume was determined and DV (m^3) displaced land approximating the

micro-depression with a cylinder having the average root diameter, at the top of which is added a cone, corresponding to the lower part.

The values of the elements measured and calculated at each observation point in the three plots were statistically processed, calculating the minimum, maximum, average, standard error of the mean and standard deviation. The correlation coefficients between the variables, the main components and the possible regressions were analyzed to evaluate the volume of land displaced according to the measured characteristics. The specialized program for statistical analysis GNU - PSPP, 2016 was used.

To test the different types of regressions between the volume deployed DV according to the analyzed environmental factors, the Microsoft Office 2016 EXCEL module was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The violent storm, similar to a tornado, from September 17, 2017 affected the western part of the country and especially the Apuseni Mountains area, with high intensities in the intramontane depressions. In Beiuş Depression the front of clouds from west to south, west formed in less than 30 minutes. The storm characterized by heavy rainfall, strong wind, gusts, with speeds of about 100 km / h and electric discharges started at 4.30 pm and lasted about 15 minutes.

The large surfaces affected by windfalls and tree breakage were accompanied by damaged surfaces, registered in the neighboring counties that rounded off parts of the Apuseni Mountains Arad, Cluj and Alba.

In the Management Unit U.P. VII Văratec, Sudrigiu Forest District, the beech (*Fagus sylvatica L.*), sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) and Norway spruce (*Picea abies L.*) stands were affected, predominantly on the slopes with western, south-western orientation, especially at the slopes but also in the middle and upper part, in the case of mass windfalls.

The soil cover is represented by those of the Cambisols (75 %), Luvisols (16 %) and Chernozems (9 %) classes (according to WRB classification). Among the most common cambisols are Eutric Cambisol (63 %) of which the typical Eutric Cambisol occupies more than 50 % of the total area (Table 1).

The species of beech trees are considered very resistant to the shade, they have a smooth bark, pivoting-tractive rooting, having a special forest importance. The common beech species (*Fagus sylvatica L.*) is a tree with large heights and diameters. The tap-root in the first decade of life later spreads in several oblique and horizontal branches, with great extension and intersection with those of the neighboring trees, ensuring a satisfactory resistance to windfalls (Stănescu et al., 1997).

Table 1

Distribution of soil types and subtypes in the U.P. VII Văratec, Forest District Sudrigiu
(source: RNP-ICAS, 2014)

No. crt.	Class	Type	Subtype	Horizons	Surface	
					ha	%
1.	Chernozems	Phaeozem	marly	Am-ACma-Cma	52.27	3
		Rendzic Leptosol	cambic	Am-Bv-Rrz	134.30	6
	Total				191.57	9
2.	Luvisols	Luvisol	typic	Ao-El-Bt-C	254.33	12
			lithic	Ao-El-Bt-R	19.18	1
		Alisol	prelucic	Ao-Bt-C(R)	37.39	3
	Total				340.90	16
3	Cambisols	Eutric Cambisol	typic	Ao-Bv-C	1110.22	54
			mollic	Am-Bv-C	122.94	6
			lithic	Ao-Bv-R	24.43	1
			rendzinic	Ao-Bv-Rrz	38.56	2
		Dystric Cambisol	typical	Ao-Bv-R(C)	259.19	12
	Total				1555.34	75
Total					2087.81	100

When observing the land there were no micro-bumps of the relief indicating the manifestation of previous windfalls.

The points chosen for the observations, the compartments: u.a. 100 A, u.a. 103 A and u.a. 104 A have areas between 22.46 ha and 35.58 ha, soil type Eutric cambisol, type of hilly site of beech stands Pm or Ps, medium or large edaphic brown, with *Asperula-Asarum*, the type of hill forest with mull flora (s) or hillock on skeletal soils with mull flora (m) (Table 2).

The plots have average altitudes between 525 m and 740 m, with the stands composition pure or nearly pure (9 Beech + 1 hornbeam in 100 A), with an index of consistency of 0.7 and average ages between 73 and 103 years.

The windfalls that occurred on the 17th of September 2017 partially affected the u.a. plots. 100 A (70 % of the surface) and u.a. 103 A (80 %), on portions located from the base of the slope, while in the plot u.a. 104 A they were mass windfalls, which affected over 95 % of the area (Fig. 5).

The soil characteristics from the plots selected for observations highlight some differences given by the subtypes of eutric cambisol, typical in the plots u.a. 100 A and u.a. 104 A and respectively, mollic in u.a. 103 A (Table 3). Typical eutric cambisol although it has a more developed profile (130 cm) than the rendzinic subtype (67 cm) has a thinner bioaccumulation horizon of 18 cm (Fig. 6.b) than the second one, which has an average thickness of 30 cm (Fig. 6.a).

Table 2

Characteristic data of plots with field observations
(source: RNP-ICAS, 2014)

Plot	u.a. 100 A	u.a. 103 A	u.a. 104 A
Surface (ha)	22.46	26.14	35.58
Type of site	Hilly beech Pm, medium edaphic brown, with <i>Asperula-Asarum</i>	Hilly beech Pm, medium edaphic brown, with <i>Asperula-Asarum</i>	Hilly beech Pm, medium edaphic brown, with <i>Asperula-Asarum</i>
Type of forest	Hill beech on skeleton soils with mull flora (m)	Hill beech with mull flora (s)	Hill beech on skeleton soils with mull flora (m)
Type and subtype of soils	Typical Eutric Cambisol	Rendzinic Eutric Cambisol	Typical Eutric Cambisol
Average altitude (m)	525	655	740
Composition	9 Beech + 1 hornbeam	10 Beech	10 Beech
Average age (years)	103	73	73
Medium consistency	0.7	0.7	0.7

u.a. 103 A

u.a. 104 A

Fig. 5. General aspect of the windfalls in the u.a. 103 A and u.a. 104 A plots

Although in the case of the mollic subtype the humus content is lower (3.5-4.2 %) than in the typical case (6 %) it is of superior quality due to the less acid reaction and the higher degree of base saturation degree.

Although the soil profile in the u.a. 100 A plot is classified as typical Eutric cambisol, it has intermediate properties between the soils of the other two plots having a shorter profile (97 cm) with a skeletal character, being formed on limestone, dolomites and conglomerates (Fig. 7).

In order to assess the volume of material resulting from the windfalls, the following elements determined at the observation points were analyzed: the displaced volume - DV (m^3); base diameter of trunk - $D_{1.3}$ (m); Height of stand - HT (m); average root diameter - ARD (m); age - A (years); development of soil profile - DSP (m) and depth of parent material - DRM (m).

Table 3

Some properties of Eutric cambisols from the observed plots
(processed after RNP-ICAS, 2014)

Soil type and subtype	Typical Eutric cambisol	Rendzinic Eutric cambisol, semi-skeletal
Texture	Sandy loam / sandy	Sandy loam/ sandy
Skelet (%)	-	25 - 50
Rock and parent material	Stoneware, clay shale, clays	Limestone, dolomite, conglomerate
Profile development(cm)	130	67
Average thickness of horizon A (cm)	18	30
Humus on the horizon A (%)	6.6	3.5-4.2
pH	5.2-5.6	5.3-6.4
Base saturation degree (%)	61-70	68-69

Fig. 6. Appearance with the subtypes of Eutric cambisol from the plots with observations:
a) rendzinic - u.a. 103 A; b) typical - u.a. 104 A

The average value of the displaced volume is 3.64 m^3 with variations between 1.22 m^3 and 10.39 m^3 . Tree characteristics had average values of: $D_{1.3} = 0.44 \text{ m}$, $HT = 29.76 \text{ m}$, $ARD = 29.76 \text{ m}$, $A = 92.32 \text{ years}$. The depth of the micro-depression - DM and the Depth of the rock / parental material -

DRM were estimated at average values of 0.74 m and 0.42 m respectively (Table 4).

Fig. 7. The rock and the parent material in the u.a. 100 A plot - limestone, dolomite, limestone: a) the rootstock; b) the resulting micro-depression

Table 4

Descriptive characteristics of the analyzed variables

No. crt.	Variables	N	Min	Max	Mean	Standard deviation	Standard error of mean
1.	Displaced volume (m ³)	24	1.22	10.39	3.64	2.41	0.49
2.	Base diameter (m)	24	0.28	0.64	0.44	0.11	0.02
3.	Height of trees (m)	24	23.50	37.40	29.76	4.30	0.88
4.	Average root diameter (m)	24	1.94	3.81	2.79	0.52	0.11
5	Age (years)	24	73	108	92.38	16.83	3.44
6.	Depth of micro-depression (m)	24	0.34	1.30	0.74	0.24	0.05
7.	Depth of rock/parent material (m)	24	0.27	0.72	0.42	0.14	0.03

The DV analysis according to the observation plots shows that the highest mean values were obtained in plot u.a. 100A, $DV = 4.57 \text{ m}^3$, the maximum and minimum values being 10.39 m^3 and 1.53 m^3 respectively, but also with the highest standard error of 1.33 m^3 . In the u.a. 104A plot in which there was registered the second value of DV of 9.42 m^3 , with the average of 3.89 m^3 and the standard error of 0.67 m^3 . The lowest displaced volumes are found in the plot u.a. 103A plot, with a maximum of 3.37 m^3 , a minimum of 1.22 m^3 and an average of 2.23 m^3 characterized by the standard error of 0.32 m^3 (Fig. 8).

It is noted that the u.a. 100A and u.a. 104 A plots are occupied by typical Eutric cambisol and the plot u.a. 103 A is occupied by Rendzinic Eutric Cambisol. The fact that the largest displaced volumes of soil are recorded on the Typic Eutric Cambisol, of 4.12 m^3 , with the variance of 6.73 m^3 and the standard error of 0.61 m^3 . The average value of DV and the

standard error are almost double compared to that on the Rendzinic Eutric Cambisol of 2.23 m^3 and 0.32 m^3 respectively. In this case the variance is also much lower, of 0.63 m^3 .

Fig. 8. Variation of volumes distributed DV (m^3) on UA units
a) Boxplot of DV b) Boxplot of DV versus u.a.: 1- u.a.100A; 2-u.a.A 103A; 3-u.a. 104A

The explanation for these differences is the development of the profile of the two subtypes of soil, estimated through the depth of the micro-depression (DM) greater in the typical case, with values between 0.34 and 1.30 m, compared to the DM for the rendzinic one, with values between 0.28 and 0.36 m.

The analysis of the first 3 main components of the analyzed factors shows that DV, $D_{1.3}$ and DRP explain 99.94 % of the total variance. Of the 3 main components $D_{1.3}$ is the main feature of the stand and DRP is a ground related feature (Table 5).

Therefore, the size of the displaced volume DV can be estimated, in 99.94 % of the cases analyzed by the characteristics of the stand synthesized by the basic diameter $D_{1.3}$ and by the characteristics of the soil type represented by the depth of the rock / the parent material DRP.

The regressions established for DV (m^3) based on the breast height diameter of the $D_{1.3}$ tree (cm) and the depth of the rock / parent material DRP (m) are of exponential type, with a shape very close to the straight line,

statistically significant in the first case ($R^2 = 0.4203$) and respectively, distinctly significant statistically ($R^2 = 0.5160$) in the second case (Fig. 9).

Table 5

Principal Components Analysis

Variables	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction sums of squared loadings			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
DV (m^3)	273.57	92.70	92.70	273.57	92.70	92.70	271.78	92.09	92.09
$D_{1,3}$ (cm)	16.85	5.71	98.41	16.85	5.71	98.41	18.10	6.13	98.23
DRP (m)	4.50	1.53	99.94	4.50	1.53	99.94	5.04	1.71	99.94
HT (m)	0.14	0.05	99.99						
ARD (m)	0.04	0.01	100.00						
DM (m)	0.01	0.00	100.00						
A (years)	0.00	0.00	100.00						

Fig. 9. The regressions of the displaced volume - DV depending on: a) the breast height diameter of the $D_{1,3}$ stand and the depth of the rock / parent material – DRP

From the statistical significance of the regressions above it can be deduced that DRP has a stronger influence on DV size than the main characteristic of the stand $D_{1,3}$.

Bifactorial linear regression of DV according to the two characteristics of the stand ($D_{1,3}$) and the soil (DRP) has the form: $Y = -1.710792 + 11.635746 * X_1 + 0.703293 * X_2$. According to the correlation report $R = 0.586194$, determined after Baghinschi, 1979, it shows that the connection established between the variables is statistically significant. This fact is confirmed by the test F, the value calculated according to the degrees of freedom $F_c = 14.87$, much higher than the tabular limit value for the accuracy of 5 %, $F^* = 2.04$.

The connections established above, which allow the estimation of the volumes of earth dislocated values (DV) by the windfalls depending on the characteristics of the $D_{1,3}$ trees and the soil (DRP), are important for monitoring the intensity of the micro-relief modification.

Also, the modification of the micro-relief as a result of windfalls has a number of negative influences such as: fragmentation of the relatively continuous slope of the valley side; bringing to the surface the low fertility horizon from the base of the soil profile; updating the rock material / parent material in the created micro-depression; preventing water leakage on the slopes; accumulation of water in micro-depressions.

Although the level differences between the bases of the micro-depression and the upper part of the soil disk are fading over time, the risk of triggering water erosion remains, this being higher in the case of mass windfalls and during the period when the land is not covered with forest vegetation. Also the risk of triggering the landslides is high, especially in the case of soils with a Bt argic horizon.

The regressions established above allow the quantitative assessment, with an assurance of over 95 % of the volume displaced from the plots, the management units affected by windfalls, using the data recorded in the Acts of Valuation (ROMSILVA, 2019) of the wood material (Table 6).

Table 6

Calculation of the total volume of land deployed in the Compartments
(after ROMSILVA, 2019)

Compartment	u.a. 100 A	u.a. 103 A	u.a. 104 A
Supraface (ha)	22.5	39.18	35.58
Species	beech	beech	beech
No. of inventoried trees	817	1868	3783
The average base diameter of the inventoried trees (m)	0.44	0.40	0.43
Average volume per stand (m ³) DV=- 1.710792 + 11.635746 D _{1.3} + 0.703293 DRP	3.17	3.18	3.62
Total dislocated volume per plot (m ³)	2589.89	5940.24	13694.46
Dislocated volume per unit (m ³ /ha)	115.11	151.31	384.89

The average dislocated volumes by the average stand, estimated through the linear regression with 2 factors $X_1 = D_{1.3}$ and $X_2 = DRP$ are between 3.17 m³ in the plot of UA 100 A and 3.62 m³ in the plot of UA 104 A.

In order to prevent these deficiencies, knowing the volume of land dislocated for the different planning units and the volume of specific earthworks (m³ / ha) allows the analysis of the variants of works necessary for the ecological reconstruction of the lands disrupted by windfalls.

CONCLUSIONS

The magnitude of the changes in the micro-relief of the European beech stands (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) produced by the windfalls on the 17th of

September 2017, at the Sudrigiu Forest District, U.P.VII Văratec, quantified by the volume of land dislocated DV is dependent on favoring factors depending on the environmental conditions.

The size of the displaced volume DV is dependent on the characteristics of the tree: the breast high diameter of the tree $D_{1,3}$, the height of the tree HT, the average diameter of the ARD root, age A and the characteristics of the soil: the depth of the micro-depression - DM and the depth of the rock / parent material - DRM.

By analyzing the possible correlations, between the factors that influence the volume of displaced land DV and the analysis of the first 3 main components, it was demonstrated that DV can be evaluated using exponential regressions, depending on the breast high diameter of the $D_{1,3}$ tree ($R^2 = 0.4203$) and depending on the depth of the rock / parental material ($R^2 = 0.5160$), statistically significant, in the first case and distinctly statistically significant in the second case.

Bifactorial linear regression of DV according to the two characteristics of tree ($D_{1,3}$) and soil (DRP) of the form: $Y = - 1.710792 + 11.635746 * X_1 + 0.703293 * X_2$ is statistically significant ($R = 0.586194$), the F test (the calculated value $F_c = 14.87$, the table value ($F^* = 2.04$) shows that the evaluation accuracy is 95 %.

Using the dislocated volume (DV) of the average stand inventoried when highlighting the wood material, out of the 3 plots analyzed, evaluated with the help of the linear bifactorial regression and the number of felled trees results the total volume dislocated on the plots and by the surface unit. The resulting specific volume is between $115.11 \text{ m}^3 / \text{ha}$ and $384.89 \text{ m}^3 / \text{ha}$ and the total volume between 2589.89 m^3 and 13694.46 m^3 .

The knowledge of the volume of dislocated land for the different compartments and of the volume of specific earthworks (m^3 / ha) is important for the analysis and differentiation of the variants of works necessary for the forest reconstruction of the lands affected by windfalls.

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EVALUATION OF PARAMETERS IN AN AEROB INDUSTRIAL FERMENTATION SYSTEM

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Abstract

Meat chicken (broiler) industry continuously increasing all over the world. Due to it, the amount of waste from the chicken industry is also increasing. Therefore, more efficient conversion of chicken manure to organic fertilizer is key problem all over the world.

Therefore, the aims of present study are to investigate the changes in temperature and moisture content during composting of chicken manure in a tank fermentation system and create a model to describe the biodegradation processes. In this study, Hydrus software was used for modelling the moisture and temperature distribution in the oval tank during the decomposing processes.

It was found that the studied oval tank fermenter can be divided into two main parts considering to the changing of temperature and moisture level. In the first phase - after the intake – where the rate of biodegradation is high there is a heterogeneous temperature zone with decreasing moisture content. Moreover, in this stage a special temperature profile was found at the cross-sectional view of the tank. The second phase was more homogenous both in temperature and moisture content. This stage is the weak fermentation part of the technology results an elongated post fermentation section. It was established, that the changes of temperature and moisture content along the tank fermenter are the same and there is a strong connection between them in the examined period. Our results pointed out that the initial turning and mixing results in a large temperature and moisture content drop and later there is sufficient time for composting to take place. The authors recommend that this system could be used as an efficient treatment for chicken manure materials to decompose and get a valuable base organic fertilizer.

Key words: chicken manure, fermentation, decompose, temperature and moisture model

INTRODUCTION

Chicken manure is very high in nitrogen and also contains a good amount of potassium and phosphorus (Szabó et al., 2019). But, the chicken manure as waste from the poultry industry includes a mixture of excreta (manure, feces and urine), bedding material or litter (e.g. wood shavings or straw), waste feed, dead birds, broken egg sand feathers removed from poultry houses. Other wastes include those from cage, conveyer belt and water-flushing systems. Poultry manure is acquired through regular cleaning of the poultry house (Kobierski et al., 2017).

The litter and manure component of this waste has a high nutritional value and is used as an organic fertiliser, thus recycling nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium. These components (poultry litter) have traditionally been land spread on soil as an amendment. The mature

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compost can improve soil fertility and plant growth (Haga, 1999). However, immature compost applied to soil would cause N starvation (Bernal et al., 2009; Moral et al., 2009), phytotoxic effects, and presence of harmful microbes (Fang et al., 1999; Tiquia, Tam, 2000).

The high nitrogen and balanced nutrients is the reason that chicken manure compost is the best kind of manure to use. But the high nitrogen in the chicken manure is dangerous to plants if the manure has not been properly composted. Raw chicken manure fertilizer can burn, and even kill plants. Moreover, over-application of this material can lead to an enriching of water nutrients resulting in eutrophication of water bodies, the spread of pathogens, the production of phytotoxic substances, air pollution and emission of greenhouse gases (Fan et al., 2000; Kelleher et al., 2002). Bitzer and Sims, 1988, reported that excessive application of poultry litter in cropping systems can result in nitrate contamination of groundwater. Excessive application of fresh poultry manure on the farm may result to excess accumulation of ammonia hence may damage the crop roots (Köteles, Pereş, 2017; Tamás et al., 2017; Szöllősi et al., 2018). Proper handling of the manure can be achieved through proper manure composting and appropriate practices of feed management (Bolan et al., 2010).

The production process of chicken manure organic fertilizer is basically includes: selection of raw material (chicken manure, etc.), drying and sterilization, mixing of ingredients, granule, cooling and screening, metering and seal, finished product warehousing.

The complicated production process of chicken manure is: The raw materials of organic fertilizer will be fermented (decomposed) and then entered into the semi-wet material crushing machine; then adding the elements of NPK, such as nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium chloride, ammonium chloride, etc., to meet the required standards; then it is stirred by a blender and then in to the granulating mechanism; after coming out, it will be dried; then sifting through the sieve, and the qualified products will be packaged; the granulation that not be qualified will return to the granule to produce again.

Thus, the chicken manure must be decomposed before casting. The parasites in the chicken manure and the infectious agents will be killed and deodorized by the process of decomposition. A considerable body of literature exists concerning the composting facilities (Elwell et al., 1998; Tiquia, Tam, 1998) and physical operation of chicken litter (Raviv et al., 1999).

Decomposing is the aerobic degradation of biodegradable organic waste. It is a relatively fast biodegradation process, taking typically 4 - 6 weeks to reach a stabilised material. The composted material is odourless and fine textured with a low moisture content and can be used as an organic

fertiliser. Composted poultry litter is easy to handle and pathogen free. Disadvantages are cited as loss of nitrogen and other nutrients during composting, equipment cost and labour, odour and available land (Sweeten, 1988).

Decomposing processes affected by several factors. Temperature, moisture content, C/N ratio have a great effect on the decomposing processes. A high moisture content, of more than 75 %, inhibits a quick start to the composting process. The moisture content (or the degree of material drying) is a major influence on the decomposition rate and the tendency to stabilise, since the metabolic heat generation during decomposition drives evaporation. Factors that contribute to moisture loss include evaporation, leaching and aeration, natural or forced. Rynk et al., 1991, reported that moisture content should be maintained between 40 % and 60 % during the composting process, although Fernandes et al., 1994 have reported that successful composting of poultry manure mixed with peat or chopped straw has been obtained in a passive static-pile at high initial moisture levels (73 – 80 %).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The oval tank fermentation and drying technology is a Japanese-developed alternative method is to poultry and pig manure, launched in 1970, which is still being developed today.

A study was undertaken by Georgakakis and Krintas, 2000, to investigate and optimise a composting system known as the oval tank system in composting poultry manure in a typical layer poultry farm in Greece. The fermentation system is one of the two treatment systems that have been applied for the treatment of wastes. The other is the Okada system and both are of Japanese origin. Both systems are based on the operation of specially designed manure turning and chopping mechanical system (MTCM). The system consists of a series of rotating metallic knives or forks with which the waste is completely turned, aerated and gradually pushed to the end of the specific tank. This installation consists of an open, shallow, oval shaped concrete tank (Fig. 1). The standard size of the tank is 60 m x 8.3 m.

Fresh manure is batch fed daily to the oval tank and an equivalent quantity of final material is removed from the exit. The tank is filled with the waste material up to a total depth of 1.0 – 1.2 m. The stirring machine with double rotors results in continuous mixing of the manure in the fermentation tank.

Fig. 1. Arrangement and processes of industrial fermentation system

The MTCM in the fermentation system completes a full run along the oval tank in approx. 2.5 h. On a daily basis, a maximum of 5 full runs can then be completed. One complete run results in the displacement of 1.5 m of manure along the tank or a maximum of 7.5 - 8.0 m after 5 runs completed in 24 h. Therefore, the minimum travelling time for fresh manure to reach the exit of the 120 m long channel is 12 - 14 days. During the turning and pushing of manure by the MTCM, surrounding air is incorporated and moisture is lost by evaporation. The fermentation system controls the initial moisture content by mixing the incoming fresh manure with the recirculated dry old material in the channel and this helps to start the composting process. Moisture control of the material in the oval tank is necessary to avoid blockages of the MTCM operation (Hosoya & Co., 1996). A particle size of less than approx. 12 mm is formed from the initially muddy-textured raw material due to the turning effect of the MTCM in the oval channel. The reduction of particle size enhances degradation due to the greater surface area available to microbes and an increase in void space for oxygen.

In this paper the performance of the oval tank fermentation system is studied by taking samples of poultry manure during a run and analysing them for moisture content, dry matter content, different nitrogen forms such as organic nitrogen and inorganic forms (nitrate and ammonium). The temperature of the material during the fermentation was also monitored.

In the fermentation procedure deep litter chicken manure and dehydrated hen manure from the Kisvárda slaughterhouse are used as a raw material. The capacity of the plant is 11000 t/year, which is 30 t daily usage. The mixing ratio of the raw materials in the fermentation tank is partly broiler and partly chicken manure (33 and 66 %). The moisture content of incoming chicken manure is varied between 20 and 40 %. For the optimal fermentation the moisture of the raw material must be adjusted to 40 - 45 % moisture by adding water (150 l/intake).

In the technology, 3 - 5 cm thick fermented manure remains at the bottom of the fermentation tank as a microbial starter.

To create a model of temperature and moisture distribution of the oval tank temperature measurements and sample collecting were made. Temperature measurement and samples collected in May, June and July to represent the effect of hot and dry circumstances on the processes of the fermentation. Sampling sites were adjusted to the sensors of the tank and our earlier observations (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Sampling strategy

The temperature of the material was measured at three points. One was the middle of the tank and two measuring points were 30 cm from the edge of the tank. Every measuring point were on the bottom of the tank. Testo 922 mobile thermometer was used to temperature measuring. From collected samples the moisture content was determined by weight loss in laboratory ($T = 105\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) (MSZ-08-0221-1:1979). The moisture content was measured by drying in an oven at $105\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 12 h, or until no change in the dry weight was observed.

Modelling environment

The two dimensional version of the Hydrus software was used for modelling the water and temperature distribution in the oval tank during the biodegradation processes. The software applies finite element model for simulating the movement of water, heat, and multiple solutes in variably saturated media. The mathematical background of the software is the Richards equation for saturated-unsaturated water flow and convection-dispersion type equations for heat and solute transport.

Model description - Applied parameters and boundary conditions

The 2D geometry of the fertilizer oval tank was created as a first step, where the target finite element size was adjusted to 0.1 m. The duration of biodegradation processes was set to 14 days in the model according to the

fermentation technology. The applied main parameters of feed material were 800 kg/m^3 bulk density, 55 % solid content and 70 % organic material content. In addition, the previously carried out results of in situ water content and temperature measurements were used as initial conditions. Finally, “no flux” boundary condition was applied at the inner and outer circumference of the model tank.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. Sampling and measurement (May, 2019)

The highest moisture content (49.50 m/m %) was measured between the sampling points 1 and 2, where the feeding point can also be found (Fig. 3). After the input point, the moisture content starts to decrease rapidly within a few meters, as a result of the intensive heat generation of biodegradation processes. The other part of the oval tank (after turning point) shows a slightly decreasing moisture content until reaching the output point. At the end of the fermentation process, the moisture content stabilizes approximately at 12 %, which is appropriate for pellet production from the composted material by pressure agglomeration technologies.

Fig. 3. Moisture distribution model based on the measured parameters in May, 2019

The fermentation tank can be divided into two parts based on the temperature distribution model. Heterogeneous temperature was observed from feeding point to sampling point 12 among the inner (45 meters), centre and outer part of the tank (Fig. 4). The highest temperature values arise in the centre of the mentioned sampling cross sections (on average higher than $7.99 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ compared to the inner parts and $10.17 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ compared to the outer parts). Strong variability was found between the inner and outer parts of the tank proved by relatively higher standard deviation values ($\pm 7.30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at inner parts, $\pm 8.82 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at outer parts). After the turning point of the oval tank,

between sampling points 12 and 21 (76 meters) no significant difference was found in temperature values. The average temperature is 22 °C, where the standard deviation can be characterized by relatively low (± 0.55 °C) values. The temperature heterogeneity in the fermentation tank can be explained by the exact location of the stirring machine. According to the above mentioned, higher microbiological activity and heat generation were formed, where the stirring machine passed through earlier.

Fig. 4. Temperature distribution model based on the measured parameters in May, 2019

II. Sampling and measurement (June, 2019)

The moisture distribution model shows different characteristics compared to May, 2019, especially around the input point (Fig. 5). The highest moisture content (42.8 m/m %) was measured at the feeding point as in the previous month, however this value was adjusted for optimization at the beginning of the biodegradation processes and remained constant until the sampling point 9 (16.8 m).

Fig. 5. Moisture distribution model based on the measured parameters in June, 2019

A rapid decrease can be observed after the high moisture content section. The other part of the oval tank (after turning point) shows a slightly decreasing moisture content, similarly to the results of May, 2019. The moisture content of the output material represents approximately double the value compared to May (20.4 m/m %).

Similar temperature characteristics were formed in June, 2019, as in the previous month. The fermentation tank can be divided again into two zones with the same boundaries (sampling point 1-12 and sampling point 12-21) based on the temperature distribution (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Temperature distribution model based on the measured parameters in June, 2019

Heterogeneous temperatures were measured between sampling points 1 and 12 (strong fermentation zone), as a result the inner, centre and outer parts of the oval tank can be separated from each other. The centre part has the highest average temperature value (50.55 °C), higher on average than 7.27 °C compared to the inner parts and 3 °C compared to the outer parts. Weak fermentation zone was observed from the turning point (sampling point 13) to the output point. The average temperature in this zone is 33.42 °C, which is higher than 11.5 °C compared to the results of May, 2019. The calculated standard deviation is ± 1.54 °C, which means a higher temperature fluctuation in May. The ambient temperature was 26 °C.

III. Sampling and measurement (July, 2019)

The highest moisture contents were found between sampling points 2 and 5 (3 meters), which is the shortest section compared to the previous two months (Fig. 7). The maximum moisture content was 38.4 m/m % in the oval tank, representing the measured lowest maximum value during the three months long period. A local minimum value of moisture content can be observed at sampling point 6, thereafter the values start to increase until

reaching sampling point 11. At the other part of the fermentation tank, the moisture content stabilizes in narrow ranges (between 25.4 m/m % and 24.3 m/m %). The moisture content of the composted material is 22.6 m/m % at the output point.

Fig. 7. Moisture distribution model based on the measured parameters in July, 2019

The heterogeneous and homogeneous temperature zones cannot be separated sharply based on the temperature distribution model of July, 2019 compared to the previous months (Fig. 8). It can be seen, that the highest temperature values formed again in the middle part until reaching the sampling point 11. The average temperature of the middle part is 52.1°C, which can be characterized by relatively lower standard deviation values ($\pm 1.82^\circ\text{C}$). At the sampling points of inner and outer parts, lower temperature values were measured, where the data fluctuation is relatively high (standard deviation values: $\pm 4.97^\circ\text{C}$ and $\pm 5.05^\circ\text{C}$).

Fig. 8. Temperature distribution model based on the measured parameters in July, 2019

After the turning point of the stirring machine, the temperature tendency shows also heterogeneous distribution (average temperature of inner part: 38.08°C, average temperature of middle part: 36.65°C, average temperature of outer part: 33.99°C), supported by relatively high standard deviation values (inner part: $\pm 7.30^\circ\text{C}$, middle part: $\pm 6.58^\circ\text{C}$, outer part: $\pm 4.70^\circ\text{C}$). The ambient temperature was 26°C in the sampling date.

CONCLUSIONS

The performance and efficiency of an oval tank fermentation system studied by taking samples monthly from May to July of chicken manure during the run and analysing them for moisture content and temperature. The two dimensional version of the Hydrus software was used for modelling the moisture and temperature distribution in the oval tank during the biodegradation processes.

Our results pointed out that the initial turning and mixing results in a large temperature and moisture content drop. It was found that the studied oval tank fermenter can be divided into two main parts considering to the changing of temperature and moisture level. In the first phase, where the rate of biodegradation is high, there is a heterogeneous temperature zone with continuously decreasing moisture content of pile. Moreover, in this stage a special temperature profile was found at the cross-sectional view of the tank. The second phase was more homogenous both in temperature and moisture content. This stage is the weak fermentation part of the technology results an elongated post fermentation section. The changes of temperature and moisture content along the tank fermenter are the same and there is a strong connection between them in the examined period. Our results pointed out that after the initial, warmer “thermophilic” stage there is sufficient time for composting. Therefore, this system could be used as an efficient treatment for chicken manure materials to decompose and get a valuable base organic fertilizer.

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